

DERIVING AND ASSESSING THE GREEKS
FOR THE FOURIER-BASED PRICING OF EUROPEAN
OPTIONS
UNDER THE HESTON MODEL

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Dedication

To my family.

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ABSTRACT

We derive and implement *FFT-based Greeks* for European options by differentiating the Carr-Madan damped transform under the integral so that a *single* FFT call simultaneously delivers option price, Delta, Gamma, and the sensitivity with respect to initial variance $\partial C/\partial v_0$ (“Vega _{v_0} ”). This unified formulation reduces runtime compared to multiple FFT evaluations while preserving accuracy, as verified against high-precision quadrature. To ensure numerical stability we employ the Lord–Kahl “little trap” formulation of the Heston characteristic function (LordKahl2010, Heston1993).

The contribution is threefold. First, we establish theoretical and numerical consistency: in the Black–Scholes limit (deterministic variance) the FFT recovers closed forms (BlackScholes1973, Merton1973), while model-agnostic static-arbitrage constraints (Merton bounds, monotonicity/convexity in strike, $\Delta \in [0, e^{-qT}]$, $\Gamma \geq 0$) hold within explicit tolerances (Merton1973, BreedenLitzenberger1978). Second, we demonstrate computational efficiency of the single-FFT scheme via controlled benchmarks. Third, we test on live European options (Deribit), converting BTC quotes to USD where needed, and document short-maturity edge effects together with their mitigation via tighter FFT settings.

CHAPTER 1

Introduction

1. Financial Derivatives, Black–Scholes Model, and Hedging

In this section we introduce the fundamental notions in financial mathematics that form the basis for the subsequent analysis of stochastic volatility models.

DEFINITION 1.1 (Financial Derivative). *A financial derivative is a contract whose value depends on (or “derives from”) the value of one or more underlying assets such as stocks, bonds, commodities, or indices. Formally, if S_t denotes the underlying price process, a derivative payoff at maturity T is given by a function $H(S_T)$.*

Examples include forwards, futures, and options. Forwards fix a price today for future delivery, while options give the right (but not the obligation) to buy or sell at a predetermined price.

DEFINITION 1.2 (European Call and Put Options). *A European call option with strike K and maturity T has payoff*

$$C_T = (S_T - K)^+,$$

while a European put option has payoff

$$P_T = (K - S_T)^+,$$

where $(x)^+ = \max\{x, 0\}$.

DEFINITION 1.3 (No-Arbitrage and Risk-Neutral Measure). *The no-arbitrage principle states that in a frictionless market there exist no self-financing trading strategies with zero initial cost that yield a strictly positive profit with probability one. Under this assumption, there exists an equivalent martingale measure \mathbb{Q} (the risk-neutral measure) such that discounted asset prices $e^{-rt}S_t$ are martingales.*

DEFINITION 1.4 (Black–Scholes Model). *In the Black–Scholes framework, the asset price $(S_t)_{t \geq 0}$ follows a geometric Brownian motion under the risk-neutral measure:*

$$dS_t = (r - q)S_t dt + \sigma S_t dW_t^{\mathbb{Q}},$$

where r is the risk-free rate, q the dividend yield, $\sigma > 0$ the (volatility) parameter, and $W_t^{\mathbb{Q}}$ a standard Brownian motion.

Solving the associated PDE leads to the celebrated Black–Scholes closed-form solution for European option prices.

DEFINITION 1.5 (Volatility). *The volatility of an asset is the instantaneous standard deviation of returns. Formally, if $\ln S_t$ denotes the log-price, its quadratic variation satisfies*

$$d\langle \ln S \rangle_t = \sigma_t^2 dt.$$

If $\sigma_t \equiv \sigma$ is constant, we have the Black–Scholes model; if not, more advanced volatility models (local, stochastic, rough) are needed.

DEFINITION 1.6 (Option Greeks). *The Greeks are sensitivities of an option price $C(S, t)$ to model parameters. Key examples include:*

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta &= \frac{\partial C}{\partial S}, && (\text{sensitivity to price}) \\ \Gamma &= \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial S^2}, && (\text{convexity}) \\ \text{Vega} &= \frac{\partial C}{\partial \sigma}, && (\text{sensitivity to volatility}) \\ \Theta &= \frac{\partial C}{\partial t}, && (\text{time decay}) \\ \text{Rho} &= \frac{\partial C}{\partial r}, && (\text{sensitivity to rates}).\end{aligned}$$

These Greeks are essential for *hedging*, i.e. constructing portfolios that offset risk exposures. For example, a *Delta-hedged* portfolio is insensitive to small movements in the underlying asset.

2. Risk, Hedging, and Volatility in Finance

A central theme in finance is the balance between *expected return* and *risk*. Investors aim to maximize gains while simultaneously limiting exposure to uncertainty. Among the different measures of risk, the most widely adopted benchmark is *volatility*, which captures the variability of asset returns across time. This section introduces the concepts of risk and hedging, and shows how they naturally lead to volatility modeling as a fundamental problem in quantitative finance.

DEFINITION 2.1 (Risk in Finance). *Risk denotes the uncertainty associated with the value of an asset or portfolio at some future date. In mathematical finance, a risk measure is a functional ρ defined on a space of random variables X (e.g. returns) that quantifies the exposure to adverse outcomes.*

Examples of risk measures include variance, Value-at-Risk (VaR), and Conditional Value-at-Risk (CVaR). In classical portfolio theory, Markowitz [25] proposed variance as the canonical risk measure and formulated the mean–variance framework, which optimizes the trade-off between expected return and volatility.

DEFINITION 2.2 (Hedging). *Hedging is the practice of constructing a trading strategy that offsets or reduces exposure to a particular source of financial risk. Formally, if $C(S, t)$ denotes the value of a derivative contract, a hedging strategy is a self-financing portfolio $\Pi_t = \phi_t S_t + \psi_t B_t$ in the underlying asset S_t and a risk-free asset B_t designed to replicate or stabilize the payoff of C .*

In practice, hedging is frequently performed by neutralizing sensitivities, known as the *Greeks*. For instance, a *Delta-hedge* eliminates first-order exposure to changes in the underlying price.

From a statistical viewpoint, a natural way to quantify variability is by using the sample variance of log-returns:

$$\hat{\sigma}^2 = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \left(\log \frac{S(t)}{S(t-1)} \right)^2.$$

This representation, motivated by Samuelson, reflects the fact that asset prices are positive and are often modeled as exponentials of random variables. If returns follow

$$\frac{S(t)}{S(t-1)} = e^{\xi_t}, \quad \xi_t \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2),$$

then $\hat{\sigma}$ provides a consistent estimator of the volatility parameter σ . This reasoning underpins the classical Black–Scholes–Merton framework [2, 26].

However, the assumption of constant volatility is empirically inadequate. Measurements of $\hat{\sigma}$ vary significantly depending on the time window, demonstrating that markets alternate between tranquil and turbulent periods. As argued in Di Nunno et al. [15], volatility itself must be regarded as stochastic: it fluctuates over time in a manner not explained entirely by macroeconomic factors.

Recognizing volatility as a random process has profound implications for finance. It plays a central role in option pricing, portfolio construction, and risk management. This motivates the study of *stochastic volatility models*, with the Heston model providing one of the most influential and analytically tractable examples.

3. Volatility: Concept, Role, and Models

Volatility is one of the central concepts in quantitative finance. Beyond its straightforward use in portfolio risk assessment and diversification (cf. the foundational mean–variance theory of Markowitz [25]), volatility acquires a deeper and more intricate role within the theory of arbitrage–free pricing of derivatives, pioneered by Black, Scholes and Merton [2, 26]. In this framework, volatility is not merely a statistical measure of dispersion, but a key input driving the dynamics of asset prices, option values, and hedging strategies. The way volatility is modeled has therefore been a major driving force in mathematical finance over the past five decades (see, e.g., Di Nunno et al. [15] for a recent survey).

DEFINITION 3.1 (Volatility). *Let $(S_t)_{t \geq 0}$ denote the price process of an asset. The instantaneous volatility σ_t is defined formally through the quadratic variation of the log–price process,*

$$d\langle \ln S \rangle_t = \sigma_t^2 dt.$$

If $\sigma_t \equiv \sigma$ is constant, we speak of constant volatility (as in the Black–Scholes model). If σ_t is time–dependent or random, one enters the domain of stochastic volatility models.

In practice, two principal notions are widely used:

- *Historical (realized) volatility*, estimated statistically from past returns, e.g.

$$\hat{\sigma}^2 = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n (\ln S_{t_j} - \ln S_{t_{j-1}})^2.$$

- *Implied volatility*, defined implicitly by inverting the Black–Scholes formula so that the model price matches a market option price.

The implied volatility surface $(K, T) \mapsto \sigma_{\text{impl}}(K, T)$ is known to be nonconstant in both strike K and maturity T , leading to the *volatility smile* or *skew*. This empirical fact contradicts the constant–volatility assumption of Black–Scholes and motivates more refined modeling frameworks.

DEFINITION 3.2 (Volatility smile/skew). *The volatility smile refers to the observed U–shaped dependence of implied volatility on strike K for fixed maturity T . When asymmetry is present, the term volatility skew is often used. Formally,*

$$\sigma_{\text{impl}}(K, T) \neq \text{constant in } K.$$

Several approaches to volatility modeling exist:

- (1) **Deterministic volatility models**, where $\sigma(t)$ is a known function of time. These capture term–structure effects but not random fluctuations.
- (2) **Local volatility models**, e.g. Dupire’s formula, where $\sigma(t, S_t)$ is a deterministic function calibrated to the full implied volatility surface.
- (3) **Stochastic volatility models**, where $(\sigma_t)_{t \geq 0}$ is itself a stochastic process (e.g. Heston, Hull–White, SABR). These models reproduce smiles and skews more naturally and capture volatility clustering.
- (4) **Rough volatility models**, where volatility is driven by fractional Brownian motion, producing short–time behaviors consistent with high–frequency data (see [15]).

The classification into *discrete* versus *continuous* volatility models is also important. Discrete–time GARCH–type models are prevalent in econometrics and risk management, whereas continuous–time stochastic volatility models dominate the arbitrage–free pricing literature. Both perspectives are consistent but serve different purposes: the former for statistical forecasting, the latter for pricing and hedging derivatives in continuous time.

We can see: the volatility is not merely a parameter but a process in its own right. Its accurate modeling is essential both for explaining the volatility smile and for providing stable hedging parameters (the Greeks). The Heston model, which we study in this thesis, belongs to the class of continuous–time stochastic volatility models with affine structure, and has become one of the most widely used benchmarks in quantitative finance.

4. From Black–Scholes to Heston: Limitations and Extensions

The Black–Scholes–Merton (BSM) model [2, 26] provides the canonical framework for modern option pricing. It assumes that the underlying asset S_t follows a geometric Brownian motion

$$dS_t = rS_t dt + \sigma S_t dW_t,$$

with constant volatility $\sigma > 0$ and risk-free rate r . Under this assumption, $\log(S_T/S_0)$ is normally distributed with variance $\sigma^2 T$, implying that returns are Gaussian with thin tails and that implied volatility should be constant across strikes and maturities.

Empirical limitations. Financial data, however, reveals systematic departures from these assumptions:

- *Fat tails.* Empirical return distributions exhibit higher kurtosis than the Gaussian law predicts. A Q–Q plot of log-returns against the normal quantiles shows systematic deviations in the tails, reflecting extreme market moves.
- *Volatility smile/skew.* Observed option prices imply a volatility surface that depends on strike and maturity. Instead of a flat line, implied volatilities form a *smile* or *skew*, especially pronounced for short maturities.
- *Clustering.* Periods of high volatility tend to cluster, followed by more tranquil intervals, contradicting the independence and stationarity assumed in BSM.

FIGURE 1. These two empirical plots from SPY (S&P 500 ETF) clearly demonstrate that market volatility is not constant. The upper panel shows rolling 21-day annualized volatility, which fluctuates between calm and turbulent periods—if volatility were constant, the curve would be flat. The lower panel plots squared log-returns, which exhibit bursts of large values followed by quiet phases—this temporal grouping of volatility, known as *volatility clustering*, directly contradicts the constant- σ assumption of classical models and motivates stochastic volatility frameworks such as Heston (1993) and Gatheral (2006).

FIGURE 2. Implied volatility of SPY call options across moneyness. **Interpretation:** If volatility were constant, the implied volatility would be flat across strike prices—yet, as seen here, it declines for deep in-the-money options and rises again for deep out-of-the-money ones, forming the characteristic *volatility smile* (or skew). This pattern shows that market participants assign higher volatility to extreme price moves, meaning volatility itself is *state-dependent*. Such behaviour cannot be captured by the constant- σ Black–Scholes model and motivates models where volatility follows its own stochastic process—exactly the idea formalized in Heston [20] and explored empirically by Gatheral [19]

FIGURE 3. Empirical evidence from SPY (S&P 500 ETF) daily log-returns illustrating the departure from the Gaussian assumption. The right panel compares the empirical histogram of returns with a fitted $\text{Normal}(\mu, \sigma)$ curve. The data show clearly heavier tails than predicted by the normal distribution, indicating that large price movements occur more frequently than a constant-volatility model would allow. The left panel presents the QQ-plot of empirical versus theoretical quantiles. If returns were normally distributed (and volatility constant), all points would align with the red diagonal line. Instead, both tails deviate significantly from the line—an indication of excess kurtosis and non-Gaussian behaviour. Together, these plots confirm that volatility is not constant but varies through time, supporting stochastic-volatility formulations.

These phenomena cannot be reconciled within the constant-volatility setting. As Gatheral emphasizes in [19], the volatility smile is not a market imperfection but rather a fundamental feature of option markets.

Towards stochastic volatility models. To address these issues, stochastic volatility models have been developed. Among them, the Heston model [20] is particularly influential due to its tractable characteristic function and ability to reproduce volatility smiles while retaining semi-closed form pricing formulas. In the Heston framework, volatility itself evolves as a mean-reverting square-root process:

$$dv_t = \kappa(\theta - v_t) dt + \sigma\sqrt{v_t} dW_t^v,$$

correlated with the asset's Brownian motion dW_t^S . This extension captures both the clustering of volatility and the skewness of implied volatilities.

5. The Heston Model

Heston (1993) models variance as a mean-reverting square-root (CIR) diffusion, under the risk-neutral measure \mathbb{Q} :

$$(1) \quad \begin{aligned} dS_t &= (r - q)S_t dt + \sqrt{v_t} S_t dW_t^{(1)}, \\ dv_t &= \kappa(\theta - v_t) dt + \sigma\sqrt{v_t} dW_t^{(2)}, \quad d\langle W^{(1)}, W^{(2)} \rangle_t = \rho dt. \end{aligned}$$

Parameters: κ (speed of mean reversion), θ (long-run variance), σ (vol-of-vol), ρ (price/variance correlation, often negative in equities), and v_0 (initial variance). The Feller condition $2\kappa\theta \geq \sigma^2$ prevents v_t from hitting zero [20].

Variance behaves like a noisy spring pulled toward θ (strength κ), with random shakes sized by σ . The correlation ρ encodes the leverage effect: a negative shock to price tends to increase variance ($\rho < 0$), producing realistic skew. Despite this realism, the model remains *analytically tractable*: European prices follow from a *closed-form characteristic function* of $\log S_T$.

Model Parameters and Their Interpretation. The Heston model (1) introduces several parameters. They can be divided into *market parameters* (observable or set exogenously) and *model parameters* (estimated/calibrated to option data):

- S_0 : **Initial asset price** at time $t = 0$.
- r : **Risk-free interest rate**, assumed constant under the risk-neutral measure.
- q : **Continuous dividend yield** (or foreign risk-free rate in FX), which reduces the drift of S_t .
- T : **Option maturity**, time horizon for pricing and hedging.
- $x_t = \log S_t$: **Log-price** of the asset, useful in Fourier methods.
- v_t : **Instantaneous variance** of returns. The square root $\sqrt{v_t}$ is the instantaneous volatility.
- v_0 : **Initial variance**, the starting value of v_t .
- κ : **Mean reversion speed**, controls how quickly v_t is pulled back to its long-run mean.
- θ : **Long-run variance**, the level around which v_t fluctuates.
- σ : **Volatility of volatility** (vol-of-vol), determines how erratic the variance path is.
- ρ : **Correlation** between the Brownian motions $W^{(1)}$ and $W^{(2)}$, encoding the leverage effect (typically $\rho < 0$ for equities).
- $dW^{(1)}, dW^{(2)}$: **Brownian shocks** to the asset and variance, respectively.
- $\tau = T - t$: **Time to maturity**, often appears in characteristic function formulas.
- $k = \log K$: **Log-strike** of the option, natural variable in FFT pricing.
- α : **Dampening parameter** in Carr-Madan FFT, chosen to ensure integrability of the payoff transform.
- $u \in \mathbb{C}$: **Fourier variable**, used when applying characteristic functions.

Together, these parameters control both the asset dynamics and the numerical implementation. The set $(\kappa, \theta, \sigma, \rho, v_0)$ is calibrated to market option prices, while (r, q, S_0) are given by market data.

6. More About Heston Model: The Heston Characteristic Function

Set $x_t := \log S_t$. From (1),

$$dx_t = \left((r-q) - \frac{1}{2}v_t \right) dt + \sqrt{v_t} dW_t^{(1)}, \quad dv_t = \kappa(\theta - v_t)dt + \sigma\sqrt{v_t} dW_t^{(2)}, \quad d\langle W^{(1)}, W^{(2)} \rangle_t = \rho dt.$$

Let $\tau := T - t$ and define the conditional characteristic function

$$\phi(u, \tau; x, v) := \mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}}[e^{iux\tau} \mid x_t = x, v_t = v]$$

By the affine property of (1), look for a solution of the exponential-affine form

$$(2) \quad \phi(u, \tau; x, v) = \exp\left(C(u, \tau) + D(u, \tau)v + iux\right).$$

Applying the Feynman-Kac PDE to ϕ and substituting (2) yields the coupled ODEs

$$(3) \quad \frac{dD}{d\tau} = \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2 D^2 + (\rho\sigma iu - \kappa)D + \frac{1}{2}(u^2 + iu), \quad D(u, 0) = 0,$$

$$(4) \quad \frac{dC}{d\tau} = \kappa\theta D + iu(r - q), \quad C(u, 0) = 0.$$

Solving (3)–(4) gives the standard closed forms (write $d(u)$ and $g(u)$ for compactness):

$$(5) \quad d(u) = \sqrt{(\rho\sigma iu - \kappa)^2 + \sigma^2(u^2 + iu)}, \quad g(u) = \frac{\kappa - \rho\sigma iu - d(u)}{\kappa - \rho\sigma iu + d(u)}.$$

$$(6) \quad D(u, \tau) = \frac{\kappa - \rho\sigma iu - d(u)}{\sigma^2} \frac{1 - e^{-d(u)\tau}}{1 - g(u)e^{-d(u)\tau}}$$

$$(7) \quad C(u, \tau) = iu(r - q)\tau + \frac{\kappa\theta}{\sigma^2} \left((\kappa - \rho\sigma iu - d(u))\tau - 2 \log \frac{1 - g(u)e^{-d(u)\tau}}{1 - g(u)} \right).$$

Thus the characteristic function of $X_T := \log S_T$ is

$$(8) \quad \phi(u) = \exp\left(C(u, \tau) + D(u, \tau)v_0 + iux_t\right).$$

Branch choice. Because the complex logarithm is multi-valued, numerical stability requires a consistent branch across u and τ ; see [1] for the “little Heston trap” fix. The form (5)–(7) together with a continuous choice of $\log(\cdot)$ along the integration contour is robust in practice [19, Ch. 2].

7. “Semi-closed” Heston Formula and the Role of ϕ

With the CF in hand, Heston’s semi-closed call price reads

$$(9) \quad C(K, T) = S_0 e^{-q\tau} P_1(K) - K e^{-r\tau} P_2(K),$$

where the probabilities P_j are computed from one-dimensional integrals of ϕ :

$$(10) \quad P_j(K) = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^\infty \Re \left[\frac{e^{-iuk}}{iu} \exp\left(C_j(u, \tau) + D_j(u, \tau)v_0 + iux_0\right) \right] du, \quad k := \log K,$$

with (C_1, D_1) and (C_2, D_2) corresponding to slightly different drifts in the Riccati system (see [20, 19] for the precise definitions). Formula (9) is called *semi-closed* because pricing reduces to a single real integral (no PDE grid or MC needed).

8. From the Characteristic Function to Fast Pricing: Carr-Madan FFT

The Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) is an algorithm that evaluates the discrete Fourier transform (DFT) and its inverse in $O(N \log N)$ operations, improving drastically upon the naive $O(N^2)$ complexity of direct matrix multiplication. For a sequence $\{x_n\}_{n=0}^{N-1}$, the DFT is defined as

$$X_k = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} x_n e^{-2\pi i k n / N}, \quad k = 0, 1, \dots, N-1.$$

The FFT exploits symmetries and periodicities in the complex exponentials (the so-called twiddle factors¹) to reorganize the computation into a recursive divide-and-conquer scheme. This leads to exponential gains in speed when N is large, which is essential in applications where transforms must be computed repeatedly or on high-resolution grids [12].

Intuitively, the FFT is a way of “listening to the hidden frequencies” inside a signal, but doing so without wasting time. Instead of summing every oscillation against every other, the FFT cleverly groups together repeating patterns so that the same multiplications are reused many times. In practice, this means that problems which would take hours to solve with brute-force Fourier methods can often be completed in seconds with FFT. This efficiency has made FFT one of the most important algorithms in numerical analysis, with applications ranging from signal processing to option pricing, where an entire spectrum of strikes can be computed in one sweep.

Informally, the breakthrough of Carr and Madan (1999) was to recognize that option prices, when viewed as functions of the strike in logarithmic form, are essentially Fourier transforms of the underlying characteristic function. The central idea was simple yet powerful: if one slightly modifies (“damps”) the payoff to make it square-integrable, then standard FFT algorithms can be applied to recover an entire strip of option prices across strikes with a single $O(N \log N)$ computation. This insight connected the needs of financial engineering computing thousands of prices quickly and consistently with decades of developments in numerical harmonic analysis, and it showed that FFT, originally designed for signal processing, could revolutionize derivative pricing.

To exploit FFT, Carr and Madan [9] damp the call in log-strike $k = \log K$: $c_\alpha(k) := e^{\alpha k} C(k)$ with $\alpha > 0$ large enough that $c_\alpha \in L^2$. The Fourier transform has the analytic form

$$(11) \quad \widehat{c}_\alpha(u) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{iuk} c_\alpha(k) dk = e^{-r\tau} \frac{\phi(u - i(\alpha + 1))}{\alpha^2 + \alpha - u^2 + i(2\alpha + 1)u}.$$

Thus, if we evaluate the right-hand side of (11) on an evenly spaced grid $u_m = m\Delta u$, $m = 0, \dots, N-1$, the inverse transform on an evenly spaced $k_n = n\Delta k$ with $\Delta k \Delta u = 2\pi/N$ is an *FFT*. This returns prices for an entire strip of strikes in one $O(N \log N)$ operation.

Vectorized kernel for implementation. In practice one computes the array

$$\Psi_m := e^{-r\tau} \frac{\phi(u_m - i(\alpha + 1))}{\alpha^2 + \alpha - u_m^2 + i(2\alpha + 1)u_m}, \quad u_m = m\Delta u,$$

optionally multiplied by Simpson weights to reduce truncation error, and then applies one FFT. Because Ψ is formed by elementwise operations on the whole u -grid, the computation is naturally *vectorized* and BLAS-friendly (basic linear algebra subprograms - standard

¹Twiddle factors are the complex roots of unity $W_N^k = e^{-2\pi i k / N}$ used in the FFT algorithm. They represent the fundamental building blocks of the discrete Fourier transform, encoding both the rotational symmetry and periodic structure of complex exponentials. By reusing these factors across recursive stages, the FFT avoids redundant computations, reducing the cost from $\mathcal{O}(N^2)$ to $\mathcal{O}(N \log N)$.

library with optimized implementations providing highly efficient routines for vector and matrix operations).

Practical choices. Typical settings: $\alpha \in [1, 2]$ (often $\alpha = 1.5$), $N = 2^{12}-2^{16}$, Δu small enough that the log-strike window $[-K_{\max}, K_{\max}]$ covers traded strikes. Zero-padding and mild windowing² can reduce aliasing. For Heston, one must take care of the branch handling of (5)–(6) as recommended in [24, 1]. We will give more details about these in Chapter 4.

When is FFT particularly attractive? When you need a dense slice of strikes/maturities. One evaluation of (11) plus a single FFT produces thousands of prices, typically orders of magnitude faster than calling a scalar quadrature per strike.

Towards extensions of Carr-Madan views. While Carr-Madan’s framework established that one FFT can recover an entire strip of option prices across strikes, their focus was purely on pricing. Greeks are typically obtained either by finite differences or by running separate FFTs for each sensitivity, which multiplies cost and numerical noise. In this thesis we extend the Fourier approach by *differentiating the damped transform under the integral*, so that Price, Delta, Gamma and the sensitivity with respect to the initial variance ($\partial C/\partial v_0$) emerge as columns of a *single batched FFT*. This reduces runtime, enforces internal consistency across Greeks, and provides a stable, unified computational framework for hedging analysis under the Heston model. It should be emphasized that the computation of Greeks under the Heston model is not a new idea in itself. Several works have addressed sensitivities in Fourier or transform-based settings, but usually either via separate FFT evaluations or alternative simulation schemes. For example, [11] develop FFT-based pricing and sensitivity analysis for stochastic volatility models, while [5] provide exact simulation methods for Heston and related affine jump diffusions, enabling finite-difference estimation of Greeks in Monte Carlo settings. Our contribution differs in that we *differentiate the Carr-Madan transform under the integral*, allowing Price, Delta, Gamma, and variance-sensitivity to be recovered simultaneously from a *single batched FFT*. This approach improves both computational efficiency and numerical consistency across sensitivities, and provides a framework particularly well-suited for hedging studies on strike grids.

Moving forward. Our thesis’ starting point is the FFT pricing under the Heston model.

- In Chapter 2 we offer a literature review of the relevant work published in this direction.
- A very brief Chapter 3 follows, offering the exposition of Research Strategy and Methodology as well as outline of the thesis.
- Chapter 4 is mainly based on the Carr-Madan work [9] and revolves around the Heston characteristic function and its derivatives, making the theoretical background and the framework of the FFT based pricing. In Chapter 4, in particular, we develop in the Section 2.5 the Single-FFT, multi-Greek formulation based on [24] work and our own formulation.
- Chapter 5 brings the analysis, testing the developments, benchmarking, stability checks as well as testing for logical and numerical consistency of the proposed

²*Zero-padding* extends the sampled function with zeros beyond its original domain before applying the FFT. This increases frequency resolution and mitigates wrap-around effects caused by the FFT’s implicit periodicity. *Windowing* multiplies the integrand by a smooth taper function (e.g., Hann or Hamming window) to reduce discontinuities at the domain boundaries. Both techniques help suppress spectral *aliasing* - spurious oscillations or distortions that arise when nonperiodic data are treated as periodic by the FFT.

method. This part is grounded on the synthetic i.e. by a program produced data and coding that coordinates and computes the outputs and compares them against the well-known FFT-prices.

- Chapter 6 goes into empirical data and shows that the method also works on real-life data - we use the same coding as in Chapter 5, just now applied on the real-time pulled data.
- The thesis is concluded with a summary of results and reflection on the lessons we can learn in the final chapter - Conclusion.
- In order to maintain the focus on the mainstream of the thesis and not overwhelm the reader with more technical terms, the reader is offered appendices: 1) on technical terms, that contains the definitions and explanations of more or less technical terms which we use throughout the thesis and are mostly known to the specialists in the field; 2) on coding (on which most of Chapter 5 and Chapter 6 is based); and 3) we include an appendix on some history of the problem and its importance for quantitative finance.

Literature Review

1. Stein and Stein (1991): An Analytic Stochastic Volatility Model

Prior to Heston’s formulation, Stein and Stein (1991) proposed an analytic stochastic volatility model in which volatility follows an Ornstein-Uhlenbeck (OU) process. This framework allowed volatility to vary stochastically over time, in contrast with the constant-volatility assumption of Black-Scholes. Importantly, Stein and Stein were among the first to provide analytic tractability in a stochastic volatility setting.

A key simplifying assumption in their model is that volatility is uncorrelated with the underlying asset price. This assumption facilitates closed-form solutions, but limits the model’s ability to capture the volatility skew and smile effects observed in equity and currency options. In practice, empirical evidence strongly supports negative correlation between volatility and returns (the so-called “leverage effect”), which the Stein-Stein model cannot reproduce.

Nevertheless, the Stein-Stein approach represents an important step in the evolution of stochastic volatility models. It demonstrated that analytic pricing was possible beyond the Black-Scholes paradigm, and it provided a natural benchmark against which more advanced models, such as Heston’s correlated variance process, could be developed. By situating Heston’s work in relation to Stein and Stein, we see more clearly the progression from early tractable but restrictive SV models to the more realistic yet still analytically manageable Heston model.

2. Heston (1993): A Closed-Form Solution for Stochastic Volatility

The Black-Scholes model [2] provides a closed-form solution for European option pricing, but relies on the assumption of constant volatility. While this assumption yields tractable results, it fails to capture observed empirical features such as volatility smiles and skews. To address this, several stochastic volatility (SV) models were introduced in the late 1980s. Scott (1987), Hull and White (1987), and Wiggins (1987) proposed models in which volatility itself follows a diffusion process. These early approaches offered a more realistic description of markets, but they typically lacked closed-form solutions and required computationally expensive numerical methods, such as solving partial differential equations in two dimensions.

Other attempts, such as those by Jarrow and Eisberg (1991) and Stein and Stein (1991), assumed that volatility is uncorrelated with the underlying asset and used averaged Black-Scholes prices. These models, however, imposed restrictive assumptions and were not well-suited to explaining the pronounced skewness effects in option prices.

Heston (1993) introduced a stochastic volatility model that overcame these limitations by providing a closed-form solution for European options based on the model’s characteristic function. The key innovation was to allow volatility to follow a mean-reverting square-root process (Cox–Ingersoll–Ross type) and to be correlated with the underlying asset. This correlation term enabled the model to reproduce both skew and smile effects in implied volatilities, while retaining analytical tractability for vanilla options.

The Heston model thus became a cornerstone of modern quantitative finance: it balances realism (stochastic, correlated volatility) with tractability (closed-form characteristic function). Its influence extends to equity, currency, and fixed-income derivatives, and it laid the foundation for the application of Fourier transform methods in option pricing. Nevertheless, the model also introduces numerical challenges, such as moment explosions and branch cut ambiguities in the characteristic function, which later works (e.g. Albrecher et al., 2007; Cui et al., 2017) would address.

3. Carr and Madan (1999): Option Valuation Using the Fast Fourier Transform

Although the Heston model provides a closed-form expression for the characteristic function of the log-price, the efficient numerical evaluation of option prices across a wide range of strikes remained a challenge. Traditional quadrature methods could be slow, especially when pricing many options simultaneously. Carr and Madan (1999) addressed this problem by introducing the use of the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) for option valuation.

The central idea was to exploit the Fourier transform of a damped option price function. By introducing a damping parameter $\alpha > 0$, Carr and Madan ensured that the transformed payoff was square-integrable, allowing the Fourier transform to be applied. The inverse transform then yielded option values for a continuum of strikes. Discretization of the Fourier integral on an evenly spaced grid enabled the direct use of the FFT algorithm, reducing computational complexity from $\mathcal{O}(N^2)$ to $\mathcal{O}(N \log N)$.

This method represented a breakthrough in numerical option pricing: it provided a fast and stable way to compute an entire option surface (many strikes) at once, which is particularly useful for calibration of models like Heston. The Carr-Madan framework also laid the groundwork for subsequent improvements and extensions, such as the COS method of Fang and Oosterlee (2009), and is now standard in both academic and practitioner toolkits.

Despite its efficiency, the FFT approach requires careful parameter choices for the damping factor α , grid size N , and step size $\Delta\eta$. Poor choices can lead to numerical oscillations or truncation errors. Furthermore, while Carr and Madan focused on pricing, the same framework can be extended to the computation of Greeks by differentiating the integrands, an aspect that remains underexplored in the literature and motivates the present research.

4. Fang and Oosterlee (2009): The COS Method

Fang and Oosterlee (2009) in [16] introduced the Fourier-Cosine (COS) method for pricing European options. Their approach is based on expanding the probability density function in a truncated Fourier-cosine series, which allows option prices to be computed as rapidly converging series. Compared with Carr-Madan FFT inversion, the COS method achieves very high accuracy with relatively few terms, and avoids some of the damping and truncation issues inherent to FFT implementations. The COS method has been widely adopted and extended to stochastic volatility and Lévy models. In the present thesis, however, we concentrate on the FFT framework, reserving the COS method as a potential benchmark for numerical accuracy.

5. Schmelzle (2010): Fourier Transform Methods in Option Pricing

Schmelzle (2010) in [29] provides a comprehensive survey of Fourier-based methods for option pricing, with particular emphasis on transform techniques that exploit the

availability of closed-form characteristic functions under models such as Heston, Bates, and related exponential Lévy processes. The paper reviews several formulations of the Fourier pricing integral, including the Carr-Madan FFT approach, Lewis’ contour integral representation, and Attari’s modification, and it evaluates their numerical performance in practice.

A key contribution of this work is its systematic comparison of quadrature techniques and implementation refinements. Schmelzle discusses numerical stability, the role of damping factors, and the accuracy of different inversion formulas. The paper highlights how parameter choices, such as grid size and discretization step, affect convergence and computational efficiency. By presenting the methods side by side, it clarifies the common mathematical structure that underlies transform-based pricing methods, positioning them as a unifying framework for both stochastic volatility and jump-diffusion models.

Although Schmelzle does not derive option sensitivities (Greeks), the survey underscores the flexibility of Fourier approaches and their central role in modern computational finance. For the purposes of this thesis, Schmelzle’s exposition provides a practical reference point on Fourier inversion and numerical implementation. It also motivates extending these methods beyond pricing to the computation of Greeks, an area that remains relatively unexplored and which this work seeks to address under the Heston model.

6. Chan, Joshi, and Zhu (2010): First and Second Order Greeks in the Heston Model

Chan, Joshi, and Zhu (2010) in [10] provide one of the earliest systematic attempts to compute both first- and second-order Greeks in the Heston model using algorithmic differentiation (AD). Their work bridges a major gap in the literature: while efficient simulation schemes for the Heston process were well developed (Broadie–Kaya, 2006; Andersen, 2008; Alfonsi, 2010), very little had been published on the stability of Greeks under these schemes. The authors argue that since hedging and risk management critically depend on sensitivities, it is not sufficient to evaluate prices accurately — the Greeks must also be robust.

The paper develops a hybrid approach that combines the pathwise method with the likelihood ratio method (LRM) to handle discontinuities in non-Lipschitz schemes such as the Quadratic-Exponential (QE), Double Gamma (DG), and Integrated Double Gamma (IDG) discretizations. Using adjoint algorithmic differentiation, they show how both gradients and Hessians of option prices can be computed efficiently in Monte Carlo settings. Numerical experiments highlight that naive applications of the pathwise method lead to unstable or fat-tailed distributions for Greeks (especially with QE or LN schemes), whereas DG and IDG produce more stable and reliable estimates. Their implementation of backward-mode AD further reduces complexity and makes the evaluation of second-order Greeks (such as Gamma and cross-Greeks) computationally feasible.

This study is important for two reasons. First, it clarifies how discretization choices directly impact the accuracy and stability of sensitivities — a point often overlooked when focusing only on option prices. Second, it demonstrates that AD techniques can extend beyond first-order derivatives, providing a general framework for higher-order Greeks. For our purposes, this work motivates the idea that Fourier-based methods (Carr–Madan FFT, COS method) could also be differentiated in a semi-analytical manner to obtain Greeks more efficiently, thus avoiding the instabilities of purely simulation-based approaches.

7. Capriotti and Giles (2011): Adjoint Algorithmic Differentiation and Greeks

Capriotti and Giles (2011) in [7] introduce adjoint algorithmic differentiation (AAD) as a systematic programming paradigm for computing price sensitivities in Monte Carlo simulations. Unlike finite-difference approaches, whose cost grows linearly with the number of parameters, AAD allows the computation of a full set of Greeks at a computational cost bounded by roughly four times that of the original pricing calculation. This represents a dramatic improvement in efficiency, especially for large portfolios and high-dimensional models.

The paper emphasizes the practicality of AAD: by viewing pricing algorithms as compositions of differentiable operations, one can propagate adjoint variables backward through the code to obtain sensitivities with minimal analytical effort. Examples are provided for diffusion models and the Libor Market Model, showing that AAD-based implementations achieve order-of-magnitude speed-ups over finite-difference “bumping.” The significance of this contribution lies in making comprehensive risk reporting computationally feasible in real time, thereby addressing a major bottleneck in quantitative risk management.

8. De Olivera and Mordecki (2014): Greeks for Lévy Models via Fourier Transform

De Olivera and Mordecki (2014) in [27] present a comprehensive framework for computing Greeks of European options in exponential Lévy models using Fourier transform techniques. Building on the Lewis (2001) representation of option prices, they show that sensitivities of any order with respect to both underlying and model parameters can be derived by differentiating under the integral sign. This yields semi-closed expressions for Delta, Gamma, Vega, Rho, Theta, and higher-order Greeks. A key advantage of their method is that numerical error arises only from the approximation of the Fourier integral, which can be efficiently evaluated with the FFT. This ensures both accuracy and computational tractability.

The authors provide explicit derivations for Call options, extend the method to second- and third-order Greeks, and test accuracy by benchmarking against the Black–Scholes model. They further demonstrate applications to the Merton jump-diffusion and Variance Gamma models, showing that their Fourier-based Greeks achieve high precision with relatively low computational cost. The paper’s central contribution lies in moving beyond prices to a full menu of sensitivities within the Fourier transform framework, setting a methodological foundation that motivates our extension of these ideas to the Heston stochastic volatility model.

9. Cao and Lin (2024): Examination of Heston Model Theory and Practice

Cao and Lin (2024) present a detailed study of the Heston model, combining both theoretical derivations and empirical applications. Their thesis begins by carefully revisiting the derivation of Heston’s closed-form solution and then validates it through Monte Carlo simulation methods, including both crude Monte Carlo and a more efficient “mixing” Monte Carlo scheme. The authors use these simulations not only to reproduce option prices but also to derive the Greeks (Delta, Gamma, Vega, Theta, Rho) by differentiating within the simulation framework. This provides a comprehensive demonstration of how sensitivities behave under different parameter values and validates the internal consistency of the model.

A major contribution of this work lies in its empirical calibration. Using WTI crude oil option data, the authors employ gradient descent and machine learning techniques to

fit the five Heston parameters. They examine the stability of parameters across maturities and maturities, and highlight limitations such as the instability of η (volatility of volatility) and ρ (correlation) when fitted to market data. By connecting model-implied volatility curves to parameter behavior, the thesis shows how theoretical insights can be aligned with market patterns. This framework—moving from derivation, simulation, Greeks, implied volatilities, and calibration—offers a methodological roadmap that we aim to extend with Fourier-based techniques for computing Greeks more efficiently.

Problem Setting

1. Research Strategy and Methodology

Methodologically, we follow the Fourier-based sensitivity differentiation of de Oliveira and Mordecki (2014) and the empirical workflow of Cao and Lin (2024), and we implement pricing/FFT according to Carr and Madan (1999) using Heston’s characteristic function (Heston, 1993).

Step 1: Stable characteristic function and differentiability. Adopt a numerically stable representation of the Heston CF $\phi(u; T) = \exp\{C(u, T) + D(u, T)v_0 + i u \ln S_0\}$ (Heston, 1993; see also stable forms in later literature). Exploit its structure to obtain analytic derivatives needed for Greek integrands:

$$\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial S_0} = \frac{i u}{S_0} \phi, \quad \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial S_0^2} = \frac{i u(i u - 1)}{S_0^2} \phi, \quad \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial v_0} = D(u, T) \phi.$$

These are the key building blocks to move from price integrals to Greek integrals (de Oliveira and Mordecki, 2014; Heston, 1993).

Step 2: Carr-Madan FFT setup and Greek integrands. Start from the damped call transform $\hat{c}_\alpha(u)$ in Carr-Madan (1999). Form *Greek-specific* integrands by replacing ϕ with the derivatives above (differentiation under the integral sign), e.g. insert $\frac{i u}{S_0} \phi$ for Δ , $\frac{i u(i u - 1)}{S_0^2} \phi$ for Γ , and $D(u, T) \phi$ for Vega_{v_0} . Invert on an equispaced frequency grid using FFT to recover Greeks on a strike grid. Choose damping α , grid size N , spacing $\Delta\eta$ per Carr-Madan (1999) with error-control guidance from transform literature (e.g., Lee, 2004).

Step 3: Implementation details. Implement in Python: (i) stable CF module; (ii) price FFT; (iii) Greek FFT (Delta, Gamma, Vega). Where helpful, include a COS-method cross-check for accuracy (Fang & Oosterlee, 2009).

Step 4: Numerical assessment and benchmarks. *Accuracy*: compare FFT-Greeks to (a) central finite-difference Greeks from a high-precision pricer and (b) available analytic references when applicable. *Efficiency*: record wall-clock time vs. $N, \Delta\eta, \alpha$. *Robustness*: stress regimes over Heston parameters $(\kappa, \theta, \sigma, \rho, v_0)$, maturity T , and moneyness K/S_0 ; map regions where FFT-Greeks are stable/unstable. Follow Cao-Lin (2024) for experiment organization and visualization (surfaces, error heatmaps).

Step 5: Practical guidelines. Synthesize recommended FFT settings $(\alpha, N, \Delta\eta)$, truncation windows, and CF forms for reliable Greek computation; document failure modes (e.g., long maturities, high σ , strong negative ρ) and remedies (grid refinement, damping adjustments).

2. Key outcomes.

(1) Closed-form *integrands* for $\Delta, \Gamma, \text{Vega}_{v_0}$ under Heston suitable for FFT; (2) accuracy within target tolerances vs. finite differences across (K, T) ; (3) measurable speedups for surfaces of Greeks; (4) a reproducible code package.

Primary references. Heston (1993); Carr & Madan (1999); de Oliveira & Mordecki (2014); Lee (2004); Fang & Oosterlee (2009); Cao & Lin (2024).

FIGURE 4. The research structure represented in form of a tree can be read as follows: first we develop based on literature review the theoretical part (derivation of FFT based Greeks). That is Layer 1. Layer 2 consists in coding and visualizing the convergence and showing that errors are small. Here is especially important that we check against well-established benchmarks, so we take Greeks that are reliable based on other methods that have previously been studied. We show that the absolute errors are small. Finally, we gather the real-time data and check the methodology on it, as the final step of the verification.

3. Contributions and novelties of this work

- We present, to our knowledge, the first *unified single-FFT formulation* of price, Delta, Gamma, and initial-variance sensitivity ($\partial C/\partial v_0$) for the Heston model. Previous studies derived Fourier formulas for individual Greeks or relied on multiple FFT evaluations; here all quantities are obtained simultaneously in one FFT computation.
- We extend Carr-Madan’s $O(N \log N)$ efficiency result from pricing to hedging: the FFT yields not only prices but also Greeks with no additional asymptotic cost, unlike standard quadrature ($O(N^2)$) or finite-difference approaches.
- We rigorously establish internal consistency (Black–Scholes limit, static arbitrage bounds) and validate the method on both synthetic data and live market quotes (Deribit BTC options), showing stable and accurate performance across maturities and parameter regimes.

FFT based pricing

1. FFT-Based Valuation and Greeks in the Heston Model

1.1. Carr-Madan Framework for Option Pricing. Let $k = \ln K$, $\alpha > 0$ a damping parameter, and define the damped call $c_\alpha(k) := e^{\alpha k} C(e^k)$. Its Fourier transform is

$$(12) \quad \widehat{c}_\alpha(u) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{iuk} c_\alpha(k) dk = e^{-rT} \frac{\phi(\xi)}{\alpha^2 + \alpha - u^2 + i(2\alpha + 1)u}, \quad \xi := u - i(\alpha + 1),$$

where $\phi(\cdot)$ is the characteristic function of $\ln S_T$ under \mathbb{Q} (Carr-Madan [9]). The price is recovered by

$$(13) \quad C(K) = \frac{e^{-\alpha k}}{\pi} \int_0^{\infty} \Re[e^{-iuk} \widehat{c}_\alpha(u)] du.$$

1.2. Fast Fourier Transform: Framework and Relevance. The Fourier transform provides a natural connection between option prices and the characteristic function of the log-asset price. Since European option prices can be represented as Fourier integrals (Carr and Madan, 1999), their numerical evaluation requires repeated computation of oscillatory integrals across a grid of strikes.

The Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) is a numerical algorithm for evaluating discrete Fourier transforms with computational complexity $\mathcal{O}(N \log N)$ instead of $\mathcal{O}(N^2)$ for naive summation (Brigham, 1988; Press et al., 2007). Originally developed in signal processing, FFT has become a standard tool in computational finance, where it enables the simultaneous recovery of option prices for a grid of strikes from a single frequency-domain calculation.

Within the Heston model, the FFT framework is particularly attractive because the model admits a closed-form characteristic function. This allows the Carr-Madan formulation to be combined with FFT to efficiently compute entire option price surfaces, and, as we shall show, to extend the framework further to the computation of Greeks.

1.3. Heston characteristic function and its derivatives. Under Heston [20] with dividends q , the log-price CF admits the affine form

$$(14) \quad \phi(z) = \exp\left(C(z, T) + D(z, T) v_0 + i z \ln S_0\right),$$

with C, D given in closed form (use a numerically stable branch; see Albrecher et al. “Little Heston Trap” [1] and Cui et al. [13]). The derivatives needed for Greeks follow immediately:

$$(15) \quad \frac{\partial \phi(z)}{\partial S_0} = \frac{iz}{S_0} \phi(z), \quad \frac{\partial^2 \phi(z)}{\partial S_0^2} = \frac{iz(iz - 1)}{S_0^2} \phi(z), \quad \frac{\partial \phi(z)}{\partial v_0} = D(z, T) \phi(z).$$

1.4. Differentiating under the Carr-Madan integral. Following the Fourier-Greeks paradigm of de Oliveira and Mordecki [27], we differentiate (13) with respect to the parameter of interest and interchange derivative and integral. Writing

$$\Psi(u; \alpha) := \frac{e^{-rT}}{\alpha^2 + \alpha - u^2 + i(2\alpha + 1)u}, \quad \xi := u - i(\alpha + 1),$$

we obtain the *Greek-specific* transforms by replacing $\phi(\xi)$ with the appropriate derivative from (15):

Delta ($\Delta = \partial C / \partial S_0$).

$$(16) \quad \Delta(K) = \frac{e^{-\alpha k}}{\pi} \int_0^\infty \Re \left[e^{-iuk} \Psi(u; \alpha) \frac{i\xi}{S_0} \phi(\xi) \right] du.$$

Gamma ($\Gamma = \partial^2 C / \partial S_0^2$).

$$(17) \quad \Gamma(K) = \frac{e^{-\alpha k}}{\pi} \int_0^\infty \Re \left[e^{-iuk} \Psi(u; \alpha) \frac{i\xi(i\xi - 1)}{S_0^2} \phi(\xi) \right] du.$$

Vega w.r.t. initial variance ($\text{Vega}_{v_0} = \partial C / \partial v_0$).

$$(18) \quad \text{Vega}_{v_0}(K) = \frac{e^{-\alpha k}}{\pi} \int_0^\infty \Re \left[e^{-iuk} \Psi(u; \alpha) D(\xi, T) \phi(\xi) \right] du.$$

Remarks (sanity checks). (i) For Δ , the integrand factor $\frac{i\xi}{S_0}$ is consistent with the affine form $\phi(z) = e^{iz \ln S_0} \dots$. (ii) For Γ , note the high-frequency multiplier $i\xi(i\xi - 1)$ can amplify tail noise; choose grids carefully. (iii) Vega_{v_0} uses the Riccati solution D , avoiding finite differences in v_0 .

1.5. Justification of the interchange (critical points). To pass derivatives under the integral in (13), we require a dominated convergence argument as in [27]: pick $\alpha > 0$ such that the *damped* payoff has a finite $(\alpha + 1)$ -moment; equivalently, ensure $\mathbb{E}[S_T^{\alpha+1}] < \infty$ so that $|\hat{c}_\alpha(u)| \lesssim |u|^{-2}$ for large $|u|$ (Carr-Madan [9], Lee's error analysis [23]). Multiplying by at most polynomial factors $|\xi|$ or $|\xi|^2$ (from Δ, Γ) preserves integrability. In Heston, exponential moments exist up to a parameter-dependent boundary; choose α below the moment explosion threshold and use a stable CF branch (Albrecher et al. [1]; see also the stable evaluation in [13]). This guarantees the integrands in (16)-(18) are absolutely integrable on $[0, \infty)$, validating the interchange.

1.6. Discrete FFT formulas. Choose N (power of two), frequency spacing $\Delta\eta$, truncation $B = N\Delta\eta$, and implied log-strike spacing $\Delta k = 2\pi/B$. Let $u_j = j\Delta\eta$ for $j = 0, \dots, N - 1$ and $k_m = -b + m\Delta k$ with $b = \frac{N}{2}\Delta k$. Define the (vectorizable) integrand kernels

$$\Psi_j := \Psi(u_j; \alpha), \quad \xi_j := u_j - i(\alpha + 1), \quad \phi_j := \phi(\xi_j), \quad w_j := (\text{quadrature weights, e.g. Simpson}).$$

Then

$$(19) \quad C_m \approx \frac{e^{-\alpha k_m}}{\pi} \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} \Re[e^{-iu_j k_m} \Psi_j \phi_j] \Delta \eta w_j,$$

$$(20) \quad \Delta_m \approx \frac{e^{-\alpha k_m}}{\pi} \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} \Re\left[e^{-iu_j k_m} \Psi_j \frac{i \xi_j}{S_0} \phi_j\right] \Delta \eta w_j,$$

$$(21) \quad \Gamma_m \approx \frac{e^{-\alpha k_m}}{\pi} \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} \Re\left[e^{-iu_j k_m} \Psi_j \frac{i \xi_j (i \xi_j - 1)}{S_0^2} \phi_j\right] \Delta \eta w_j,$$

$$(22) \quad \text{Vega}_{v_0, m} \approx \frac{e^{-\alpha k_m}}{\pi} \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} \Re[e^{-iu_j k_m} \Psi_j D(\xi_j, T) \phi_j] \Delta \eta w_j.$$

Using the FFT, the vectors $\{C_m\}$, $\{\Delta_m\}$, $\{\Gamma_m\}$, $\{\text{Vega}_{v_0, m}\}$ are obtained in $\mathcal{O}(N \log N)$ for the whole strike lattice.

1.7. Numerical Cautions and Best Practices. Although the Heston characteristic function admits a semi-closed form, its use in FFT pricing requires careful numerical handling. Several subtle points can strongly affect stability and accuracy:

- **Choice of damping α .** The Carr-Madan FFT method introduces a damping factor $e^{\alpha k}$ to ensure integrability of the payoff transform. If α is too small, the Fourier integrand decays slowly at the tails, leading to aliasing and oscillations in the recovered option price. If α is too large, the integrand decays faster but round-off errors (from subtracting nearly equal large numbers) dominate. Empirically, values $\alpha \in [1, 2]$ for calls balance these effects [9, 23]. This reflects the trade-off between convergence speed and numerical stability.
- **Branch stability in C, D .** The functions $C(u, \tau)$ and $D(u, \tau)$ involve complex logarithms. Because the logarithm is multi-valued, one must choose a consistent branch cut; otherwise, numerical evaluation will jump discontinuously, producing wildly incorrect option prices. The “Little Heston Trap” prescription of [1] specifies a stable branch choice for $d(u)$ and $g(u)$ in the Riccati solution, while later refinements (e.g. [13]) propose stabilized algebraic forms. Without this fix, FFT prices can oscillate or diverge unpredictably.
- **Gamma sensitivity and high-frequency amplification.** When computing second derivatives (Gamma), the Fourier kernel contains the factor $i\xi(i\xi - 1)$, which grows quadratically with frequency. This amplifies numerical noise at high u . To control this, one should increase the FFT grid size N , use a finer frequency step $\Delta\eta$, and apply smoothing weights such as Simpson’s rule. Intuitively, Greeks require more information from the tails of the distribution than prices do, so higher resolution and smoothing are essential.
- **Dividends and internal consistency checks.** With a continuous dividend yield q , the Heston semi-closed form implies the exact identity

$$\Delta = e^{-qT} P_1,$$

where P_1 is one of the Fourier-integral probabilities in Heston’s formula. This relation provides a convenient benchmark: if the FFT-computed Δ deviates significantly, the implementation likely suffers from truncation or discretization error. Such “sanity checks” are important for validating FFT-based Greeks.

- **Cross-method validation.** FFT results should be benchmarked against alternative methods: (i) high-precision finite-difference approximations of prices/Greeks,

(ii) COS-expansion Greeks [16], which converge exponentially in the number of terms, and (iii) adjoint-differentiated Monte Carlo methods [10, 7], which scale well in high dimensions. Comparing across methods reveals systematic biases (e.g. truncation vs. discretization) and gives confidence that observed differences are due to model dynamics rather than numerical artefacts.

2. FFT-Based Greeks under Heston: Detailed Derivations

2.1. Preliminaries and notation. Let $k = \ln K$, fix a damping parameter $\alpha > 0$, and define the damped call $c_\alpha(k) := e^{\alpha k} C(e^k)$. Carr and Madan [9] show that its Fourier transform

$$\widehat{c}_\alpha(u) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{iuk} c_\alpha(k) dk = e^{-rT} \frac{\phi(\xi)}{\alpha^2 + \alpha - u^2 + i(2\alpha + 1)u}, \quad \xi := u - i(\alpha + 1).$$

The inversion reads

$$(23) \quad C(K) = \frac{e^{-\alpha k}}{\pi} \int_0^\infty \Re[e^{-iuk} \Psi(u; \alpha) \phi(\xi)] du, \quad \Psi(u; \alpha) := \frac{e^{-rT}}{\alpha^2 + \alpha - u^2 + i(2\alpha + 1)u}.$$

Under Heston [20], the characteristic function of $X_T := \ln S_T$ has affine form

$$(24) \quad \phi(z) = \exp(C(z, T) + D(z, T) v_0 + iz \ln S_0),$$

with (using a numerically stable branch; see [1, 13])

$$\begin{aligned} d(z) &= \sqrt{(\rho\sigma iz - \kappa)^2 + \sigma^2(iz + z^2)}, \\ g(z) &= \frac{\kappa - \rho\sigma iz - d(z)}{\kappa - \rho\sigma iz + d(z)}, \\ C(z, T) &= (r - q) izT + \frac{\kappa\theta}{\sigma^2} \left[(\kappa - \rho\sigma iz - d)T - 2 \ln \frac{1 - ge^{-dT}}{1 - g} \right], \\ D(z, T) &= \frac{\kappa - \rho\sigma iz - d}{\sigma^2} \frac{1 - e^{-dT}}{1 - ge^{-dT}}. \end{aligned}$$

Basic CF derivatives (used repeatedly). From (24):

$$(25) \quad \frac{\partial \phi(z)}{\partial S_0} = \frac{iz}{S_0} \phi(z), \quad \frac{\partial^2 \phi(z)}{\partial S_0^2} = \frac{iz(iz - 1)}{S_0^2} \phi(z), \quad \frac{\partial \phi(z)}{\partial v_0} = D(z, T) \phi(z).$$

These identities are immediate because S_0 and v_0 enter only through the affine exponent.

We now differentiate (23) under the integral sign. The interchange is justified under the moment/damping assumptions discussed in Subsection 2.7 below, following [9, 23, 27].

2.2. Delta: $\Delta = \frac{\partial C}{\partial S_0}$. Start from (23), differentiate w.r.t. S_0 and bring the derivative inside the integral:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta(K) &= \frac{\partial}{\partial S_0} \left\{ \frac{e^{-\alpha k}}{\pi} \int_0^\infty \Re[e^{-iuk} \Psi(u; \alpha) \phi(\xi)] du \right\} \\ &= \frac{e^{-\alpha k}}{\pi} \int_0^\infty \Re \left[e^{-iuk} \Psi(u; \alpha) \frac{\partial \phi(\xi)}{\partial S_0} \right] du \quad (k \text{ and } \Psi \text{ do not depend on } S_0). \end{aligned}$$

Insert the CF derivative from (25) with $z = \xi$:

$$\frac{\partial \phi(\xi)}{\partial S_0} = \frac{i\xi}{S_0} \phi(\xi).$$

Hence the FFT-ready integral for Delta is

$$(26) \quad \Delta(K) = \frac{e^{-\alpha k}}{\pi} \int_0^\infty \Re \left[e^{-iuk} \Psi(u; \alpha) \frac{i\xi}{S_0} \phi(\xi) \right] du.$$

Comment. The factor $\frac{i\xi}{S_0}$ originates from the $iz \ln S_0$ term in the exponent of (24). For consistency checks, recall that in Heston the analytic formula yields $\Delta = e^{-qT} P_1$; numerically, (26) should match that benchmark to high precision.

2.3. Gamma: $\Gamma = \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial S_0^2}$. Differentiate Δ once more in S_0 :

$$\Gamma(K) = \frac{e^{-\alpha k}}{\pi} \int_0^\infty \Re \left[e^{-iuk} \Psi(u; \alpha) \frac{\partial^2 \phi(\xi)}{\partial S_0^2} \right] du,$$

where

$$\frac{\partial^2 \phi(\xi)}{\partial S_0^2} = \frac{i\xi(i\xi - 1)}{S_0^2} \phi(\xi) \quad \text{by (25)}.$$

Therefore

$$(27) \quad \Gamma(K) = \frac{e^{-\alpha k}}{\pi} \int_0^\infty \Re \left[e^{-iuk} \Psi(u; \alpha) \frac{i\xi(i\xi - 1)}{S_0^2} \phi(\xi) \right] du.$$

Comment (stability). The polynomial multiplier $i\xi(i\xi - 1)$ grows like $|u|^2$ along the real axis, hence (27) is more sensitive to high-frequency noise than (26). In practice, increase N , use smaller frequency step $\Delta\eta$, and employ smoothing weights (e.g. Simpson) in the Riemann sum. This mirrors guidance in [23] for transform error control.

2.4. Vega (w.r.t. initial variance v_0): $\text{Vega}_{v_0} = \frac{\partial C}{\partial v_0}$. Again from (23),

$$\text{Vega}_{v_0}(K) = \frac{e^{-\alpha k}}{\pi} \int_0^\infty \Re \left[e^{-iuk} \Psi(u; \alpha) \frac{\partial \phi(\xi)}{\partial v_0} \right] du.$$

Using (25) with $z = \xi$,

$$\frac{\partial \phi(\xi)}{\partial v_0} = D(\xi, T) \phi(\xi),$$

we obtain

$$(28) \quad \text{Vega}_{v_0}(K) = \frac{e^{-\alpha k}}{\pi} \int_0^\infty \Re \left[e^{-iuk} \Psi(u; \alpha) D(\xi, T) \phi(\xi) \right] du.$$

Comment. This quantity is the sensitivity to the *initial variance* v_0 . If desired, the same logic yields sensitivities to model parameters $(\kappa, \theta, \sigma, \rho)$ by differentiating $C(\cdot), D(\cdot)$ w.r.t. those parameters (parameter Greeks), but our focus is on the Greeks most used in hedging.

2.5. Single-FFT, multi-Greek formulation. Let $k = \log K$, damping $\alpha > 0$, and frequencies $u_j = j\eta$ for $j = 0, \dots, N - 1$ with $\Delta k \eta = 2\pi/N$ and $k_m = k_0 + m\Delta k$. Define $\xi_j := u_j - i(\alpha + 1)$, the Carr-Madan kernel

$$\Psi_j := \frac{e^{-rT}}{\alpha^2 + \alpha - u_j^2 + i(2\alpha + 1)u_j},$$

and the (stable) Heston characteristic function values $\phi_j := \phi(\xi_j; T)$ computed on the Lord-Kahl branch [24, 20]. Let w_j be Simpson weights.

Common factor and Greek-specific multipliers. Set

$$B_j := \Psi_j \phi_j w_j \eta \cdot e^{-iu_j k_0}, \quad M_j^{(\text{P})} := 1, \quad M_j^{(\Delta)} := \frac{i \xi_j}{S_0}, \quad M_j^{(\Gamma)} := \frac{i \xi_j (i \xi_j - 1)}{S_0^2}, \quad M_j^{(\text{V})} := D(\xi_j, T).$$

The four damped inversion sums (price, Δ , Γ , Vega $_{v_0}$) share the factor B_j and differ only by the multiplier $M_j^{(\ell)}$.

Discrete inversion as a single FFT.. Define the $N \times 4$ stacked integrand matrix

$$H_{j,\ell} := B_j M_j^{(\ell)}, \quad \ell \in \{\text{P}, \Delta, \Gamma, \text{V}\}.$$

Let \mathcal{F}_N denote the discrete Fourier transform acting along the frequency index j (the standard FFT operator). Then the four outputs on the log-strike grid are obtained *simultaneously* by one transform:

$$(29) \quad \widehat{H}_{m,\ell} := (\mathcal{F}_N H)_{m,\ell}, \quad \begin{aligned} C_m &= \frac{e^{-\alpha k_m}}{\pi} \Re(\widehat{H}_{m,\text{P}}), \\ \Delta_m &= \frac{e^{-\alpha k_m}}{\pi} \Re(\widehat{H}_{m,\Delta}), \\ \Gamma_m &= \frac{e^{-\alpha k_m}}{\pi} \Re(\widehat{H}_{m,\Gamma}), \\ \text{Vega}_{v_0,m} &= \frac{e^{-\alpha k_m}}{\pi} \Re(\widehat{H}_{m,\text{V}}). \end{aligned}$$

[Single-FFT unification] Under the damping/moment and dominated-convergence conditions used for (23), the discrete Carr-Madan inversions for $C, \Delta, \Gamma, \partial C / \partial v_0$ on an equispaced log-strike grid can be written in the form (29). Consequently, evaluating the stacked matrix $H \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times 4}$ with one batched FFT produces the four quantities on the entire strike grid without additional transforms.

SKETCH. Linearity of the Fourier inversion and the identities $\partial_{S_0} \phi(\xi) = \frac{i\xi}{S_0} \phi(\xi)$, $\partial_{S_0}^2 \phi(\xi) = \frac{i\xi(i\xi-1)}{S_0^2} \phi(\xi)$, $\partial_{v_0} \phi(\xi) = D(\xi, T) \phi(\xi)$ imply that each Greek equals the price integrand multiplied by a polynomial (or affine) factor in ξ . After Riemann-sum discretisation with common weights w_j and phase $e^{-iu_j k_0}$, all four sums share B_j and differ only by $M_j^{(\ell)}$. Stacking the four columns and applying the DFT along j yields (29). \square

Complexity. For fixed (N, η) the single evaluation (29) costs $O(N \log N)$ (one FFT) instead of four separate FFTs; constants drop further via plan/cache reuse in batched evaluation [17]. This preserves Carr-Madan efficiency for pricing [9] while extending it to hedging Greeks.

Remark (notation to implementation). In code, (29) corresponds to forming an $N \times 4$ array H and calling a *single* FFT over the frequency axis (e.g. one NumPy/FFTW/MKL batched transform). The de-damping factor $e^{-\alpha k_m} / \pi$ and the real part are then applied elementwise to the resulting four columns.

2.6. From integrals to FFT sums (implementation sketch). Let $u_j = j \Delta \eta$, $j = 0, \dots, N - 1$, with $\Delta \eta > 0$ and truncation $B = N \Delta \eta$, and let $k_m = -b + m \Delta k$, $m = 0, \dots, N - 1$, with $\Delta k = 2\pi / B$ and $b = \frac{N}{2} \Delta k$. Define vectorized kernels

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi_j &:= \Psi(u_j; \alpha), \quad \xi_j := u_j - i(\alpha + 1), \quad \phi_j := \phi(\xi_j) \\ \chi_j^{(\Delta)} &:= \frac{i \xi_j}{S_0}, \quad \chi_j^{(\Gamma)} := \frac{i \xi_j (i \xi_j - 1)}{S_0^2}, \quad \chi_j^{(\text{V})} := D(\xi_j, T) \end{aligned}$$

and quadrature weights w_j (e.g. $w_0 = w_{N-1} = \frac{1}{3}$, odd j : $\frac{4}{3}$, even j : $\frac{2}{3}$ for Simpson). Then

$$\begin{aligned} C_m &\approx \frac{e^{-\alpha k_m}}{\pi} \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} \Re[e^{-iu_j k_m} \Psi_j \phi_j] \Delta\eta w_j, \\ \Delta_m &\approx \frac{e^{-\alpha k_m}}{\pi} \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} \Re[e^{-iu_j k_m} \Psi_j \chi_j^{(\Delta)} \phi_j] \Delta\eta w_j, \\ \Gamma_m &\approx \frac{e^{-\alpha k_m}}{\pi} \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} \Re[e^{-iu_j k_m} \Psi_j \chi_j^{(\Gamma)} \phi_j] \Delta\eta w_j, \\ \text{Vega}_{v_0, m} &\approx \frac{e^{-\alpha k_m}}{\pi} \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} \Re[e^{-iu_j k_m} \Psi_j \chi_j^{(V)} \phi_j] \Delta\eta w_j. \end{aligned}$$

These sums are *convolutions on equispaced grids* and can be computed for all m in $\mathcal{O}(N \log N)$ via FFT (see [9]; error control as in [23]).

2.7. Why the differentiation is legitimate. To pass derivatives through the integral in (23), we require:

- (i) **Moment/damping:** choose α in the *moment strip* so that $\mathbb{E}[S_T^{\alpha+1}] < \infty$ (Carr-Madan [9]). In Heston, exponential moments exist up to a parameter-dependent boundary; pick α below the moment explosion time.
- (ii) **Tail decay and dominated convergence:** with such α , the damped transform satisfies $|\widehat{c}_\alpha(u)| \lesssim |u|^{-2}$ as $|u| \rightarrow \infty$ (see [9, 23]). Multipliers arising from Δ and Γ are polynomial in u (at most quadratic), so integrability is preserved; dominated convergence applies.
- (iii) **Stable CF evaluation:** evaluate $\phi(\xi)$ using the ‘‘Little Heston Trap’’ branch to avoid spurious oscillations [1]; for extreme parameters use the stabilized routines of [13]. This is a numerical, not analytic, requirement to make the integrand well behaved.

These are exactly the hypotheses used for Fourier-Greeks in exponential Lévy models [27], adapted here to the Heston setting.

2.8. Sanity checks and cross-validation.

- For calls with dividend yield q , analytic Heston yields $\Delta = e^{-qT} P_1$; check (26) numerically against that closed form across (K, T) .
- Compare FFT-Greeks to: (a) high-accuracy finite-difference Greeks (tight steps, Richardson extrapolation), (b) COS-Greeks as a spectral benchmark [16], (c) AD-based Monte Carlo Greeks [10, 7].
- Map stability vs. $(\kappa, \theta, \sigma, \rho, v_0)$ and T ; Γ typically requires finer frequency grids.

2.9. Essential identities: derivatives of the Heston characteristic function.

Under the risk-neutral Heston dynamics, the log-price characteristic function is affine

$$(30) \quad \phi(z; T) = \mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}}[e^{iz \ln S_T} \mid S_0, v_0] = \exp(C(z, T) + D(z, T) v_0 + iz \ln S_0),$$

with C, D given in closed form (Heston [20]) and evaluated on a numerically stable branch (Albrecher et al. [1]; Cui et al. [13]). Crucially, $C(z, T), D(z, T)$ depend on model parameters $(\kappa, \theta, \sigma, \rho, r, q)$ and T , but *not* on S_0 or v_0 .

Derivatives with respect to S_0 and v_0 . Because S_0 and v_0 appear only in the affine exponent, we can differentiate explicitly:

$$(31) \quad \frac{\partial \phi(z; T)}{\partial S_0} = \exp(\dots) \frac{\partial}{\partial S_0} (iz \ln S_0) = \frac{iz}{S_0} \phi(z; T),$$

$$(32) \quad \frac{\partial^2 \phi(z; T)}{\partial S_0^2} = \frac{\partial}{\partial S_0} \left(\frac{iz}{S_0} \phi \right) = \left(\frac{iz(iz-1)}{S_0^2} \right) \phi(z; T),$$

$$(33) \quad \frac{\partial \phi(z; T)}{\partial v_0} = \exp(\dots) \frac{\partial}{\partial v_0} (D(z, T) v_0) = D(z, T) \phi(z; T).$$

These identities are exact and model the entire effect of S_0 and v_0 on ϕ via simple multiplicative factors.

Inserted into Carr-Madan's damped pricing transform (Carr & Madan [9]), they yield *Greek-specific* Fourier integrands by a trivial substitution $\phi(\xi) \mapsto \partial_{S_0} \phi(\xi)$, $\partial_{S_0}^2 \phi(\xi)$, or $\partial_{v_0} \phi(\xi)$ at $\xi = u - i(\alpha + 1)$ (with damping $\alpha > 0$). This turns the price integral into semi-analytic FFT formulas for Δ , Γ , and Vega_{v_0} .

Legitimacy of differentiating under the integral. Let $c_\alpha(k) = e^{\alpha k} C(e^k)$ be the damped call and $\widehat{c}_\alpha(u)$ its transform in the Carr-Madan formula. To bring derivatives inside the inversion integral we assume:

- *Moment/damping condition:* choose α in the moment strip so that $\mathbb{E}[S_T^{\alpha+1}] < \infty$. In Heston this holds for α below the moment explosion boundary (see Carr-Madan [9] and transform error control in Lee [23]).
- *Tail decay / dominated convergence:* with such α , $|\widehat{c}_\alpha(u)| \lesssim |u|^{-2}$ as $|u| \rightarrow \infty$ (Carr-Madan [9]; Lee [23]). Multiplicative factors from the derivative identities grow at most polynomially in u (linear for Δ , quadratic for Γ), preserving integrability; dominated convergence then justifies the interchange. This mirrors the rigorous Fourier-Greeks treatment in de Oliveira & Mordecki [27].
- *Stable CF evaluation:* evaluate C, D on the ‘‘Little Heston Trap’’ branch to avoid spurious blowups (Albrecher et al. [1]); use stabilized routines for extreme parameters (Cui et al. [13]).

Benchmarking and Stability Checks

1. Numerical robustness and correctness

Aim. We verify that the FFT-based Greeks derived in Chapter 4 match “ground-truth” Heston Greeks to tight numerical tolerances across OTM/ATM/ITM strikes and short/long maturities. Accuracy and stability are established by direct comparison against high-accuracy quadrature of the same integral representations under the Heston model.

1.1. Remarks on thresholds and fixing parameters. Unless otherwise stated, all numerical illustrations are based on the following standard configuration:

$$S_0 = 100.0, \quad r = 0.0, \quad q = 0.0, \quad \sigma_{\text{BS}} = 0.20,$$

with strikes $K \in \{90.0, 100.0, 110.0\}$, maturities $T \in \{0.25, 1.00\}$, and Carr-Madan FFT parameters $\alpha = 1.5$, $N = 2^{12}$, $\eta = 0.25$, and $k_0 = \log(100.0) - 3.0$. These parameter values follow standard benchmark conventions in the Fourier-pricing literature (e.g. Carr and Madan [9], Fang and Oosterlee [16]). The spot price $S_0 = 100$ serves as a natural normalization around the at-the-money (ATM) region, with strikes at 90, 100, and 110 capturing moderate in- and out-of-the-money behavior. Zero rates ($r = q = 0$) isolate model and numerical effects without the confounding influence of discounting or dividends. The volatility $\sigma_{\text{BS}} = 0.20$ corresponds to a typical annualized market level for equity indices, ensuring comparability with earlier FFT studies. The FFT grid parameters (α, N, η, k_0) are chosen to balance accuracy and runtime: the damping factor $\alpha = 1.5$ guarantees integrability and numerical stability of the Carr–Madan transform, while $N = 2^{12}$ and $\eta = 0.25$ provide sufficient frequency resolution to cover the relevant strike range without aliasing. The log-strike offset $k_0 = \log(100) - 3$ centers the numerical grid around the ATM region, reducing edge distortions in the recovered price and Greek surfaces.

Static-arbitrage and logical constraints. In order to validate numerical results for option prices and Greeks, we require that certain model-agnostic constraints are satisfied. These conditions are well known in the literature (see [26, 3, 9, 24]) and apply equally to Black-Scholes, Heston, or Fourier-based pricing schemes. We summarise them below, together with numerical acceptance rules that allow for small discretisation errors.

Bounds on price (rational bounds). For a European call,

$$\max\{S_0 e^{-qT} - K e^{-rT}, 0\} \leq C(K, T) \leq S_0 e^{-qT}.$$

We accept a result if any violation is smaller than a tolerance 10^{-4} . Larger deviations imply rejection.

Monotonicity in strike. The call price must be nonincreasing in the strike K . We therefore check that finite differences satisfy

$$C(K_{j+1}, T) - C(K_j, T) \leq 5 \times 10^{-4}.$$

Convexity in strike. Call prices are convex functions of K , equivalently

$$\frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial K^2} = e^{-rT} f_Q(K) \geq 0$$

(Breedon-Litzenberger). Numerically, the second difference

$$C(K_{j+1}) - 2C(K_j) + C(K_{j-1}) \geq -5 \times 10^{-4}$$

must hold.

Slope bounds in strike. The slope of the call with respect to strike is bounded:

$$0 \leq -\frac{\partial C}{\partial K} \leq e^{-rT}.$$

We enforce this with a tolerance 10^{-6} in finite differences.

Put-call parity. Put-call parity requires

$$C(K, T) - P(K, T) = S_0 e^{-qT} - K e^{-rT}.$$

Numerically we accept residuals up to $10^{-6}(1 + C + P)$.

Delta bounds. For calls,

$$0 \leq \Delta \leq e^{-qT}.$$

We check that Δ lies within this interval up to tolerance 10^{-6} .

Gamma nonnegativity. Convexity in the spot implies $\Gamma \geq 0$. Numerically we require $\Gamma \geq -5 \times 10^{-4}$ and that no spurious sign changes occur across adjacent nodes.

Vega sign. For $T > 0$, Vega is nonnegative:

$$\text{Vega} = \frac{\partial C}{\partial \sigma} \geq 0.$$

We accept $\text{Vega} \geq -10^{-6}$, allowing small noise near expiry.

Calendar monotonicity. With nonnegative carry ($r \geq q$), call prices are nondecreasing in maturity:

$$C(K, T_{m+1}) - C(K, T_m) \geq -10^{-4}.$$

This property may fail if $q > r$ is large, in which case deviations are expected.

FFT-specific consistency. When using Carr-Madan FFT, consistency requires damping removal and a stable Heston characteristic function (the ‘‘little trap’’ of [24]). Prices must satisfy all of the above checks, while Greeks are evaluated with looser tolerance 5×10^{-4} since Fourier differentiation is noisier. If failures cluster at grid edges, windowing and frequency steps must be adjusted.

1.2. Reference formulas and FFT mapping. Let $k = \log K$ and $\alpha > 0$ be the Carr-Madan damping parameter. For $z := u - i(\alpha + 1)$ and the (stable) Heston characteristic function $\phi(z; T) = \exp(C(z, T) + D(z, T)v_0)$ in the ‘‘little Heston trap’’ formulation, the damped call as a function of k is

$$(34) \quad C_\alpha(k) = \frac{e^{-\alpha k}}{\pi} \int_0^\infty \Re(e^{-iuk} \Psi(u)) du, \quad \Psi(u) := \frac{e^{-rT} \phi(z; T)}{\alpha^2 + \alpha - u^2 + i(2\alpha + 1)u}.$$

Differentiating under the integral yields the Greeks’ Fourier integrands:

$$(35) \quad \Delta : \quad \frac{\partial C_\alpha}{\partial S_0} = \frac{e^{-\alpha k}}{\pi} \int_0^\infty \Re\left(e^{-iuk} \Psi(u) \frac{iz}{S_0}\right) du,$$

$$(36) \quad \Gamma : \quad \frac{\partial^2 C_\alpha}{\partial S_0^2} = \frac{e^{-\alpha k}}{\pi} \int_0^\infty \Re\left(e^{-iuk} \Psi(u) \frac{-(iz + z^2)}{S_0^2}\right) du,$$

$$(37) \quad \text{Vega}_{v_0} : \quad \frac{\partial C_\alpha}{\partial v_0} = \frac{e^{-\alpha k}}{\pi} \int_0^\infty \Re\left(e^{-iuk} \Psi(u) D(z, T)\right) du,$$

where $D(\cdot, T)$ is the affine coefficient in $\phi = \exp(C + Dv_0)$, and Δ/Γ are w.r.t. S_0 while *Vega* here is w.r.t. the initial variance v_0 (we denote it Vega_{v_0} throughout).

Stability of the characteristic function. We evaluate ϕ using the numerically stable complex-logarithm formulation (“little Heston trap”) to avoid branch-cut discontinuities that corrupt Fourier inversion. This choice is standard and recommended in the Heston literature.¹

1.3. Experimental setup. Model parameters. Unless stated otherwise we use $S_0 = 100$, $r = 0$, $q = 0$, $\kappa = 2.0$, $\theta = 0.04$, $\sigma = 0.6$, $\rho = -0.7$, $v_0 = 0.05$. Strikes $K \in \{90, 100, 110\}$, maturities $T \in \{0.25, 1.00\}$.

Reference (ground-truth). We evaluate (34)–(37) by high-accuracy quadrature on $u \in [0, u_{\max}]$ with Simpson weights ($N = 2^{14}$ points, $u_{\max} = 200$, $\alpha = 1.5$). This provides *reference* Price/ $\Delta/\Gamma/\text{Vega}$ values.

FFT-based. For the FFT we compute the same integrands on a uniform frequency grid $u_m = m\eta$, apply Simpson weights, and map to a regular log-strike grid $k_j = k_0 + j\Delta k$ with $\Delta k\eta = 2\pi/N$. We use $N = 2^{12}$, $\eta = 0.25$, $k_0 = \log S_0 - 3$, $\alpha = 1.5$ and linearly interpolate to the desired K .

2. Analysis of Delta, Gamma and Vega

We will present tables showing that FFT-pricing and thereon based Greeks have desired properties. For all tables in this section, we fix the baseline parameters

$$S_0 = 100, r = 0, q = 0, \sigma_{\text{BS}} = 0.20, K \in \{90, 100, 110\}, T \in \{0.25, 1.00\},$$

together with Carr-Madan FFT inputs $\alpha = 1.5$, $N = 2^{12}$, $\eta = 0.25$, and $k_0 = \log(100) - 3$. All reported option prices and Greeks are obtained under this configuration, unless explicitly varied in the robustness analysis.

2.1. Delta comparison and verification. Remark on Table 1.1. Table 1.1 compares Delta values obtained via Carr-Madan FFT with those from reference quadrature integration. Errors are consistently in the order 10^{-5} - 10^{-4} , comfortably below acceptance thresholds discussed in [9, 24]. Theoretical sanity checks are also satisfied: Deltas lie within the expected interval $[0, 1]$, are decreasing in strike, and converge to 0 or 1 as options become deep out- or in-the-money. These observations confirm that the FFT implementation produces meaningful and reliable Delta values.

TABLE 1. Comparison of FFT-based and reference Delta values. Reference quadrature: $N = 2^{14}$, $u_{\max} = 200$, $\alpha = 1.5$. FFT: $N = 2^{12}$, $\eta = 0.25$, $k_0 = \log S_0 - 3$, $\alpha = 1.5$.

T	K	Price _{ref}	Price _{FFT}	$ e_P $	Δ_{ref}	Δ_{FFT}	$ e_\Delta $
0.25	90	11.281628	11.281855	2.27e−04	0.867935	0.867886	4.96e−05
0.25	100	4.074919	4.075344	4.25e−04	0.607988	0.607946	4.20e−05
0.25	110	0.559669	0.561398	1.73e−03	0.163908	0.164172	2.65e−04
1.00	90	13.993240	13.993403	1.63e−04	0.811730	0.811704	2.57e−05
1.00	100	7.361344	7.361557	2.12e−04	0.640322	0.640305	1.61e−05
1.00	110	2.897635	2.898908	1.27e−03	0.380732	0.380728	4.21e−06

¹See LordKahl2010 for a rigorous treatment of the principal branch and numerical stability. The original FFT pricing framework is due to CarrMadan1999; the Heston model is from Heston1993.

Black-Scholes Limit Verification. A key internal consistency check is to verify that the Heston-FFT method reduces to the Black-Scholes closed form when the variance process is deterministic. This occurs when

$$v_0 = \theta = \sigma_{\text{BS}}^2, \quad \rho = 0, \quad \kappa \rightarrow \infty, \quad \sigma \rightarrow 0,$$

so that the CIR variance process collapses to a constant. In this limit the Heston characteristic function coincides with the Gaussian characteristic function, and option prices and Greeks must agree exactly with the Black-Scholes formulas.

We implement this limit numerically by setting $v_0 = \theta = \sigma_{\text{BS}}^2$, choosing κ very large, σ very small, and $\rho = 0$. Under this parameterisation we compare FFT outputs against Black-Scholes closed-form values for strikes $K \in \{90, 100, 110\}$ and maturities $T \in \{0.25, 1.00\}$. Errors are found to be negligible (in the range 10^{-4} - 10^{-3}), which confirms both the logical and numerical consistency of the FFT implementation in the Black-Scholes limit [9, 24].

FIGURE 5. Delta error diagnostics. (a) heat map of absolute Delta error $e_{\Delta}(K, T)$ across the strike-maturity grid; (b) error versus grid size N at-the-money (ATM); (c) error versus frequency step η (ATM); (d) sensitivity to window centre k_0 (ATM); (e) sensitivity to damping α (ATM); (f) histogram of relative error $e_{\Delta}^{\text{rel}}(K, T)$ over all (K, T) points. Baseline parameters as in Section 1.1 this chapter.

2.2. Delta Analysis via Visualizations - Errors, Reliability and Convergence.

Panel (a): Delta absolute error over (K, T) . Color encodes $e_{\Delta}(K, T)$: darker \Rightarrow smaller error, lighter \Rightarrow larger error. Two expected patterns are visible: (i) errors are smallest near the centre of the strike window and grow as we approach the edges (aliasing/truncation); (ii) short maturities exhibit larger errors due to steeper payoff curvature and stronger sensitivity to de-damping.²

²This is consistent with FFT discretisation and windowing effects; see [9, 23].

Panel (b): Error vs. N (ATM).. Holding η fixed, increasing N reduces $\Delta k = 2\pi/(N\eta)$ and thus improves resolution. The curve decays monotonically, illustrating convergence with N until a noise floor is reached (dominated by de-damping and machine precision). This behaviour matches transform-method error analyses in [23].

Panel (c): Error vs. η (ATM).. For fixed N , changing η trades off frequency truncation against strike resolution because Δk scales like $1/\eta$. The U-shaped profile is typical: too small $\eta \Rightarrow$ narrow frequency window (truncation); too large $\eta \Rightarrow$ coarse Δk (interpolation error). The baseline choice (here $\eta \approx 0.25$) sits near the minimum, in line with practical guidance in [9].

Panel (d): Sensitivity to k_0 (ATM). Shifting k_0 recentres the phase factor e^{-iuk_0} used in the inversion. The mild oscillation reflects phase-alignment and window-edge effects; placing k_0 so that the *ATM* strike lies well inside the window minimises error. If oscillations grow or become irregular, enlarge the window (increase N or decrease η) [9].

Panel (e): Sensitivity to damping α (ATM).. Moderate increases in α reduce error by improving integrand decay; beyond a point, de-damping in strike space amplifies noise and the curve flattens. The observed decrease-then-plateau profile is the expected trade-off; values around $\alpha \in [1, 2]$ are commonly robust for European calls [9, 23].

Panel (f): Histogram of relative error over (K, T) . The distribution is highly concentrated near zero, with a short right tail. This indicates uniform accuracy across the grid rather than isolated outliers. Bins near the tail typically correspond to the window edges and shortest maturities; if heavy tails appear, refine N and re-tune η, α .

Overall, Figure 5 demonstrates that Delta errors are small, well-behaved under standard parameter variations, and decrease predictably with FFT grid refinement. This is consistent with the transform-method literature [9, 23, 24].

FIGURE 6. Delta profiles and absolute errors. Top left: Delta vs. strike at $T = 0.25$; FFT and reference overlap almost perfectly, decreasing monotonically from ≈ 1 (deep ITM) to 0 (deep OTM). Top right: absolute error vs. strike at $T = 0.25$; all below 10^{-4} with slightly larger values at window edges. Bottom left: Delta vs. maturity at $K = 100$; values rise from ≈ 0.52 at $T = 0.25$ to ≈ 0.64 at $T = 1.0$, consistent with increasing in-the-money probability. Bottom right: absolute error vs. maturity at $K = 100$; errors below 2×10^{-5} and decreasing with T , reflecting smoother distributions for longer maturities.

2.3. Gamma comparison. Remark on Table 1.2. Table 1.2 reports Gamma values obtained via Carr-Madan FFT and reference quadrature integration. Reported errors are in the order 10^{-5} - 10^{-4} , well below the acceptance thresholds suggested in [9, 24]. Furthermore, theoretical sanity checks (Gamma positivity, convexity in strike, and plausible magnitudes in the range of 10^{-2} to 10^{-3} for the given baseline parameters) are satisfied, confirming that the FFT implementation produces meaningful and reliable Greeks.

Black-Scholes Limit Verification. A fundamental internal consistency check is to verify that the Heston-FFT implementation reduces to the Black-Scholes model in the appropriate limit. Setting $v_0 = \theta = \sigma_{BS}^2$, $\rho = 0$, $\kappa \rightarrow \infty$, and $\sigma \rightarrow 0$, the variance process becomes deterministic and the Heston model collapses to Black-Scholes. In this regime, the FFT prices and Greeks must coincide with the Black-Scholes closed-form values.

Table 1.2 reports such a comparison for strikes $K \in \{90, 100, 110\}$ and maturities $T \in \{0.25, 1.00\}$. Errors are within 10^{-4} - 10^{-3} , consistent with numerical tolerances. This confirms that the FFT implementation is logically and numerically consistent in the Black-Scholes limit, in line with the recommendations of [9, 24].

TABLE 2. Comparison of FFT-based and reference Gamma values. Reference quadrature: $N = 2^{14}$, $u_{\max} = 200$, $\alpha = 1.5$. FFT: $N = 2^{12}$, $\eta = 0.25$, $k_0 = \log S_0 - 3$, $\alpha = 1.5$.

T	K	Price _{ref}	Price _{FFT}	$ e_P $	Γ_{ref}	Γ_{FFT}	$ e_\Gamma $
0.25	90	11.281628	11.281855	2.27e-04	1.420199e-02	1.420653e-02	4.54e-06
0.25	100	4.074919	4.075344	4.25e-04	3.843484e-02	3.843594e-02	1.10e-06
0.25	110	0.559669	0.561398	1.73e-03	3.869296e-02	3.866444e-02	2.85e-05
1.00	90	13.993240	13.993403	1.63e-04	1.145055e-02	1.145220e-02	1.65e-06
1.00	100	7.361344	7.361557	2.12e-04	2.198609e-02	2.198635e-02	2.62e-07
1.00	110	2.897635	2.898908	1.27e-03	3.077096e-02	3.075711e-02	1.38e-05

FIGURE 7. Gamma error diagnostics. Panel (a): Gamma absolute error across (K, T) ; errors are 10^{-3} - 10^{-4} with largest values at short maturities and window edges. Panel (b): error vs. N (ATM); decreasing monotonically, showing convergence. Panel (c): error vs. η (ATM); U-shaped profile from truncation vs. resolution trade-off. Panel (d): sensitivity to k_0 (ATM); mild oscillations due to phase alignment, with central placement minimising error. Panel (e): sensitivity to α (ATM); errors fall then plateau, robust for $\alpha \in [1, 2]$. Panel (f): histogram of relative error; distribution concentrated near zero with few outliers.

2.4. Gamma Analysis via Visualizations - Errors, Reliability and Convergence.

FIGURE 8. Gamma profiles and errors. Panel (a): Gamma vs. strike at $T = 0.25$; FFT and reference overlap, peaking near-the-money and declining symmetrically. Panel (b): absolute error vs. strike at $T = 0.25$; all errors below 3×10^{-5} with larger values at strike extremes. Panel (c): Gamma vs. maturity at $K = 100$; values decrease with T , consistent with lower curvature for longer horizons. Panel (d): absolute error vs. maturity at $K = 100$; errors below 10^{-5} and decreasing in T , reflecting smoother distributions.

2.5. Vega comparisson.

Black-Scholes limit verification. In the deterministic variance limit of the Heston model ($v_0 = \theta = \sigma_{BS}^2$, $\rho = 0$, $\kappa \rightarrow \infty$, $\sigma \rightarrow 0$), the Vega with respect to v_0 must coincide with the Black-Scholes expression $\partial C / \partial v_0 = (\partial C / \partial \sigma) / (2\sigma)$. Table 1.3 confirms this consistency: FFT-based values agree with the Black-Scholes closed form to within 10^{-3} across strikes and maturities. The slightly larger discrepancies compared to Delta and Gamma are expected, since Vega involves differentiation with respect to volatility and is thus more sensitive to numerical noise. Nevertheless, all results remain well within the acceptance thresholds, validating the correctness of the FFT implementation for Vega in the Black-Scholes limit [9, 24].

2.6. Vega Analysis via Visualizations - Errors, Reliability and Convergence.

We finally show how Vega behaves. We compare Vega absolute errors, and show that as N becomes larger i.e. as refinements and grid-size increases the errors for the at-the-money is smaller.

TABLE 3. Comparison of FFT-based and reference Vega values. Reference quadrature: $N = 2^{14}$, $u_{\max} = 200$, $\alpha = 1.5$. FFT: $N = 2^{12}$, $\eta = 0.25$, $k_0 = \log S_0 - 3$, $\alpha = 1.5$. Vega is w.r.t. v_0 .

T	K	Price _{ref}	Price _{FFT}	$ e_P $	Vega _{v_0,ref}	Vega _{v_0,FFT}	$ e_V $
0.25	90	11.281628	11.281855	2.27e-04	20.864669	20.866928	2.26e-03
0.25	100	4.074919	4.075344	4.25e-04	36.982640	36.978138	4.50e-03
0.25	110	0.559669	0.561398	1.73e-03	20.441050	20.446450	5.40e-03
1.00	90	13.993240	13.993403	1.63e-04	30.949678	30.949529	1.49e-04
1.00	100	7.361344	7.361557	2.12e-04	39.136585	39.135034	1.55e-03
1.00	110	2.897635	2.898908	1.27e-03	35.229232	35.219455	9.78e-03

FIGURE 9. Vega error diagnostics. Panel (a): Vega absolute error across (K, T) ; errors are larger near short maturities and OTM strikes, as expected from high sensitivity to volatility. Panel (b): error vs. N (ATM); monotone decrease confirms convergence with grid refinement. Panel (c): error vs. η (ATM); U-shaped curve reflects the usual truncation-resolution trade-off. Panel (d): sensitivity to k_0 (ATM); oscillations arise from window centring, but remain small. Panel (e): sensitivity to α (ATM); moderate damping reduces error, plateauing for $\alpha \in [1, 2]$, consistent with theory. Panel (f): histogram of relative error; most errors are close to zero with a few outliers at grid edges, consistent with expected FFT noise for Vega.

FIGURE 10. Vega profiles and errors. Panel (a): Vega vs. strike at $T = 0.25$; FFT matches the reference, peaking near-the-money and tapering toward deep ITM/OTM strikes, consistent with theory. Panel (b): absolute error vs. strike at $T = 0.25$; errors reach up to 0.015 at the edges, reflecting Vega’s high sensitivity to volatility changes and window effects. Panel (c): Vega vs. maturity at $K = 100$; values increase from ≈ 37 at $T = 0.25$ to ≈ 41 at $T = 0.5$, then slowly decline, showing the expected time profile. Panel (d): absolute error vs. maturity at $K = 100$; errors decrease steadily with T , as longer horizons smooth volatility sensitivity and reduce FFT noise.

3. Comments

Absolute errors are small across all strikes and maturities; the worst relative price error is $\approx 0.31\%$ (at $T = 0.25$, $K = 110$), while the largest relative Greek errors are $\lesssim 0.2\%$ for Δ , $\approx 0.07\%$ for Γ , and $\approx 0.03\%$ for Vega_{v_0} over this grid. Moreover, $\Delta \in [0, 1]$, $\Gamma \geq 0$, and $\text{Vega}_{v_0} \geq 0$ throughout, and monotonicity/convexity in K hold.

4. Numerical gates and pass/fail

We adopt the following acceptance gates for this chapter:

- Price: $\max |e_P| < 5 \times 10^{-3}$,
- Delta: $\max |e_\Delta| < 3 \times 10^{-4}$,
- Gamma: $\max |e_\Gamma| < 5 \times 10^{-5}$,
- Vega_{v_0} : $\max |e_V| < 1 \times 10^{-2}$.

All entries in Tables in the above sections *pass* these gates.

4.1. Reproducibility and implementation notes.

- (1) *Characteristic function.* We use the stable principal-branch form of the Heston characteristic function to avoid discontinuities in Fourier inversion.³
- (2) *Integral evaluation.* Reference values use Simpson quadrature on $[0, u_{\max}]$ with $N = 2^{14}$; FFT values use a uniform frequency grid $u_m = m \eta$ with Simpson weights, the standard FFT strike mapping $\Delta k \eta = 2\pi/N$, and damping $\alpha = 1.5$, following [9].
- (3) *Greek definitions.* Vega_{v_0} means partial derivative w.r.t. initial variance v_0 (not w.r.t. volatility σ); we keep this convention throughout.
- (4) *Cross-checks.* We also verified the Black-Scholes limit ($\kappa \rightarrow \infty$, $\sigma \rightarrow 0$, $\rho = 0$, $\theta = v_0 = \sigma_{\text{BS}}^2$) and finite-difference Greeks against the reference price; discrepancies were negligible at the settings above.

4.2. Logical and Numerical Consistency. In addition to comparing FFT-based Greeks with the semi-analytical Heston reference values, we also carried out a secondary validation step using the Black-Scholes model as a benchmark. The motivation for this auxiliary test is twofold: logical consistency and numerical consistency.

Logical consistency. The Carr-Madan FFT framework is a general Fourier inversion algorithm. If the method is correctly implemented, then inserting the Black-Scholes characteristic function must reproduce the well-known closed-form Black-Scholes prices and Greeks with high precision. This test is not intended to produce new financial results, but rather to confirm that the implementation is internally consistent and that the inversion machinery behaves as expected in a model where exact closed forms are available.

Numerical consistency. The Heston model introduces additional numerical challenges: affine terms in the characteristic function can become stiff, cancellation may occur in logarithmic expressions, and sensitivity to grid parameters is more pronounced. By testing the FFT inversion on the Black-Scholes characteristic function, we isolate the performance of the numerical method itself from these model-specific issues. In other words, if the FFT reproduces Black-Scholes closed-form results to machine accuracy, then any residual discrepancies in the Heston setting can be attributed to the model complexity rather than to flaws in the FFT algorithm.

4.3. Summary and Conclusion of Error Analysis. The FFT-based Greeks computed from the analytically differentiated Fourier integrands match the reference Heston Greeks to high precision at modest grid sizes. This supports the use of the FFT method for fast, accurate Greeks on strike grids, provided standard damping and windowing guidelines are observed.

4.4. Runtime and ablation: single FFT vs multiple FFTs. We benchmark the proposed *single-FFT*, *multi-Greek* implementation against two alternatives: (i) high-accuracy Simpson quadrature for one at-the-money strike, and (ii) four separate FFT evaluations (price, Δ , Γ , $\partial C / \partial v_0$) on the same grid. All experiments were run in Python (NumPy 1.26, FFTW backend) on a local machine (Intel i7-1185G7 CPU, Windows 11, single thread). Timings are medians over 10 repetitions after warm-up.

³See LordKahl2010.

TABLE 4. Runtime comparison for computing $(C, \Delta, \Gamma, \partial C/\partial v_0)$ on one strike grid ($N = 2^{12}$, $\eta = 0.25$, $\alpha = 1.5$, $k_0 = \log S_0 - 3$, $T = 0.25$).

Method	Calls	Time (ms)	Relative (vs quad)
Quadrature (ATM, Simpson)	–	52.17	1.0000×
Separate FFTs (4 calls/grid)	4	16.77	0.3215×
Single batched FFT (grid)	1	6.18	0.1185×

The single batched FFT achieves the same $O(N \log N)$ complexity but reduces constant factors by avoiding repeated plan setup and cache passes. Accuracy is preserved: for all strikes and maturities tested, the outputs from single vs. separate FFTs match to machine precision, and ATM values agree with quadrature within tight tolerances ($|e_\Delta| < 1.4 \times 10^{-3}$, $|e_\Gamma| < 1.1 \times 10^{-4}$, $|e_{\text{Vega}_{v_0}}| < 2.8 \times 10^{-2}$).

Benchmark protocol. We benchmark two implementations on identical grids (N, η, α, k_0) and maturity T : (i) a *single batched FFT* that transforms the stacked integrand matrix (Fortran order so the FFT axis is contiguous), and (ii) *four separate FFTs* applied to each column. We time only the FFT call (integrand construction excluded) after one warm-up, and report the *median* runtime over R repeats together with the *interquartile range* (IQR). Threads are pinned to 1 and the same NumPy backend is used for all runs. Across all grid sizes N , the single batched FFT is consistently faster than running four separate FFTs, roughly halving the median runtime (e.g. 0.127 ms vs. 0.280 ms at $N = 2048$, and 1.660 ms vs. 2.274 ms at $N = 8192$). The advantage grows with larger grids, confirming that the batching strategy reduces constant factors while preserving the $O(N \log N)$ complexity. Variability (IQR) is larger at $N = 8192$, reflecting cache and memory effects, but the median advantage of the batched approach is robust.

TABLE 5. Runtime comparison of single batched FFT vs. four separate FFTs. Reported are medians over 10 runs, with interquartile ranges (IQR), minima, and maxima (all in ms).

N	Method	Median (ms)	IQR (ms)	Min (ms)	Max (ms)	Repeats
2048	Single batched FFT	0.127	0.020	0.122	2.187	10
2048	Separate (4 FFTs)	0.280	0.106	0.257	2.347	10
4096	Single batched FFT	0.288	0.051	0.249	3.355	10
4096	Separate (4 FFTs)	0.534	0.068	0.499	2.587	10
8192	Single batched FFT	1.660	1.051	0.593	3.744	10
8192	Separate (4 FFTs)	2.274	1.037	1.126	5.289	10

FIGURE 11. The plot shows the runtime for different grid size of single FFT (our approach) versus the classical four-fold approach and confirms that the median time of the execution on the increasing grid size keeps consistency and has better results. The time for the single FFT computation (our approach) is around 45% faster than the classical.

Empirical Hedging with FFT-based Greeks

Contributions. We implement Fourier-based Greeks for European options by differentiating the Carr-Madan (1999) damped transform under the integral, combined with the stable Heston characteristic function of Lord and Kahl (2010). A single FFT evaluation yields price, Delta, Gamma, and $\partial C/\partial v_0$ (Vega with respect to initial variance), avoiding finite-difference noise. We validate numerically via (i) Black-Scholes limit tests (Heston \rightarrow BS when variance is deterministic), (ii) model-agnostic static-arbitrage checks (bounds, monotonicity, convexity), and (iii) sensitivity to FFT discretization parameters (N, η, α, k_0) with explicit acceptance thresholds. Finally, we apply the FFT Greeks to real market quotes to assess hedging performance, illustrating that transform-based Greeks deliver stable and accurate risk measures in practice.

1. Live Market Data: Deribit European Options (Source, Endpoints, Units)

Source (official). We use the *public REST API* of the Deribit exchange to fetch a small live cross-section of **European, cash-settled** crypto options.¹ Deribit confirms that its options are *European style* (exercise only at expiry) and cash-settled; this applies to the inverse (coin-settled) products used below and to their newer linear USDC-settled products.²

Endpoints (read-only). We only call public, read-only methods:

- `/public/get_index_price` to obtain the USD index level S_0 (BTC index).³
- `/public/get_instruments` to list live option instruments (strike K , expiry timestamp, call/put).⁴
- `/public/ticker` to read best bid/ask for each instrument and form the mid quote.⁵

These three endpoints are sufficient to build a clean cross-section (one expiry, many strikes) for pricing and Greeks comparisons.

Why this dataset fits our method. Our numerical framework (Carr-Madan FFT with the Lord-Kahl stable Heston characteristic function) is derived for *European* options. Deribit’s options are European and cash-settled, so there is *no early-exercise bias* and no discrete dividend adjustments are needed; therefore the model assumptions match the contract design. Moreover, the API exposes the *full instrument grid* at a point in time (strikes

¹<https://docs.deribit.com/> (API docs; production base URL <https://www.deribit.com/api/v2>; accessed 12 Sep 2025).

²European & cash-settled options: Deribit support article “Inverse Options” <https://support.deribit.com/hc/en-us/articles/25944688327069-Inverse-Options> (accessed 12 Sep 2025). See also “Linear USDC Options” <https://support.deribit.com/hc/en-us/articles/25944750999581-Linear-USDC-Options> (accessed 12 Sep 2025).

³https://www.deribit.com/api/v2/public/get_index_price, documented at <https://docs.deribit.com/> (accessed 12 Sep 2025).

⁴https://www.deribit.com/api/v2/public/get_instruments, documented at <https://docs.deribit.com/> (accessed 12 Sep 2025).

⁵<https://www.deribit.com/api/v2/public/ticker>, documented at <https://docs.deribit.com/> (accessed 12 Sep 2025).

and a nearby expiry), which is exactly what we need to validate monotonicity/convexity in K and to compare FFT prices and Greeks against live mids.

Units and conversion (BTC \rightarrow USD).. Inverse BTC options on Deribit are *quoted in BTC* (premium per BTC). To compare against our USD-denominated model outputs, we convert quotes to USD via

$$\text{mid}_{\text{USD}} = \text{mid}_{\text{BTC}} \times S_0,$$

where S_0 is the BTC USD index from `get_index_price`.⁶ After conversion, we evaluate standard *USD* sanity constraints:

$$\begin{aligned} \max\{S_0 e^{-qT} - K e^{-rT}, 0\} &\leq C \leq S_0 e^{-qT} \\ 0 &\leq \Delta \leq e^{-qT} \\ \Gamma &\geq 0 \end{aligned}$$

and nonnegative vega with respect to the initial variance v_0 for $T > 0$.

Practical details used in this paper. We select the nearest expiry with a minimum number of liquid calls (nonzero bid/ask, ask $>$ bid), compute T from the exchange timestamps, and set $q = 0$. For the BS-limit anchor we estimate an ATM implied volatility from the USD mid at $K \approx S_0$ and set $v_0 = \theta = \sigma_{\text{ATM}}^2$ (with κ large, σ small, $\rho = 0$), then compute FFT price and Greeks on a strike grid. All data are fetched directly from <https://www.deribit.com/api/v2> at run time; no historical downloads or paid feeds are required.

We present the results with tables for the completeness only. The available code can be analyzed for the further details.

⁶Deribit’s documentation and education pages discuss inverse (coin-settled) vs. linear (USDC-settled) conventions and the resulting payoff/PNL units; see e.g. <https://insights.deribit.com/education/what-is-an-options-contract/> and the linear/inverse notes <https://support.deribit.com/hc/en-us/articles/25944750999581-Linear-USDC-Options> (accessed 12 Sep 2025).

TABLE 6. Deribit BTC calls (USDC), expiry 2025-09-14 08:00:00+00:00 (rows=16). Prices/Greeks via Carr-Madan FFT (Heston CF, BS-limit anchor). ATM $\sigma \approx 0.1517$.

instrument	K	T_{days}	mid_usd	$P_{\text{usd}}^{\text{FFT}}$	Δ	Γ	$\partial C / \partial v_0$	bound	Δ	bd	$\Gamma \geq 0$	$\partial C / \partial \theta_0 \geq 0$
BTC.USDC-14SEP25-104000-C	104,000	0.58	11,641.7	11,626.8	1	-4.73484×10^{-14}	-2.85368×10^{-6}	True	True	True	True	True
BTC.USDC-14SEP25-106000-C	106,000	0.58	9,642.12	9,626.88	1	2.49811×10^{-14}	-2.20047×10^{-6}	True	True	True	True	True
BTC.USDC-14SEP25-108000-C	108,000	0.58	7,642.56	7,626.96	1	6.65914×10^{-15}	-2.44545×10^{-6}	True	True	True	True	True
BTC.USDC-14SEP25-109000-C	109,000	0.58	6,642.93	6,626.99	1	-8.07874×10^{-15}	-2.60583×10^{-6}	True	True	True	True	True
BTC.USDC-14SEP25-110000-C	110,000	0.58	5,643.12	5,627.01	1	-7.10779×10^{-15}	-2.59993×10^{-6}	True	True	True	True	True
BTC.USDC-14SEP25-111000-C	111,000	0.58	4,643.93	4,627.06	1	8.06166×10^{-14}	-1.73029×10^{-6}	True	True	True	True	True
BTC.USDC-14SEP25-112000-C	112,000	0.58	3,646.34	3,627.08	1	6.48431×10^{-10}	6.40857×10^{-3}	True	True	True	True	True
BTC.USDC-14SEP25-113000-C	113,000	0.58	2,647.6	2,627.13	0.999922	4.43472×10^{-7}	4.38465	True	True	True	True	True
BTC.USDC-14SEP25-114000-C	114,000	0.58	1,650.13	1,629.5	0.990122	3.74452×10^{-5}	370.224	True	True	True	True	True
BTC.USDC-14SEP25-115000-C	115,000	0.58	686.48	698.821	0.814624	3.79097×10^{-4}	3,748.16	True	True	True	True	True
BTC.USDC-14SEP25-116000-C	116,000	0.58	132.5	133.481	0.299643	4.93287×10^{-4}	4,877.17	True	True	True	True	True
BTC.USDC-14SEP25-117000-C	117,000	0.58	25	7.03246	0.0263324	8.67836×10^{-5}	858.037	True	True	True	True	True
BTC.USDC-14SEP25-118000-C	118,000	0.58	16.89	0.0757497	4.14588×10^{-4}	2.12799×10^{-6}	21.0397	True	True	True	True	True
BTC.USDC-14SEP25-119000-C	119,000	0.58	15	0.000150585	1.09988×10^{-6}	7.72689×10^{-9}	0.076394	True	True	True	True	True
BTC.USDC-14SEP25-120000-C	120,000	0.58	0.51	-1.52790×10^{-7}	4.86580×10^{-10}	4.32679×10^{-12}	4.04349×10^{-5}	True	True	True	True	True
BTC.USDC-14SEP25-122000-C	122,000	0.58	0.06	-2.19077×10^{-7}	9.89417×10^{-12}	-7.16133×10^{-15}	-2.33404×10^{-6}	True	True	True	True	True

TABLE 7. Deribit BTC calls (USDC), expiry 2025-09-15 08:00:00+00:00 (rows=15). ATM $\sigma \approx 0.2015$.

instrument	K	T_{days}	mid.usd	$P_{\text{usd}}^{\text{FFT}}$	Δ	Γ	$\partial C / \partial v_0$	bounds	Δ bd	$\Gamma \geq 0$	$\partial C / \partial v_0 \geq 0$
BTC_USDC-15SEP25-106000-C	106,000	1.58	9,689.95	9,632.69	1	1.17424×10^{-13}	-3.06266×10^{-6}	True	True	True	True
BTC_USDC-15SEP25-108000-C	108,000	1.58	7,690.89	7,632.88	1	4.54988×10^{-10}	1.07029×10^{-2}	True	True	True	True
BTC_USDC-15SEP25-110000-C	110,000	1.58	5,696.31	5,633.07	0.999917	2.16999×10^{-7}	5.10741	True	True	True	True
BTC_USDC-15SEP25-111000-C	111,000	1.58	4,711.91	4,633.57	0.998987	2.21933×10^{-6}	52.2356	True	True	True	True
BTC_USDC-15SEP25-112000-C	112,000	1.58	3,720.75	3,637.30	0.992002	1.42616×10^{-5}	335.671	True	True	True	True
BTC_USDC-15SEP25-113000-C	113,000	1.58	2,726.67	2,658.83	0.959159	5.70646×10^{-5}	1,343.11	True	True	True	True
BTC_USDC-15SEP25-114000-C	114,000	1.58	1,782.61	1,744.21	0.859388	1.45325×10^{-4}	3,420.47	True	True	True	True
BTC_USDC-15SEP25-115000-C	115,000	1.58	985	979.585	0.662766	2.37699×10^{-4}	5,594.65	True	True	True	True
BTC_USDC-15SEP25-116000-C	116,000	1.58	447.5	447.992	0.408463	2.52800×10^{-4}	5,950.07	True	True	True	True
BTC_USDC-15SEP25-117000-C	117,000	1.58	187.5	159.614	0.190018	1.76705×10^{-4}	4,159.04	True	True	True	True
BTC_USDC-15SEP25-118000-C	118,000	1.58	90	42.8485	0.0643678	8.19650×10^{-5}	1,929.18	True	True	True	True
BTC_USDC-15SEP25-119000-C	119,000	1.58	52.5	8.48976	0.0155918	2.55020×10^{-5}	600.23	True	True	True	True
BTC_USDC-15SEP25-120000-C	120,000	1.58	35	1.22333	0.00267502	5.37445×10^{-6}	126.497	True	True	True	True
BTC_USDC-15SEP25-122000-C	122,000	1.58	13.34	0.00969503	2.82089×10^{-5}	7.80694×10^{-8}	1.83749	True	True	True	True
BTC_USDC-15SEP25-124000-C	124,000	1.58	1.98	2.15072×10^{-5}	7.59888×10^{-9}	2.68425×10^{-10}	6.31269×10^{-3}	True	True	True	True

FIGURE 12.

Data and method. We construct call slices from Deribit’s live book (USDC–linear when available; otherwise inverse BTC–settled converted to USD via the index). For each expiry we anchor a near–Black–Scholes Heston parameter set to the ATM implied volatility (this is *not* a calibration). Prices and Greeks are computed on a dense log–strike grid via the Carr–Madan FFT [9], using Simpson frequency weights and the Lord–Kahl stable Heston characteristic function [24, 20]. We take damping $\alpha = 2$, grid $N = 2^{16}$, step $\eta \approx 0.08$, and exact window centering $k_0 = \log S_0 - \frac{1}{2}N\Delta k$ with $\Delta k = 2\pi/(N\eta)$. Interpolating to market strikes yields $\Delta, \Gamma, \partial C/\partial v_0$.

Intpretation. Option prices satisfy the Merton bounds and, by Breeden–Litzenberger,

$$\partial C/\partial K = -e^{-rT}\mathbb{Q}(S_T > K) \leq 0$$

(monotone in K) and

$$\partial^2 C/\partial K^2 = e^{-rT}f_{S_T}(K) \geq 0$$

(convex in K) [3]. The rare, tiny excursions we observe for deep OTM or sub–day maturities are standard FFT finite–band artefacts (truncation/periodization). They shrink to numerical zero when we increase the Fourier band $B = N\eta$, raise α , refine N , and keep k_0 centered. In the near–ATM region that drives hedging and calibration, all checks pass.

FIGURE 13. Delta violation

FIGURE 14. Gamma violation

FIGURE 15. Vega violation

Explanation. Model-agnostic checks for FFT-based Heston prices/Greeks (USD). We verify per expiry: (i) Merton bounds $\max\{S_0 e^{-qT} - K e^{-rT}, 0\} \leq C \leq S_0 e^{-qT}$, (ii) $0 \leq \Delta \leq e^{-qT}$, (iii) $\Gamma \geq 0$, (iv) $\partial C / \partial v_0 \geq 0$, and (v) monotone/convex $C(K)$. Histograms show violation magnitudes; bars at 0 mean the constraint is met. Occasional tiny excursions (deep OTM, sub-day T) are classic FFT truncation/periodization artefacts and vanish as we increase damping α , resolution N , reduce step η , and center the window $k_0 = \log S_0 - \frac{1}{2} N \Delta k$ with $\Delta k = 2\pi / (N\eta)$

Setup. Prices/Greeks via Carr-Madan FFT (Heston CF, BS limit). Quotes converted BTC \rightarrow USD before checks.

Conclusion

1. Starting and ending point of our research

In this thesis we have developed and implemented FFT-based Greeks for the Heston model by differentiating the Carr-Madan damped pricing transform under the integral. A key methodological contribution is the demonstration that price, Delta, Gamma, and the sensitivity with respect to initial variance can be obtained from a *single* FFT evaluation. This unified framework provides not only theoretical elegance but also a substantial computational gain compared to separate quadrature or multiple FFT runs. We verified the legitimacy of differentiation under the integral, ensuring that the approach remains well posed within the Heston moment conditions. The numerical experiments confirm that the FFT-based Greeks are accurate, stable, and logically consistent. Across standard benchmarks the method recovers closed-form results in the Black–Scholes limit and satisfies model-agnostic static-arbitrage constraints such as rational bounds, convexity, and monotonicity in strike. Error analysis shows that FFT-based results match high-precision quadrature within tight tolerances, while runtime profiling demonstrates a significant reduction in computation time due to the single-FFT strategy. Sensitivity analysis further highlights the method’s robustness across parameter regimes, with errors controllable by standard grid refinements and damping adjustments.

2. Lessons we can take from this study

This study reinforces several general lessons about the interaction between mathematical modeling and computational implementation. First, even elegant analytic models such as Heston’s stochastic volatility framework depend critically on robust numerical methods to achieve practical accuracy. The Fast Fourier Transform (FFT), when used thoughtfully with appropriate damping and discretization, converts theoretical insight into a fast and reproducible pricing engine. Second, the analytical structure of characteristic functions allows for the unified computation of Greeks—showing how differentiation and transform methods can together reduce computational complexity while preserving stability. Finally, numerical experiments highlight that efficiency is never a substitute for theoretical correctness: differentiation under the integral and proper moment conditions are essential to preserve model integrity.

3. Looking at Pure and Applied Mathematics: The Interplay for Successful Wealth Management

The broader implication of this research extends beyond option pricing. The methods developed here illustrate how *pure mathematics*—complex analysis, Fourier theory, and stochastic calculus—can directly inform *applied financial engineering*. Through this interplay, abstract concepts such as characteristic functions and moment generating properties become the computational foundations of real-world decision-making in risk management and asset allocation.

In wealth management, these ideas translate into tangible outcomes: better hedging accuracy, improved sensitivity analysis, and reduced computational risk when calibrating portfolios to market volatility. This synthesis of theoretical and applied thinking—rooted in the mathematical rigor of Black–Scholes [2], Heston [20], Gatheral [19], and refined through modern computational methods such as Carr–Madan [9] and Fang–Oosterlee [16]—embodies the ideal of quantitative finance: to convert mathematical structure into economic insight.

4. Limitations and Future Work

Despite the numerical efficiency of the single-FFT formulation, certain aspects remain open for future research. The following directions may further advance this framework:

- **Calibration under market microstructure noise.** Incorporating observed bid–ask spreads, discrete tick sizes, and asynchronous price data into the calibration of the Heston model may improve empirical robustness and model stability.
- **Extension to rough volatility and stochastic interest rates.** Extending the Fourier-transform approach to rough volatility models or to Heston models with stochastic short rates could capture additional empirical features of financial markets.
- **Adaptive FFT grids and spectral accuracy.** Developing adaptive integration grids or nonuniform FFT methods would enhance numerical accuracy in extreme strikes and improve convergence for Greeks with high-frequency amplification.

These directions naturally continue the present work toward a unified and robust class of Fourier-based methods for stochastic volatility modeling, bridging theoretical tractability and computational efficiency.

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Appendix 1 - Glossary of technical terms in the thesis

In order to not overwhelm the course of the thesis, we give in this appendix the explanation of some concepts which do not play a central role in the thesis; however, we believe they need to be included in order for the reader to fully understand the scientific and mathematical context in which they appear. The reference is any standard numerical book such as [28] accompanied with a quantitative finance book such as [33].

- **Affine Characteristic Function.** A function of the form $\phi(z) = \exp(C(z, T) + D(z, T)v_0 + iz \ln S_0)$, typical for stochastic volatility models such as Heston. The term “affine” refers to the linear dependence on the initial variance v_0 .
- **At-the-Money (ATM) and Related Moneyness Terms.** The *moneyness* of an option describes the relationship between the current underlying price S_0 and the strike price K . An option is *At-the-Money (ATM)* when $K = S_0$, *In-the-Money (ITM)* when it has intrinsic value ($S_0 > K$ for calls, $S_0 < K$ for puts), and *Out-of-the-Money (OTM)* when it has no intrinsic value. In the context of FFT-based pricing, ATM strikes are often used as numerical benchmarks because the payoff and characteristic-function integrands are most balanced there, providing a natural test of algorithmic stability.
- **Attari’s Modification (2004).** An alternative Fourier-transform formulation of option prices that improves the numerical efficiency and stability of the Carr–Madan (1999) FFT method. In the original Carr–Madan approach, the payoff is exponentially damped by $e^{\alpha k}$ to ensure square-integrability of its Fourier transform, introducing a damping parameter that must be tuned manually. Attari (2004) derived a representation in which the integrand is inherently square-integrable without artificial damping, by analytically reformulating the payoff in terms of the log-return and characteristic function of $\ln S_T$. This yields a simpler and faster single-integral expression, requiring no arbitrary α , and avoids numerical sensitivity near the origin. Schmelzle (2010) later incorporated this modification in his unified Fourier pricing framework, demonstrating that Attari’s formulation performs robustly across both equity and FX options. See: Attari, M. *Option Pricing Using Fourier Transforms: A Numerically Efficient Simplification* (<https://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.520042>)
- **Carr–Madan Transform.** A Fourier representation of the option price based on a *damped* call payoff $c_\alpha(k) = e^{\alpha k} C(e^k)$, which ensures integrability of the Fourier transform and allows efficient evaluation via FFT.
- **Characteristic Function (ϕ).** The Fourier transform of the log-price distribution under the risk-neutral measure. In Heston, ϕ admits a closed form depending on complex functions $C(z, T)$ and $D(z, T)$.
- **Conditional Value at Risk (CVaR) / Expected Shortfall (ES).** A coherent risk measure that represents the *expected loss conditional on losses exceeding VaR*. For the same loss random variable L , it is defined as

$$\text{CVaR}_\alpha(L) = \mathbb{E}[L \mid L \geq \text{VaR}_\alpha(L)],$$

or equivalently as the average of tail losses beyond the α -quantile. CVaR therefore provides more comprehensive information about the tail behaviour of losses and is subadditive, making it theoretically superior to VaR for portfolio optimization and regulatory capital assessment. In practice, CVaR complements VaR by quantifying the *severity* of extreme events rather than merely their probability.

- **Convexity in Strike and Gamma Positivity.** The option price as a function of strike must be convex for arbitrage-free models, implying that the second derivative with respect to strike (or equivalently, Γ with respect to S_0) is nonnegative. In numerical experiments, maintaining positive Γ across strikes indicates both mathematical soundness and numerical stability. Loss of convexity typically signals discretization or aliasing errors in the Fourier inversion.
- **Damping Parameter (α).** A positive real constant introduced in the Carr–Madan method to make the call payoff integrable. Small α gives slow tail decay; large α increases round-off error. Typical values for calls are $\alpha \in [1, 2]$.
- **Delta (Δ).** The first derivative of the option price with respect to the underlying price S_0 . Measures the rate of change of the option value when the underlying moves.
- **Dupire’s Local Volatility Formula.** Introduced by Bruno Dupire (1994), the local volatility framework models the instantaneous volatility as a deterministic function of both time t and asset level S_t , denoted $\sigma_{\text{loc}}(t, S_t)$. Under risk-neutral dynamics,

$$dS_t = (r - q)S_t dt + \sigma_{\text{loc}}(t, S_t)S_t dW_t,$$

Dupire derived a direct relationship between the local volatility surface and observable European call prices $C(K, T)$:

$$\sigma_{\text{loc}}^2(K, T) = \frac{2 \partial_T C(K, T)}{K^2 \partial_{KK} C(K, T)}.$$

This formula allows one to back out the implied volatility function consistent with the entire market surface. However, local volatility models cannot capture stochastic or clustered volatility effects.

- **Efficiency.** The measure of computational performance balancing accuracy, stability, and speed. In numerical finance, an algorithm is considered efficient if it achieves a desired error tolerance with minimal computational cost, typically quantified by lower asymptotic complexity (e.g. $\mathcal{O}(N \log N)$ versus $\mathcal{O}(N^2)$) or faster convergence per unit of runtime. Efficiency represents the practical payoff of a theoretically sound model.
- **Error Metrics for Numerical Greeks.** The accuracy of FFT-based Greeks is often quantified using absolute and relative errors against benchmark (e.g. closed-form or high-precision) values. The *absolute error* $|G_{\text{FFT}} - G_{\text{ref}}|$ measures direct deviation, while the *relative error* $|G_{\text{FFT}} - G_{\text{ref}}|/|G_{\text{ref}}|$ normalizes this by magnitude. Plotting histograms of relative errors for Δ , Γ , or Vega $_{v_0}$ reveals how tightly the FFT-based estimates cluster around true values. A narrow, symmetric histogram centered near zero indicates both accuracy and robustness, whereas long tails or skewness expose numerical instability or systematic bias.
- **FFT (Fast Fourier Transform).** An algorithm for computing discrete Fourier transforms in $\mathcal{O}(N \log N)$ time instead of $\mathcal{O}(N^2)$. It enables efficient computation of option prices and Greeks for a grid of strikes from one frequency-domain evaluation.

- **Fractional Brownian Motion (fBM).** A continuous Gaussian process $\{W_t^H\}_{t \geq 0}$ with zero mean and covariance

$$\mathbb{E}[W_t^H W_s^H] = \frac{1}{2}(t^{2H} + s^{2H} - |t - s|^{2H}),$$

where $H \in (0, 1)$ is the *Hurst exponent*. For $H = \frac{1}{2}$, fBM reduces to standard Brownian motion. When $H < \frac{1}{2}$, increments are negatively correlated (*rough*), while $H > \frac{1}{2}$ implies persistence and long memory. fBM underlies rough volatility models, explaining the empirically observed fractal nature of realized volatility trajectories.

- **Frequency Domain / Fourier Space.** The space in which functions are represented by their oscillatory frequency components rather than their values over time or price. Option prices and sensitivities are often computed in this domain.
- **GARCH-Type Models.** The Generalized Autoregressive Conditional Heteroskedasticity (GARCH) family, introduced by Bollerslev (1986), models discrete-time conditional variance as

$$\sigma_t^2 = \omega + \alpha \epsilon_{t-1}^2 + \beta \sigma_{t-1}^2,$$

where ϵ_{t-1} are past residuals. These models capture volatility clustering—large shocks tend to be followed by large volatility—and are widely used in econometrics and risk forecasting. Continuous-time analogues of GARCH dynamics motivate stochastic volatility models like Heston and Hull–White.

- **Gamma (Γ).** The second derivative of the option price with respect to S_0 . Indicates curvature of the price function and sensitivity of Δ .
- **Greek-Specific Integrand.** In Fourier-based option pricing, a *Greek-specific integrand* refers to the modified Fourier kernel obtained by differentiating the pricing integral with respect to a model parameter or initial condition. For example, differentiating the Carr–Madan pricing transform with respect to the initial spot S_0 introduces additional multiplicative factors in the integrand (e.g. $i\xi/S_0$ for Delta, $i\xi(i\xi - 1)/S_0^2$ for Gamma, or $D(\xi, T)$ for Vega). These parameter-dependent factors define distinct “Greek-specific” integrands whose Fourier inversion yields the corresponding sensitivities. This technique, first formalized in de Oliveira and Mordecki (2014), enables the simultaneous evaluation of prices and Greeks within the same FFT framework by replacing the characteristic function $\phi(\xi)$ with its analytical derivatives.
- **Greeks.** Partial derivatives of an option price with respect to inputs such as underlying price, volatility, interest rate, or time. They measure various sensitivities crucial for hedging.
- **Heston Model.** A stochastic volatility model with mean-reverting variance process. The asset price S_t follows $dS_t = (r - q)S_t dt + \sqrt{v_t} S_t dW_t^S$, and the variance v_t follows $dv_t = \kappa(\theta - v_t) dt + \sigma \sqrt{v_t} dW_t^v$ with correlation ρ between the Brownian motions.
- **Lévy Models.** Lévy models generalize Brownian-motion-based dynamics by allowing the asset’s log-returns to follow a process with jumps and continuous components. A Lévy process $\{X_t\}_{t > 0}$ satisfies independent and stationary increments and is fully characterized by its *Lévy–Khintchine representation*, whose characteristic exponent captures drift, diffusion, and jump intensity. When used in finance, $S_t = S_0 e^{X_t}$ produces realistic heavy tails and asymmetric return distributions, fitting market data with volatility smiles and skews that constant-volatility models cannot reproduce. Prominent examples include the Variance

Gamma, Normal Inverse Gaussian, and CGMY models, which retain tractable characteristic functions and are naturally compatible with FFT-based pricing frameworks.

- **Little Heston Trap.** A branch-stabilization method proposed by Albrecher et al. (2007) to avoid discontinuities when evaluating complex logarithms in the Heston characteristic function.
- **Moment Explosion Boundary.** The upper bound on α such that the exponential moment $\mathbb{E}[S_T^{\alpha+1}]$ is finite. Choosing α below this threshold ensures integrability and stable Fourier inversion.
- **Numerical Damping / Smoothing Weights.** Techniques (e.g., Simpson’s rule) used to reduce oscillations in numerical integration, especially important for higher-order Greeks where high-frequency noise is amplified.
- **Parameter Sensitivities in the Heston Model.** Sensitivities, or *Greeks*, measure how the option price reacts to small perturbations in model inputs or market parameters. For instance, $\Delta = \partial C / \partial S_0$ quantifies sensitivity to the underlying price, $\Gamma = \partial^2 C / \partial S_0^2$ captures convexity, and $\text{Vega}_{v_0} = \partial C / \partial v_0$ measures responsiveness to initial variance. By examining how these sensitivities behave across strikes and maturities, one can assess the internal consistency of both the model and the numerical implementation. In the Heston framework, correctly shaped sensitivities (e.g. positive Γ , smooth Δ) also confirm the absence of static arbitrage violations.
- **Quadrature.** A numerical integration technique that approximates the value of a definite integral by summing weighted function evaluations. In computational finance, quadrature is used to evaluate Fourier or expectation integrals when no closed form exists. The computational complexity of standard quadrature schemes (e.g. trapezoidal or Simpson’s rule) grows as $\mathcal{O}(N)$, where N is the number of integration points, compared with $\mathcal{O}(N \log N)$ for FFT-based methods. Quadrature thus provides accuracy but may become computationally expensive for dense grids or multidimensional problems.
- **Quadrature Weights.** Numerical coefficients (such as trapezoidal or Simpson weights) applied to discretized integrands to approximate continuous Fourier integrals accurately.
- **Riccati Equation (for C and D).** A pair of ordinary differential equations governing the evolution of the Heston characteristic function coefficients $C(u, T)$ and $D(u, T)$. Their closed-form solution makes Heston analytically tractable.
- **Robustness.** The degree to which a numerical or statistical method produces stable, reliable results under small perturbations of input data, parameters, or discretization settings. A robust algorithm maintains accuracy across different parameter regimes and is insensitive to rounding errors or branch discontinuities—properties particularly valuable in stochastic volatility calibration and option pricing.
- **Rough Volatility Models.** Empirical studies show that volatility time series exhibit long memory and roughness, inconsistent with the smooth diffusion assumption of classical models. Rough volatility models (e.g. Gatheral, Jaisson, and Rosenbaum, 2018) describe the log-variance as driven by a *fractional Brownian motion* (fBM) with Hurst exponent $H < \frac{1}{2}$:

$$dX_t = \mu dt + \nu dW_t^H,$$

where W_t^H has correlated, non-Markovian increments. These models reproduce empirical volatility roughness and improve short-maturity smile fits while preserving analytical tractability via fractional calculus techniques.

- **Static Arbitrage Constraints.** Conditions ensuring economically consistent pricing surfaces, including monotonicity in strike, convexity, and positive Gamma. Violations indicate numerical or modeling errors.
- **Stochastic Volatility Models (SVMs).** In SVMs, the instantaneous variance itself follows a random process, introducing an additional source of uncertainty. Examples include:
 - **Heston Model (1993):** variance mean-reverting diffusion with correlation ρ .
 - **Hull–White (1987):** lognormal mean-reverting variance process.
 - **SABR Model (Hagan et al., 2002):** captures smiles and skews via stochastic volatility and correlation.
- **Truncation Boundary (B).** The cutoff in Fourier space where integration is stopped; must be chosen large enough so that the tail contribution is negligible but small enough to avoid aliasing.
- **Value at Risk (VaR).** A widely used risk measure that quantifies the potential loss in the value of a portfolio over a specified time horizon at a given confidence level. Formally, for a loss random variable L , the α -level Value at Risk is defined as the α -quantile of its distribution,

$$\text{VaR}_\alpha(L) = \inf\{\ell \in \mathbb{R} : \mathbb{P}(L \leq \ell) \geq \alpha\}.$$

For example, a one-day $\text{VaR}_{0.99}$ of \$1,000,000 indicates that losses are expected to exceed \$1,000,000 with probability only 1%. VaR captures the extreme quantile of the loss distribution but does not account for the magnitude of losses beyond this threshold, which motivates the complementary use of Conditional Value at Risk (CVaR) for assessing tail severity.

- **Vega with Respect to Initial Variance (Vega_{v_0}).** Sensitivity of the option price to changes in the initial variance parameter v_0 in the Heston model, obtained by differentiating the characteristic function with respect to v_0 . This Greek measures how the market value of an option responds to changes in the starting level of volatility, providing insight into volatility-of-volatility effects and model calibration stability.
- **Volatility Clustering.** The empirical phenomenon that large (small) returns tend to be followed by large (small) ones, leading to periods of high and low volatility—evidence against constant-volatility assumptions. This temporal dependence motivates models with stochastic or regime-switching volatility dynamics.
- **Volatility Smiles and Skews.** The *implied volatility smile* refers to the observed curvature in implied volatilities plotted against strike price: deep in-the-money and out-of-the-money options have higher implied volatilities than at-the-money options. A *skew* describes asymmetry in this curve, often with higher volatility for out-of-the-money puts (the “volatility skew” or “smirk”). Classical Black–Scholes assumes constant volatility, producing a flat line. Stochastic and local volatility models reproduce smiles and skews naturally by allowing volatility to vary over time and across states.

CHAPTER 9

Appendix 2 - Coding

1. Chapter 1

```
import numpy as np, pandas as pd, matplotlib.pyplot as plt, yfinance as yf
from datetime import datetime, timedelta

# --- download SPY ---
end = datetime.today()
start = end - timedelta(days=365*5)
spy = yf.download("SPY", start=start, end=end)
close = spy["Close"].dropna()
rets = np.log(close/close.shift(1)).dropna()

# --- rolling volatility (21 trading days 1 month) ---
roll_vol = rets.rolling(21).std() * np.sqrt(252)

plt.figure(figsize=(8,4))
plt.plot(roll_vol, color='navy')
plt.title("SPY: Rolling 21-Day Annualized Volatility")
plt.ylabel("Volatility")
plt.tight_layout(); plt.show()

# --- volatility clustering (squared returns) ---
plt.figure(figsize=(8,4))
plt.plot(rets.index, rets**2, color='darkred')
plt.title("SPY: Squared Daily Log-Returns (Volatility Clustering)")
plt.ylabel("Squared return")
plt.tight_layout(); plt.show()

from scipy.stats import norm
from scipy.optimize import brentq

def bs_call(S, K, T, r, sigma):
    d1=(np.log(S/K)+(r+0.5*sigma**2)*T)/(sigma*np.sqrt(T))
    d2=d1-sigma*np.sqrt(T)
    return S*norm.cdf(d1)-K*np.exp(-r*T)*norm.cdf(d2)

def implied_vol(mid,S,K,T,r):
    f=lambda s: bs_call(S,K,T,r,s)-mid
    try: return brentq(f,1e-6,5)
    except: return np.nan

ticker=yf.Ticker("SPY")
expiries=ticker.options
```

```

near_exp=expiries[0]; mid_exp=expiries[min(4,len(expiries)-1)]
S=float(close.iloc[-1]); r=0.02
asof=pd.to_datetime(close.index[-1])

def smile(exp):
    chain=ticker.option_chain(exp).calls
    T=(pd.to_datetime(exp)-asof).days/365
    chain["mid"]=0.5*(chain["bid"]+chain["ask"])
    df=chain[(chain["mid"]>0)&(chain["bid"]>0)]
    df["iv"]=df.apply(lambda r_: implied_vol(r_["mid"],S,r_["strike"],T,r),axis=1)
    df["moneyness"]=df["strike"]/S
    return df.dropna(subset=["iv"]),T

smiles=[]; labels=[]
for exp in [near_exp,mid_exp]:
    df,T=smile(exp)
    smiles.append(df.sort_values("moneyness"))
    labels.append(f"{exp} (T{T:.2f}y)")

plt.figure(figsize=(10,4))
for df,lab in zip(smiles,labels):
    plt.plot(df["moneyness"],df["iv"],marker='.',label=lab)
plt.axvline(1.0,linestyle=':')
plt.title("SPY Calls: Implied-Volatility Smile/Skew")
plt.xlabel("Moneyness K/S"); plt.ylabel("Implied Volatility")
plt.legend(); plt.tight_layout(); plt.show()

    from scipy import stats
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

# --- ensure rets is a clean 1D numeric array with enough data ---
rets_arr = np.asarray(rets, dtype=float).ravel()
rets_arr = rets_arr[np.isfinite(rets_arr)] # drop NaN/Inf

if rets_arr.size < 10:
    raise ValueError(f"Not enough returns for QQ-plot (got {rets_arr.size}). "
                    "Check your data download / date range.")

# --- Histogram vs Normal PDF ---
plt.figure(figsize=(6,4))
plt.hist(rets_arr, bins=80, density=True, alpha=0.6, label='Empirical')
mu, sig = rets_arr.mean(), rets_arr.std()
x = np.linspace(rets_arr.min(), rets_arr.max(), 200)
plt.plot(x, stats.norm.pdf(x, mu, sig), 'r--', label='Normal(,)')
plt.title("SPY Daily Log>Returns: Heavy Tails vs Normal")
plt.legend(); plt.tight_layout(); plt.show()

# --- QQ-plot: empirical quantiles vs normal quantiles ---
fig = plt.figure(figsize=(5,5))

```

```

ax = fig.add_subplot(111)
# You can pass the string "norm" or the distribution object stats.norm:
stats.probplot(rets_arr, dist="norm", plot=ax)
ax.set_title("QQ-Plot of SPY Returns vs Normal Distribution")
plt.tight_layout(); plt.show()

```

2. Chapter 5 and 6

```

import numpy as np

# =====
# 1) Stable Heston characteristic function (Lord{Kahl \little trap")
# =====
def heston_charfunc_lord_kahl(u, T, v0, kappa, theta, sigma, rho, r, q, return_CD=False):
    """
    phi(u) = exp(C(u,T) + D(u,T) * v0), stable (Lord & Kahl).
    If return_CD=True, also returns (C, D).
    """
    iu = 1j * u
    a = kappa * theta
    b = kappa - rho * sigma * iu
    d = np.sqrt(b*b + (iu + u*u) * sigma * sigma)
    g = (b - d) / (b + d)
    e = np.exp(-d * T)
    C = (r - q) * iu * T + (a / (sigma*sigma)) * ((b - d) * T - 2.0 * np.log((1 - g)*
    D = ((b - d) / (sigma*sigma)) * ((1 - e) / (1 - g*e))
    phi = np.exp(C + D * v0)
    if return_CD:
        return phi, C, D
    return phi

def phi_logS_shifted(z, S0, T, v0, kappa, theta, sigma, rho, r, q, return_CD=False):
    """
    Characteristic function of log S_T evaluated at shifted argument z = u - i(+1).
    Includes S0^{(+1)} * e^{i u log S0} factor implicitly via exp(i z log S0).
    """
    # exp(i z log S0)
    S_factor = np.exp(1j * z * np.log(S0))
    if return_CD:
        phi, C, D = heston_charfunc_lord_kahl(z, T, v0, kappa, theta, sigma, rho, r, q, return_CD=True)
        return S_factor * phi, C, D
    else:
        phi = heston_charfunc_lord_kahl(z, T, v0, kappa, theta, sigma, rho, r, q)
        return S_factor * phi

# =====
# 2) Reference (single-strike) price and Greeks via analytic integrands
# =====

```

```

def cm_price_singleK(S0, K, T, r, q, v0, kappa, theta, sigma, rho,
                    alpha=1.5, N=2**14, u_max=200.0):
    """
    Carr-Madan damped price at a single strike (high-accuracy quadrature).
    """
    k = np.log(K)
    du = u_max / N
    u = np.arange(N) * du
    beta = alpha + 1.0
    z = u - 1j * beta

    phi = phi_logS_shifted(z, S0, T, v0, kappa, theta, sigma, rho, r, q)
    denom = (alpha**2 + alpha - u*u) + 1j*(2*alpha + 1)*u
    psi = np.exp(-r*T) * phi / denom
    integrand = np.exp(-1j * u * k) * psi # keep complex

    # Simpson weights (complex-safe)
    if (N-1) % 2 == 0:
        w = np.ones(N); w[0]=1.0; w[-1]=1.0; w[1:-1:2]=4.0; w[2:-1:2]=2.0
        integral = (du/3.0) * np.sum(w * integrand)
    else:
        w = np.ones(N); w[0]=0.5; w[-1]=0.5
        integral = du * np.sum(w * integrand)

    C = (np.exp(-alpha * k) / np.pi) * integral
    return float(np.real(C))

def cm_greeks_singleK(S0, K, T, r, q, v0, kappa, theta, sigma, rho,
                    alpha=1.5, N=2**14, u_max=200.0):
    """
    Reference Greeks via analytic differentiation under the integral:
    Delta: multiply integrand by (i z / S0)
    Gamma: multiply integrand by (-(i z + z^2)/S0^2)
    Vega (w.r.t. v0): multiply integrand by D(z), where phi = exp(C + D v0)
    """
    k = np.log(K)
    du = u_max / N
    u = np.arange(N) * du
    beta = alpha + 1.0
    z = u - 1j * beta

    # phi, C, D at shifted argument
    phi, C, D = heston_charfunc_lord_kahl(z, T, v0, kappa, theta, sigma, rho, r, q, r)
    # include S0 factor: exp(i z log S0)
    S_term = np.exp(1j * z * np.log(S0))
    phiS = S_term * phi

    denom = (alpha**2 + alpha - u*u) + 1j*(2*alpha + 1)*u
    base = np.exp(-r*T) * phiS / denom
    phase = np.exp(-1j * u * k)

```

```

# Price integrand (for completeness; not needed here)
# price_int = phase * base

# Delta integrand: (i z / S0) * (price integrand w/o the final exp(- k)/ factor)
delta_int = phase * base * (1j * z / S0)

# Gamma integrand: -(i z + z^2)/S0^2 * base * phase
gamma_int = phase * base * (-(1j * z + z*z) / (S0*S0))

# Vega(v0) integrand: D(z) * base * phase
vega_int = phase * base * D

# Simpson weights (complex-safe)
if N % 2 == 0:
    w = np.ones(N); w[0]=1.0; w[-1]=1.0; w[1:-1:2]=4.0; w[2:-1:2]=2.0
    W = (du/3.0) * w
else:
    w = np.ones(N); w[0]=0.5; w[-1]=0.5
    W = du * w

factor = np.exp(-alpha * k) / np.pi

Delta = factor * np.sum(W * delta_int)
Gamma = factor * np.sum(W * gamma_int)
Vega = factor * np.sum(W * vega_int)

# Greeks must be real for real inputs
return float(np.real(Delta)), float(np.real(Gamma)), float(np.real(Vega))

# =====
# 3) FFT (Carr{Madan) grid: price and Greeks via analytic integrands
# =====
def cm_fft_grid_all(S0, T, r, q, v0, kappa, theta, sigma, rho,
                    alpha=1.5, N=2**12, eta=0.25, k0=None):
    """
    Return (k_grid, Price, Delta, Gamma, Vega_v0) arrays (length N)
    using a single FFT for each integrand flavor.
    """
    if k0 is None:
        k0 = np.log(S0) - 3.0

    m = np.arange(N)
    u = m * eta
    beta = alpha + 1.0
    z = u - 1j * beta

    # phi, C, D at shifted argument
    phi, C, D = heston_charfunc_lord_kahl(z, T, v0, kappa, theta, sigma, rho, r, q, r)
    S_term = np.exp(1j * z * np.log(S0))

```

```

phiS    = S_term * phi

denom = (alpha**2 + alpha - u*u) + 1j*(2*alpha + 1)*u
base   = np.exp(-r*T) * phiS / denom

# The four frequency-domain inputs (price + 3 Greeks)
F_price = base
F_delta = base * (1j * z / S0)
F_gamma = base * (-(1j * z + z*z) / (S0*S0))
F_vega  = base * D

# Simpson weights in frequency
w = np.ones(N); w[0]=1.0; w[-1]=1.0; w[1:-1:2]=4.0; w[2:-1:2]=2.0
w *= (eta / 3.0)

# strike spacing
dk = 2.0 * np.pi / (N * eta)
j  = np.arange(N)
k  = k0 + j * dk

# Common complex FFT kernel
kern = np.exp(-1j * u * k0) * w / np.pi # 1/pi factor here

# FFTs
P = np.fft.fft(F_price * kern)
Df = np.fft.fft(F_delta * kern)
Gf = np.fft.fft(F_gamma * kern)
Vf = np.fft.fft(F_vega * kern)

# Undo damping per strike: exp(-alpha * k)
damp = np.exp(-alpha * k)

Price = np.real(damp * P)
Delta = np.real(damp * Df)
Gamma = np.real(damp * Gf)
Vega  = np.real(damp * Vf)

return k, Price, Delta, Gamma, Vega

def price_greeks_fft_atK(S0, K, T, r, q, v0, kappa, theta, sigma, rho,
                        alpha=1.5, N=2**12, eta=0.25, k0=None):
    """
    Interpolate FFT-based Price/Greeks to a specific strike K.
    """
    k_grid, P, D, G, V = cm_fft_grid_all(S0, T, r, q, v0, kappa, theta, sigma, rho,
                                         alpha, N, eta, k0)
    k = np.log(K)
    # linear interpolation
    if k <= k_grid[0]:
        return float(P[0]), float(D[0]), float(G[0]), float(V[0])

```

```

if k >= k_grid[-1]:
    return float(P[-1]), float(D[-1]), float(G[-1]), float(V[-1])
idx = np.searchsorted(k_grid, k) - 1
t = (k - k_grid[idx]) / (k_grid[idx+1] - k_grid[idx])
price = (1-t)*P[idx] + t*P[idx+1]
delta = (1-t)*D[idx] + t*D[idx+1]
gamma = (1-t)*G[idx] + t*G[idx+1]
vega = (1-t)*V[idx] + t*V[idx+1]
return float(price), float(delta), float(gamma), float(vega)

# =====
# 4) Demo / Comparison printout
# =====
if __name__ == "__main__":
    # Parameters
    S0 = 100.0
    r, q = 0.00, 0.00
    kappa = 2.0
    theta = 0.04
    sigma = 0.6
    rho = -0.7
    v0 = 0.05

    strikes = [90.0, 100.0, 110.0]
    maturities = [0.25, 1.0]

    # Reference quadrature controls
    alpha_ref = 1.5
    N_ref = 2**14
    u_max_ref = 200.0

    # FFT grid controls
    alpha_fft = 1.5
    N_fft = 2**12
    eta_fft = 0.25
    k0_fft = np.log(S0) - 3.0 # keep fixed (don't depend on complex S0)

    print("=== Heston: FFT-based vs Reference (Analytic-Integral Greeks) ===\n")
    header = ("T      K      "
              "Price_ref    Price_FFT    "
              "Delta_ref     Delta_FFT    "
              "Gamma_ref     Gamma_FFT    "
              "Vega_ref      Vega_FFT     "
              "|e_P|         |e_D|         |e_G|         |e_V|")
    print(header)
    print("-"*len(header))

    for T in maturities:
        for K in strikes:
            # Reference (single-strike quadrature)

```

```

C_ref = cm_price_singleK(S0, K, T, r, q, v0, kappa, theta, sigma, rho,
                        alpha=alpha_ref, N=N_ref, u_max=u_max_ref)
D_ref, G_ref, V_ref = cm_greeks_singleK(S0, K, T, r, q, v0, kappa, theta,
                                       alpha=alpha_ref, N=N_ref, u_max=u_max_ref)

# FFT-based (interpolated at K)
C_fft, D_fft, G_fft, V_fft = price_greeks_fft_atK(S0, K, T, r, q, v0, kappa, theta, sigma, rho,
                                                  alpha=alpha_fft, N=N_fft)

eP = abs(C_fft - C_ref)
eD = abs(D_fft - D_ref)
eG = abs(G_fft - G_ref)
eV = abs(V_fft - V_ref)

print(f"{T:<4.2f} {K:<6.1f} "
      f"{C_ref:>11.6f} {C_fft:>11.6f} "
      f"{D_ref:>10.6f} {D_fft:>10.6f} "
      f"{G_ref:>11.6e} {G_fft:>11.6e} "
      f"{V_ref:>11.6f} {V_fft:>11.6f} "
      f"{eP:>9.2e} {eD:>9.2e} {eG:>9.2e} {eV:>9.2e}")

print("\n=== Explicit FFT-based Greeks ===")
for T in maturities:
    for K in strikes:
        _, D_fft, G_fft, V_fft = price_greeks_fft_atK(S0, K, T, r, q, v0, kappa, theta, sigma, rho,
                                                    alpha=alpha_fft, N=N_fft, u_max=u_max_ref)
        print(f"T={T:.2f}, K={K:.1f} | FFT-based Delta={D_fft:.6f}, "
              f"Gamma={G_fft:.6e}, Vega={V_fft:.6f}")

def finite_diff_greeks_from_price(price_fn, S0, K, T, r, q, v0, kappa, theta, sigma, rho):
    # clean finite-difference checks (reference price function ONLY)
    epsS = 1e-4 * S0
    C0 = price_fn(S0, K, T, r, q, v0, kappa, theta, sigma, rho)
    Cp = price_fn(S0 + epsS, K, T, r, q, v0, kappa, theta, sigma, rho)
    Cm = price_fn(S0 - epsS, K, T, r, q, v0, kappa, theta, sigma, rho)
    Delta_fd = (Cp - Cm) / (2*epsS)
    Gamma_fd = (Cp - 2*C0 + Cm) / (epsS**2)

    epsv = 1e-6 # bump v0 (absolute)
    Cv_p = price_fn(S0, K, T, r, q, v0 + epsv, kappa, theta, sigma, rho)
    Cv_m = price_fn(S0, K, T, r, q, v0 - epsv, kappa, theta, sigma, rho)
    Vega_fd = (Cv_p - Cv_m) / (2*epsv)
    return Delta_fd, Gamma_fd, Vega_fd

def bs_limit_params(sigma_bs):
    return dict(v0=sigma_bs**2, theta=sigma_bs**2, kappa=1e6, sigma=1e-4, rho=0.0)

def run_checks():
    S0, r, q = 100.0, 0.0, 0.0

```

```

v0, kappa, theta, sigma, rho = 0.05, 2.0, 0.04, 0.6, -0.7
Ks = [90.0, 100.0, 110.0]; Ts = [0.25, 1.0]

# tighten reference a bit for testing
pref = dict(alpha=1.5, N=2**15, u_max=250.0) # reference quadrature
pfft = dict(alpha=1.5, N=2**13, eta=0.20, k0=np.log(S0)-3.5) # fft grid

print("\n[1] Ref vs FFT convergence sanity")
for T in Ts:
    for K in Ks:
        C_ref = cm_price_singleK(S0,K,T,r,q,v0,kappa,theta,sigma,rho, **pref)
        D_ref, G_ref, V_ref = cm_greeks_singleK(S0,K,T,r,q,v0,kappa,theta,sigma,rho, **pref)
        C_fft, D_fft, G_fft, V_fft = price_greeks_fft_atK(S0,K,T,r,q,v0,kappa,theta,sigma,rho, **pref)
        print(f"T={T:.2f},K={K:.1f} | dP={abs(C_fft-C_ref):.2e}, dD={abs(D_fft-D_ref):.2e}, dG={abs(G_fft-G_ref):.2e}, dV={abs(V_fft-V_ref):.2e}")

print("\n[2] Financial sanity (bounds/monotonicity/convexity)")
T=0.5
# Check bounds and monotonicity across K
grid = np.linspace(70, 130, 13)
last_price = None
last_delta = None
convex_ok = True
prices = []
for K in grid:
    C = cm_price_singleK(S0,K,T,r,q,v0,kappa,theta,sigma,rho, **pref)
    D,G,V = cm_greeks_singleK(S0,K,T,r,q,v0,kappa,theta,sigma,rho, **pref)
    prices.append(C)
    assert 0.0 <= D <= 1.0 + 1e-6, f"Delta out of bounds: {D}"
    assert G >= -1e-8, f"Gamma negative: {G}"
    assert V >= -1e-6, f"Vega negative: {V}"
    if last_price is not None:
        assert C <= last_price + 1e-8, "Price did not decrease with K"
        assert D <= last_delta + 1e-6, "Delta did not decrease with K"
    last_price, last_delta = C, D
# Convexity via discrete second difference
for i in range(1, len(grid)-1):
    if prices[i-1] - 2*prices[i] + prices[i+1] < -1e-4:
        convex_ok = False
print("Convexity OK:", convex_ok)

print("\n[3] Finite-difference vs analytic-integrand Greeks (reference)")
for T in Ts:
    for K in Ks:
        D_ref, G_ref, V_ref = cm_greeks_singleK(S0,K,T,r,q,v0,kappa,theta,sigma,rho, **pref)
        D_fd, G_fd, V_fd = finite_diff_greeks_from_price(cm_price_singleK, S0,K,T,r,q,v0,kappa,theta,sigma,rho, **pref)
        print(f"T={T:.2f},K={K:.1f} | err={abs(D_ref-D_fd):.2e}, err={abs(G_ref-G_fd):.2e}, err={abs(V_ref-V_fd):.2e}")

print("\n[4] Black{Scholes limit (prices+Greeks)")
sigma_bs = 0.20
hpar = bs_limit_params(sigma_bs)

```

```

from math import log, sqrt, exp
from math import erf
def N(x): return 0.5*(1+erf(x/np.sqrt(2)))
for T in Ts:
    for K in Ks:
        # BS closed form
        d1 = (np.log(S0/K) + (r - q + 0.5*sigma_bs**2)*T)/(sigma_bs*np.sqrt(T))
        d2 = d1 - sigma_bs*np.sqrt(T)
        C_bs = S0*np.exp(-q*T)*N(d1) - K*np.exp(-r*T)*N(d2)
        Delta_bs = np.exp(-q*T)*N(d1)
        Gamma_bs = np.exp(-q*T)*np.exp(-0.5*d1*d1)/(S0*sigma_bs*np.sqrt(T)*np.sqrt(2*np.pi))
        Vega_bs = S0*np.exp(-q*T)*np.sqrt(T)*np.exp(-0.5*d1*d1)/np.sqrt(2*np.pi)

        # Heston->BS via limit params; Greeks w.r.t v0 (note: not same as BS vega)
        C_ref = cm_price_singleK(S0, K, T, r, q, **hpar, **hpar, rho=0.0, **dict(
            C_fft, D_fft, G_fft, V_fft = price_greeks_fft_atK(S0, K, T, r, q, **hpar,

        print(f"T={T:.2f},K={K:.1f} | BS C={C_bs:.6f}, Heston->BS C_FFT={C_fft:.6f}

```

2.1. Black-Scholes vs FFT verification and sanity check.

```

import numpy as np
from math import log, sqrt, exp, erf, pi

# -----
# Black{Scholes closed-form (with C/v0)
# -----
def _N(x):
    return 0.5 * (1.0 + erf(x / sqrt(2.0)))

def _phi(x):
    return (1.0 / sqrt(2.0 * pi)) * np.exp(-0.5 * x * x)

def bs_price_delta_gamma_vega_v0(S0, K, T, r, q, sigma_bs):
    """
    Return (Price, Delta, Gamma, Vega_v0) in Black{Scholes.
    Vega_v0 = C/v0 with v0 = sigma^2, so Vega_v0 = (C)/(2).
    """
    if T <= 0:
        payoff = max(S0 - K, 0.0)
        return payoff, float(S0 > K), 0.0, 0.0

    sig = sigma_bs
    d1 = (log(S0/K) + (r - q + 0.5*sig*sig)*T) / (sig * sqrt(T))
    d2 = d1 - sig*sqrt(T)

    disc_r = exp(-r*T)
    disc_q = exp(-q*T)

```

```

price = S0*disc_q*_N(d1) - K*disc_r*_N(d2)
delta = disc_q*_N(d1)
gamma = disc_q*_phi(d1) / (S0 * sig * sqrt(T))
vega_sigma = S0 * disc_q * sqrt(T) * _phi(d1) # C/
vega_v0 = vega_sigma / (2.0 * sig) # C/v0 with v0 = ^2
return float(price), float(delta), float(gamma), float(vega_v0)

# -----
# Heston CF (Lord{Kahl \little trap") | stable branch
# -----
def heston_charfunc_lord_kahl(u, T, v0, kappa, theta, sigma, rho, r, q, return_CD=False):
    """
    Stable Heston CF:
    phi(u) = exp(C(u,T) + D(u,T) * v0)
    Returns (phi[, C, D]).
    """
    iu = 1j * u
    a = kappa * theta
    b = kappa - rho * sigma * iu
    d = np.sqrt(b*b + (iu + u*u) * sigma * sigma)
    g = (b - d) / (b + d)
    e = np.exp(-d * T)
    C = (r - q) * iu * T + (a / (sigma*sigma)) * ((b - d) * T - 2.0 * np.log((1 - g*
    D = ((b - d) / (sigma*sigma)) * ((1 - e) / (1 - g*e))
    phi = np.exp(C + D * v0)
    if return_CD:
        return phi, C, D
    return phi

# -----
# Carr{Madan FFT: Prices & Greeks on a strike grid
# (trapezoidal weights; alpha-damped; analytic-integrand Greeks)
# -----
def cm_fft_grid_all(S0, T, r, q, v0, kappa, theta, sigma, rho,
                    alpha=1.5, N=2**12, eta=0.25, k0=None):
    """
    Return (k_grid, Price, Delta, Gamma, Vega_v0) arrays (length N).
    - Trapezoidal weights (compatible with power-of-two N)
    - Analytic-integrand Greeks:
      Delta: multiply by (i z / S0)
      Gamma: multiply by -(i z + z^2) / S0^2
      Vega_v0: multiply by D(z) (since phi = exp(C + D v0))
    - Strike spacing: dk = 2/(N*eta) with phase centering at k0
    """
    if T <= 0:
        raise ValueError("Use T>0 for transform-based pricing.")

    # Frequency grid
    m = np.arange(N, dtype=float)
    u = m * eta

```

```

beta = alpha + 1.0
z = u - 1j * beta

# Affine CF at shifted arg
phi, C, D = heston_charfunc_lord_kahl(z, T, v0, kappa, theta, sigma, rho, r, q, r)
S_term = np.exp(1j * z * np.log(S0)) #  $S_0^{i z}$ 

# Carr-Madan denominator
denom = (alpha**2 + alpha - u*u) + 1j*(2*alpha + 1)*u

# Common base
base = np.exp(-r*T) * (S_term * phi) / denom

# Frequency-domain inputs
F_price = base
F_delta = base * (1j * z / S0)
F_gamma = base * (-(1j * z + z*z) / (S0*S0))
F_vega = base * D

# Trapezoidal weights in frequency
w = np.ones(N); w[0] = 0.5; w[-1] = 0.5
w *= eta

# Strike grid mapping
dk = 2.0 * np.pi / (N * eta)
if k0 is None:
    # center the window around log(S0)
    k0 = np.log(S0) - 0.5 * N * dk
j = np.arange(N)
k = k0 + j * dk # log-strike grid

# Kernel: phase shift to k0 and 1/ factor
kern = np.exp(-1j * u * k0) * w / np.pi

# FFTs
P = np.fft.fft(F_price * kern)
Df = np.fft.fft(F_delta * kern)
Gf = np.fft.fft(F_gamma * kern)
Vf = np.fft.fft(F_vega * kern)

# Remove damping in strike domain
damp = np.exp(-alpha * k)
Price = np.real(damp * P)
Delta = np.real(damp * Df)
Gamma = np.real(damp * Gf)
Vega = np.real(damp * Vf)

return k, Price, Delta, Gamma, Vega

```

```

def price_greeks_fft_atK(S0, K, T, r, q, v0, kappa, theta, sigma, rho,

```

```

        alpha=1.5, N=2**12, eta=0.25, k0=None):
    """
    Interpolate FFT-based (Price, Delta, Gamma, Vega_v0) to a specific strike K.
    Raises if K is outside the FFT grid (avoid hidden extrapolation).
    """
    k_grid, P, D, G, V = cm_fft_grid_all(S0, T, r, q, v0, kappa, theta, sigma, rho,
                                         alpha=alpha, N=N, eta=eta, k0=k0)
    k = np.log(K)
    if not (k_grid[0] <= k <= k_grid[-1]):
        raise ValueError("K outside FFT k-grid; enlarge N or adjust eta/k0")
    idx = np.searchsorted(k_grid, k) - 1
    t = (k - k_grid[idx]) / (k_grid[idx+1] - k_grid[idx])
    price = (1-t)*P[idx] + t*P[idx+1]
    delta = (1-t)*D[idx] + t*D[idx+1]
    gamma = (1-t)*G[idx] + t*G[idx+1]
    vega = (1-t)*V[idx] + t*V[idx+1]
    return float(price), float(delta), float(gamma), float(vega)

# -----
# Near{Black{Scholes Heston params (numerically gentle)
# -----
def heston_params_bs_limit(sigma_bs):
    """
    Choose Heston params so variance is (almost) deterministic at  $BS^2$ :
    v0 = theta =  $BS^2$ , rho = 0, kappa moderately large, vol-of-vol very small.
    Extremely large kappa / tiny sigma cause stiffness; avoid that here.
    """
    return {
        "v0": sigma_bs**2,
        "theta": sigma_bs**2,
        "kappa": 100.0, # not 1e6
        "sigma": 1e-3, # not 1e-4
        "rho": 0.0
    }

# -----
# Driver: verify BS limit across a small grid
# -----
def verify_bs_limit_across_grid(
    S0=100.0, r=0.0, q=0.0,
    sigma_bs=0.20,
    Ks=(90.0, 100.0, 110.0),
    Ts=(0.25, 1.00),
    alpha_fft=1.5, N_fft=2**12, eta_fft=0.20, k0_fft=None,
    gates = dict(max_eP=5e-4, max_eD=1e-4, max_eG=5e-5, max_eV=5e-3)
):
    if k0_fft is None:
        # center window around log S0
        dk = 2.0*np.pi/(N_fft*eta_fft)
        k0_fft = np.log(S0) - 0.5 * N_fft * dk

```

```

hp = heston_params_bs_limit(sigma_bs)

print("=== Black{Scholes Limit Verification (BS closed-form vs Heston-FFT in BS-l
print("Note: Vega reported is C/v0; BS vega is converted via C/v0 = (C/)/(2).")
print(f"sigma_BS={sigma_bs:.4f}, v0=theta={sigma_bs**2:.6f}, "
      f"kappa={hp['kappa']:.1f}, sigma(vol-of-vol)={hp['sigma']:.1e}, rho={hp['rho']:.1e}")
print()
print("T      K      Price_BS      Price_FFT      |e_P|      Delta_BS      Delta_FFT      |e_D|
      "Gamma_BS      Gamma_FFT      |e_G|      Vega_v0_BS      Vega_v0_FFT      |e_V|")
print("-"*168)

max_eP = max_eD = max_eG = max_eV = 0.0

for T in Ts:
    for K in Ks:
        # BS closed form
        P_bs, D_bs, G_bs, Vv0_bs = bs_price_delta_gamma_vega_v0(S0, K, T, r, q, s)
        # Heston-FFT in BS-limit
        P_fft, D_fft, G_fft, Vv0_fft = price_greeks_fft_atK(
            S0, K, T, r, q,
            hp["v0"], hp["kappa"], hp["theta"], hp["sigma"], hp["rho"],
            alpha=alpha_fft, N=N_fft, eta=eta_fft, k0=k0_fft
        )
        # Errors
        eP = abs(P_fft - P_bs); max_eP = max(max_eP, eP)
        eD = abs(D_fft - D_bs); max_eD = max(max_eD, eD)
        eG = abs(G_fft - G_bs); max_eG = max(max_eG, eG)
        eV = abs(Vv0_fft - Vv0_bs); max_eV = max(max_eV, eV)

        print(f"{T:0.2f} {K:6.1f} {P_bs:11.6f} {P_fft:11.6f} {eP:9.2e} "
              f"{D_bs:10.6f} {D_fft:10.6f} {eD:9.2e} "
              f"{G_bs:10.6e} {G_fft:10.6e} {eG:9.2e} "
              f"{Vv0_bs:11.6f} {Vv0_fft:11.6f} {eV:9.2e}")

print("\nSuggested acceptance gates (near-BS limit): "
      f"max|e_P|<{gates['max_eP']:.1e}, max|e_D|<{gates['max_eD']:.1e}, "
      f"max|e_G|<{gates['max_eG']:.1e}, max|e_V|<{gates['max_eV']:.1e}")
print(f"Observed maxima: max|e_P|={max_eP:.2e}, max|e_D|={max_eD:.2e}, "
      f"max|e_G|={max_eG:.2e}, max|e_V|={max_eV:.2e}")

# -----
# Run the check
# -----
if __name__ == "__main__":
    verify_bs_limit_across_grid(
        S0=100.0, r=0.0, q=0.0,
        sigma_bs=0.20,
        Ks=(90.0, 100.0, 110.0),
        Ts=(0.25, 1.00),

```

```

        alpha_fft=1.5,
        N_fft=2**13,           # a bit finer than 2**12 for tighter match
        eta_fft=0.20,         # slightly smaller eta to push aliasing further out
        k0_fft=None           # auto-center around log S0
    )

```

2.2. Visualizations.

```

# =====
# 2x3 matrix figures per Greek + 2x2 slices
# =====
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import os

S0    = 100.0
r, q  = 0.0, 0.0
kappa = 2.0
theta = 0.04
sigma = 0.6
rho   = -0.7
v0    = 0.05

# Reference (ground-truth) quadrature
alpha_ref = 1.5
N_ref     = 2**15
u_max_ref = 250.0

# FFT baseline
alpha_fft = 1.5
N_fft     = 2**12
eta_fft   = 0.25
k0_fft    = np.log(S0) - 3.0

# Grids
Ks = np.linspace(80, 120, 9)
Ts = np.array([0.25, 0.5, 1.0])

# ATM point for convergence/sensitivity
K_ATM, T_ATM = 100.0, 0.25

# ----- Helpers -----
def _error_metrics(ref, approx, eps=1e-12):
    abs_err = np.abs(approx - ref)
    rel_err = abs_err / (np.abs(ref) + eps)
    return abs_err, rel_err

def _compute_grid(S0, r, q, v0, kappa, theta, sigma, rho,
                  Ks, Ts, alpha_ref, N_ref, u_max_ref,

```

```

        alpha_fft, N_fft, eta_fft, k0_fft):
rows = []
for T in Ts:
    for K in Ks:
        C_ref = cm_price_singleK(S0, K, T, r, q, v0, kappa, theta, sigma, rho,
                                alpha=alpha_ref, N=N_ref, u_max=u_max_ref)
        D_ref, G_ref, V_ref = cm_greeks_singleK(S0, K, T, r, q, v0, kappa, theta,
                                                alpha=alpha_ref, N=N_ref, u_max=u_max_ref)
        C_fft, D_fft, G_fft, V_fft = price_greeks_fft_atK(S0, K, T, r, q, v0, kappa, theta,
                                                           alpha=alpha_fft, N=N_fft)

        rows.append(dict(T=T, K=K,
                        P_ref=C_ref, P_fft=C_fft,
                        D_ref=D_ref, D_fft=D_fft,
                        G_ref=G_ref, G_fft=G_fft,
                        V_ref=V_ref, V_fft=V_fft))
return pd.DataFrame(rows).sort_values(["T", "K"]).reset_index(drop=True)

def _gridify(df, col, Ks, Ts):
M = np.zeros((len(Ts), len(Ks)))
for i, T in enumerate(Ts):
    M[i,:] = df[df["T"]==T].sort_values("K")[col].to_numpy()
return M

# Map names
_LABELS = {
    "price": ("P_ref", "P_fft", "Price"),
    "delta": ("D_ref", "D_fft", "Delta"),
    "gamma": ("G_ref", "G_fft", "Gamma"),
    "vega" : ("V_ref", "V_fft", "Vega"),
}

# ----- Core: build 2x3 matrix & 2x2 slices -----
def greek_matrix_and_slices(metric: str,
                            outdir="figs_matrix",
                            Ns=(2**11, 2**12, 2**13, 2**14),
                            etas=(0.20, 0.25, 0.30),
                            k0_shifts=(-4.0, -3.5, -3.0, -2.5, -2.0),
                            alphas=(1.0, 1.25, 1.5, 1.75, 2.0),
                            K_slices=(90.0, 100.0, 110.0),
                            T_slices=(0.25, 0.5, 1.0)):
    """
    metric in {'price', 'delta', 'gamma', 'vega'}.
    Produces:
    - 2x3 matrix figure: heatmap | errors vs N | errors vs eta
                        errors vs k0 | errors vs alpha | histogram(rel)
    - 2x2 slices figure: values vs K + abs error vs K; values vs T + abs error vs T
    Saves PNGs and returns their paths.
    """
    os.makedirs(outdir, exist_ok=True)
    ref_col, fft_col, pretty = _LABELS[metric]

```

```

# Build grid (ref & fft)
df = _compute_grid(S0, r, q, v0, kappa, theta, sigma, rho,
                  Ks, Ts, alpha_ref, N_ref, u_max_ref,
                  alpha_fft, N_fft, eta_fft, k0_fft)
df["e_abs_"+metric] = np.abs(df[fft_col] - df[ref_col])
df["e_rel_"+metric] = df["e_abs_"+metric] / (np.abs(df[ref_col]) + 1e-12)

# ----- (1) 2x3 MATRIX -----
fig, axes = plt.subplots(2, 3, figsize=(11.0, 7.0))

# A. Heatmap of abs error
M = _gridify(df, "e_abs_"+metric, Ks, Ts)
ax = axes[0,0]
im = ax.imshow(M, aspect='auto', origin='lower',
               extent=(Ks[0], Ks[-1], Ts[0], Ts[-1]))
fig.colorbar(im, ax=ax)
ax.set_title(f"{pretty} abs error")
ax.set_xlabel("Strike K"); ax.set_ylabel("T")

# Gather ATM refs once
Pref = cm_price_singleK(S0, K_ATM, T_ATM, r, q, v0, kappa, theta, sigma, rho,
                       alpha=alpha_ref, N=N_ref, u_max=u_max_ref)
Dref, Gref, Vref = cm_greeks_singleK(S0, K_ATM, T_ATM, r, q, v0, kappa, theta, sigma, rho,
                                     alpha=alpha_ref, N=N_ref, u_max=u_max_ref)
REF = {"price": Pref, "delta": Dref, "gamma": Gref, "vega": Vref}[metric]

# B. Errors vs N (log{log}) at ATM
eN = []
for N in Ns:
    C, D, G, V = price_greeks_fft_atK(S0, K_ATM, T_ATM, r, q, v0, kappa, theta, sigma, rho,
                                       alpha=alpha_fft, N=N, eta=eta_fft, k0=k0_fft)
    FFT = {"price": C, "delta": D, "gamma": G, "vega": V}[metric]
    eN.append(abs(FFT - REF))
ax = axes[0,1]
ax.loglog(Ns, eN, marker='o')
ax.set_title(f"{pretty}: error vs N (ATM)")
ax.set_xlabel("N"); ax.set_ylabel("abs error")

# C. Errors vs eta at ATM
eEta = []
for et in etas:
    C, D, G, V = price_greeks_fft_atK(S0, K_ATM, T_ATM, r, q, v0, kappa, theta, sigma, rho,
                                       alpha=alpha_fft, N=N_fft, eta=et, k0=k0_fft)
    FFT = {"price": C, "delta": D, "gamma": G, "vega": V}[metric]
    eEta.append(abs(FFT - REF))
ax = axes[0,2]
ax.plot(etas, eEta, marker='o')
ax.set_title(f"{pretty}: error vs eta (ATM)")
ax.set_xlabel(""); ax.set_ylabel("abs error")

```

```

# D. Sensitivity vs k0 at ATM
eK0 = []
for shift in k0_shifts:
    k0h = np.log(S0) + shift
    C, D, G, V = price_greeks_fft_atK(S0, K_ATM, T_ATM, r, q, v0, kappa, theta, s
                                     alpha=alpha_fft, N=N_fft, eta=eta_fft, k0=k
    FFT = {"price": C, "delta": D, "gamma": G, "vega": V}[metric]
    eK0.append(abs(FFT - REF))
ax = axes[1,0]
ax.plot(k0_shifts, eK0, marker='o')
ax.set_title(f"{pretty}: sensitivity to $k_0$ (ATM)")
ax.set_xlabel("k0 shift"); ax.set_ylabel("abs error")

# E. Sensitivity vs alpha at ATM
eA = []
for a in alphas:
    C, D, G, V = price_greeks_fft_atK(S0, K_ATM, T_ATM, r, q, v0, kappa, theta, s
                                     alpha=a, N=N_fft, eta=eta_fft, k0=k0_fft)
    FFT = {"price": C, "delta": D, "gamma": G, "vega": V}[metric]
    eA.append(abs(FFT - REF))
ax = axes[1,1]
ax.plot(alphas, eA, marker='o')
ax.set_title(f"{pretty}: sensitivity to  $\alpha$  (ATM)")
ax.set_xlabel(""); ax.set_ylabel("abs error")

# F. Histogram of relative errors over (K,T)
ax = axes[1,2]
ax.hist(df["e_rel_"+metric].to_numpy(), bins=20)
ax.set_title(f"{pretty}: relative error over $(K,T)$")
ax.set_xlabel("relative error"); ax.set_ylabel("count")

fig.tight_layout()
matrix_path = os.path.join(outdir, f"{metric}_matrix_2x3.png")
fig.savefig(matrix_path, dpi=300)
plt.close(fig)

# ----- (2) 2x2 SLICES -----
fig2, axes2 = plt.subplots(2, 2, figsize=(10.0, 7.0))

# Values vs K at fixed T (show ref & FFT distinctly)
Tfix = T_slices[0]
subK = df[df["T"]==Tfix].sort_values("K")
ax = axes2[0,0]
# Distinct linestyles/markers to ensure both are visible even if overlaid
ax.plot(subK["K"], subK[ref_col], marker='o', linestyle='-', label=f"{pretty} ref")
ax.plot(subK["K"], subK[fft_col], marker='x', linestyle='--', label=f"{pretty} FFT")
ax.set_title(f"{pretty} vs K at T={Tfix}")
ax.set_xlabel("K"); ax.set_ylabel(pretty); ax.legend()

```

```

# Error vs K at same T
ax = axes2[0,1]
ax.plot(subK["K"], np.abs(subK[fft_col]-subK[ref_col]), marker='o')
ax.set_title(f"{pretty} abs error vs K (T={Tfix})")
ax.set_xlabel("K"); ax.set_ylabel("abs error")

# Values vs T at fixed K (show ref & FFT distinctly)
Kfix = K_slices[1]
subT = df[df["K"]==Kfix].sort_values("T")
ax = axes2[1,0]
ax.plot(subT["T"], subT[ref_col], marker='o', linestyle='--', label=f"{pretty} ref")
ax.plot(subT["T"], subT[fft_col], marker='x', linestyle='--', label=f"{pretty} FFT")
ax.set_title(f"{pretty} vs T at K={Kfix}")
ax.set_xlabel("T"); ax.set_ylabel(pretty); ax.legend()

# Error vs T at same K
ax = axes2[1,1]
ax.plot(subT["T"], np.abs(subT[fft_col]-subT[ref_col]), marker='o')
ax.set_title(f"{pretty} abs error vs T (K={Kfix})")
ax.set_xlabel("T"); ax.set_ylabel("abs error")

fig2.tight_layout()
slices_path = os.path.join(outdir, f"{metric}_slices_2x2.png")
fig2.savefig(slices_path, dpi=300)
plt.close(fig2)

return matrix_path, slices_path

# ----- Generate for Delta/Gamma/Vega -----
delta_paths = greek_matrix_and_slices("delta", outdir="figs_matrix")
gamma_paths = greek_matrix_and_slices("gamma", outdir="figs_matrix")
vega_paths = greek_matrix_and_slices("vega", outdir="figs_matrix")

print("Saved Delta figures/snippet:", delta_paths)
print("Saved Gamma figures/snippet:", gamma_paths)
print("Saved Vega figures/snippet:", vega_paths)

```

2.3. Benchmarking of Price and Greeks - Quadrature based versus FFT.

```

import numpy as np
from math import log, sqrt, exp, erf, pi

# ----- Normal helpers + BS closed-form (optional external check) -----
def _N(x): # CDF
    return 0.5 * (1.0 + erf(x / sqrt(2.0)))

def _phi(x): # PDF
    return (1.0 / sqrt(2.0 * pi)) * np.exp(-0.5 * x * x)

```

```

def bs_price_delta_gamma_vega_v0(S0, K, T, r, q, sigma_bs):
    if T <= 0:
        payoff = max(S0 - K, 0.0)
        return payoff, float(S0 > K), 0.0, 0.0
    sig = sigma_bs
    d1 = (log(S0/K) + (r - q + 0.5*sig*sig)*T) / (sig * sqrt(T))
    d2 = d1 - sig*sqrt(T)
    disc_r = exp(-r*T); disc_q = exp(-q*T)
    price = S0*disc_q*_N(d1) - K*disc_r*_N(d2)
    delta = disc_q*_N(d1)
    gamma = disc_q*_phi(d1) / (S0 * sig * sqrt(T))
    vega_sigma = S0 * disc_q * sqrt(T) * _phi(d1) # C/
    vega_v0 = vega_sigma / (2.0 * sig) # C/v0 with v0 = ^2
    return float(price), float(delta), float(gamma), float(vega_v0)

# ----- Heston CF (Lord{Kahl \little trap}) -----
def heston_charfunc_lord_kahl(u, T, v0, kappa, theta, sigma, rho, r, q, return_CD=False):
    iu = 1j * u
    a = kappa * theta
    b = kappa - rho * sigma * iu
    d = np.sqrt(b*b + (iu + u*u) * sigma * sigma)
    g = (b - d) / (b + d)
    e = np.exp(-d * T)
    C = (r - q) * iu * T + (a / (sigma*sigma)) * ((b - d) * T - 2.0 * np.log((1 - g)*
    D = ((b - d) / (sigma*sigma)) * ((1 - e) / (1 - g*e))
    phi = np.exp(C + D * v0)
    if return_CD:
        return phi, C, D
    return phi

# ----- Carr{Madan FFT to strike grid (TRAPEZOIDAL weights) -----
def cm_fft_grid_all(S0, T, r, q, v0, kappa, theta, sigma, rho,
                    alpha=1.5, N=2**12, eta=0.25, k0=None):
    if T <= 0:
        raise ValueError("Use T>0 for transform-based pricing.")

    m = np.arange(N, dtype=float)
    u = m * eta
    beta = alpha + 1.0
    z = u - 1j * beta

    # CF at shifted argument and spot factor
    phi, C, D = heston_charfunc_lord_kahl(z, T, v0, kappa, theta, sigma, rho, r, q, r
    S_term = np.exp(1j * z * np.log(S0))

    # Denominator and base
    denom = (alpha**2 + alpha - u*u) + 1j*(2*alpha + 1)*u
    base = np.exp(-r*T) * (S_term * phi) / denom

```

```

# Frequency-space inputs (analytic-integrand Greeks)
F_price = base
F_delta = base * (1j * z / S0)
F_gamma = base * (-(1j * z + z*z) / (S0*S0))
F_vega = base * D

# TRAPEZOIDAL weights (compatible with N=2^m)
w = np.ones(N)
if N >= 3:
    w[1:-1:2] = 4.0
    w[2:-1:2] = 2.0
w *= (eta/3.0)

# Strike grid mapping and centering
dk = 2.0 * np.pi / (N * eta)
if k0 is None:
    k0 = np.log(S0) - 0.5 * N * dk
j = np.arange(N)
k = k0 + j * dk # log-strike grid

# Kernel (phase to k0) and 1/ factor
kern = np.exp(-1j * u * k0) * w / np.pi

# FFTs
P = np.fft.fft(F_price * kern)
Df = np.fft.fft(F_delta * kern)
Gf = np.fft.fft(F_gamma * kern)
Vf = np.fft.fft(F_vega * kern)

# Remove damping in strike domain
damp = np.exp(-alpha * k)
Price = np.real(damp * P)
Delta = np.real(damp * Df)
Gamma = np.real(damp * Gf)
Vega = np.real(damp * Vf)

return k, Price, Delta, Gamma, Vega

def price_greeks_fft_atK(S0, K, T, r, q, v0, kappa, theta, sigma, rho,
                        alpha=1.5, N=2**12, eta=0.25, k0=None):
    k_grid, P, D, G, V = cm_fft_grid_all(S0, T, r, q, v0, kappa, theta, sigma, rho,
                                         alpha=alpha, N=N, eta=eta, k0=k0)
    k = np.log(K)
    if not (k_grid[0] <= k <= k_grid[-1]):
        raise ValueError("K outside FFT k-grid; enlarge N or adjust eta/k0")
    idx = np.searchsorted(k_grid, k) - 1
    t = (k - k_grid[idx]) / (k_grid[idx+1] - k_grid[idx])
    price = (1-t)*P[idx] + t*P[idx+1]
    delta = (1-t)*D[idx] + t*D[idx+1]
    gamma = (1-t)*G[idx] + t*G[idx+1]

```

```

vega = (1-t)*V[idx] + t*V[idx+1]
return float(price), float(delta), float(gamma), float(vega)

# ----- Single-strike REFERENCE quadrature (Simpson, correct parity) -----
def price_delta_gamma_vega_quadrature_atK(S0, K, T, r, q, v0, kappa, theta, sigma, rho,
                                           alpha=1.5, umax=200.0, Nq=2**15):
    """
    Use composite Simpson on [0,umax]. Requires Nq odd (Nq-1 even subintervals).
    If Nq is even, we fall back to trapezoid for robustness.
    """
    u = np.linspace(0.0, umax+1e-12, Nq)
    du = u[1] - u[0]
    beta = alpha + 1.0
    z = u - 1j * beta
    k = np.log(K)

    phi, C, D = heston_charfunc_lord_kahl(z, T, v0, kappa, theta, sigma, rho, r, q, r)
    S_term = np.exp(1j * z * np.log(S0))
    denom = (alpha**2 + alpha - u*u) + 1j*(2*alpha + 1)*u
    base = np.exp(-r*T) * (S_term * phi) / denom
    phase = np.exp(-1j * u * k)

    Gp = base * phase
    Gd = base * (1j * z / S0) * phase
    Gg = base * (-(1j * z + z*z) / (S0*S0)) * phase
    Gv = base * D * phase

    if (Nq - 1) % 2 == 0:
        # Simpson
        w = np.ones(Nq); w[1:-1:2] = 4.0; w[2:-1:2] = 2.0
        W = (du / 3.0) * w
    else:
        # Trapezoid fallback
        w = np.ones(Nq); w[0] = 0.5; w[-1] = 0.5
        W = du * w

    pref = np.exp(-alpha * k) / np.pi
    P = np.real(pref * np.sum(Gp * W))
    Dlt = np.real(pref * np.sum(Gd * W))
    Gmm = np.real(pref * np.sum(Gg * W))
    Vv0 = np.real(pref * np.sum(Gv * W))
    return float(P), float(Dlt), float(Gmm), float(Vv0)

# ----- Near{Black{Scholes Heston parameters (numerically gentle) -----
def heston_params_bs_limit(sigma_bs):
    return {"v0": sigma_bs**2, "theta": sigma_bs**2, "kappa": 100.0, "sigma": 1e-3, "rho": 0.0}

# ----- Pretty printers -----
def table_delta(S0, r, q, sigma_bs, Ks, Ts, alpha_q, umax, Nq, alpha_fft, N_fft, eta_0):
    hp = heston_params_bs_limit(sigma_bs)

```

```

print("Table: Delta comparison (Reference vs FFT) in near{BS Heston}")
print(f"Ref: Nq={Nq}, umax={umax}, alpha={alpha_q}. FFT: N={N_fft}, eta={eta_fft}")
print()
print(" T      K      Price_ref      Price_FFT      |e_P|      Delta_ref      Delta_F")
print("-"*100)
for T in Ts:
    for K in Ks:
        Pref, Dref, _, _ = price_delta_gamma_vega_quadrature_atK(
            S0, K, T, r, q, **hp, alpha=alpha_q, umax=umax, Nq=Nq
        )
        Pfft, Dfft, _, _ = price_greeks_fft_atK(
            S0, K, T, r, q, **hp, alpha=alpha_fft, N=N_fft, eta=eta_fft, k0=k0_fft
        )
        print(f"{T:0.2f} {K:6.1f} {Pref:11.6f} {Pfft:11.6f} {abs(Pfft-Pref):9.2e}
              f"{Dref:12.6f} {Dfft:12.6f} {abs(Dfft-Dref):9.2e}")

def table_gamma(S0, r, q, sigma_bs, Ks, Ts, alpha_q, umax, Nq, alpha_fft, N_fft, eta_fft):
    hp = heston_params_bs_limit(sigma_bs)
    print("\nTable: Gamma comparison (Reference vs FFT) in near{BS Heston}")
    print(f"Ref: Nq={Nq}, umax={umax}, alpha={alpha_q}. FFT: N={N_fft}, eta={eta_fft}")
    print()
    print(" T      K      Price_ref      Price_FFT      |e_P|      Gamma_ref      Gamma_F")
    print("-"*100)
    for T in Ts:
        for K in Ks:
            Pref, _, Gref, _ = price_delta_gamma_vega_quadrature_atK(
                S0, K, T, r, q, **hp, alpha=alpha_q, umax=umax, Nq=Nq
            )
            Pfft, _, Gfft, _ = price_greeks_fft_atK(
                S0, K, T, r, q, **hp, alpha=alpha_fft, N=N_fft, eta=eta_fft, k0=k0_fft
            )
            print(f"{T:0.2f} {K:6.1f} {Pref:11.6f} {Pfft:11.6f} {abs(Pfft-Pref):9.2e}
                  f"{Gref:12.6e} {Gfft:12.6e} {abs(Gfft-Gref):9.2e}")

def table_vega(S0, r, q, sigma_bs, Ks, Ts, alpha_q, umax, Nq, alpha_fft, N_fft, eta_fft):
    hp = heston_params_bs_limit(sigma_bs)
    print("\nTable: Vega_{v0} comparison (Reference vs FFT) in near{BS Heston}")
    print(f"Ref: Nq={Nq}, umax={umax}, alpha={alpha_q}. FFT: N={N_fft}, eta={eta_fft}")
    print("Vega is w.r.t. v0 (initial variance).")
    print()
    print(" T      K      Price_ref      Price_FFT      |e_P|      Vega_v0_ref      Vega_v0_F")
    print("-"*100)
    for T in Ts:
        for K in Ks:
            Pref, _, _, Vref = price_delta_gamma_vega_quadrature_atK(
                S0, K, T, r, q, **hp, alpha=alpha_q, umax=umax, Nq=Nq
            )
            Pfft, _, _, Vfft = price_greeks_fft_atK(
                S0, K, T, r, q, **hp, alpha=alpha_fft, N=N_fft, eta=eta_fft, k0=k0_fft
            )

```

```

        print(f"{T:0.2f} {K:6.1f} {Pref:11.6f} {Pfft:11.6f} {abs(Pfft-Pref):9.2e}
              f"{Vref:12.6f} {Vfft:12.6f} {abs(Vfft-Vref):9.2e}")

# ----- Driver -----
if __name__ == "__main__":
    S0=100.0; r=0.0; q=0.0; sigma_bs=0.20
    Ks=(90.0, 100.0, 110.0)
    Ts=(0.25, 1.00)

    # Reference quadrature (choose Nq odd for Simpson)
    alpha_q=1.5; umax=250.0; Nq=2**15

    # FFT settings (centered window; slightly finer than 2**12)
    alpha_fft=1.5; N_fft=2**13; eta_fft=0.20
    dk = 2.0*np.pi/(N_fft*eta_fft)
    k0_fft = np.log(S0) - 0.5 * N_fft * dk

    table_delta(S0,r,q,sigma_bs,Ks,Ts,alpha_q,umax,Nq,alpha_fft,N_fft,eta_fft,k0_fft)
    table_gamma(S0,r,q,sigma_bs,Ks,Ts,alpha_q,umax,Nq,alpha_fft,N_fft,eta_fft,k0_fft)
    table_vega (S0,r,q,sigma_bs,Ks,Ts,alpha_q,umax,Nq,alpha_fft,N_fft,eta_fft,k0_fft)

```

2.4. Empirical Data - Chapter 6.

```

# =====
# Real Deribit options → Heston FFT prices & Greeks (USD)
# Robust no-arbitrage checks PER EXPIRY (incl. convexity).
# - Carr{Madan FFT (Simpson weights) + Lord{Kahl "little trap"
# - Prefer USDC-linear options; fallback to inverse (BTC-settled)
# - ATM BS IV → near-Black{Scholes Heston anchor (not a calibration)
# - Shape tests both at market strikes and on native FFT k-grid
# =====
# pip install requests pandas numpy matplotlib

import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
import requests, time
from math import log, sqrt, exp, erf, pi
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from datetime import datetime, timezone

# ----- Normal helpers -----
def _N(x): # standard normal CDF
    return 0.5 * (1.0 + erf(x / sqrt(2.0)))

def _phi(x): # standard normal PDF
    return (1.0 / sqrt(2.0 * pi)) * np.exp(-0.5 * x * x)

# ----- Black{Scholes (USD) -----
def bs_price_delta_gamma_vega_v0(S0, K, T, r, q, sigma):
    if T <= 0:
        payoff = max(S0 - K, 0.0)

```

```

    return payoff, float(S0 > K), 0.0, 0.0
sig = max(1e-12, sigma)
d1 = (log(S0/K) + (r - q + 0.5*sig*sig)*T) / (sig * sqrt(T))
d2 = d1 - sig*sqrt(T)
disc_r = exp(-r*T); disc_q = exp(-q*T)
price = S0*disc_q*_N(d1) - K*disc_r*_N(d2)
delta = disc_q*_N(d1)
gamma = disc_q*_phi(d1) / (S0 * sig * sqrt(T))
vega_sigma = S0 * disc_q * sqrt(T) * _phi(d1)      # C/
vega_v0     = vega_sigma / (2.0 * sig)              # C/v0 with v0= $\sigma^2$ 
return float(price), float(delta), float(gamma), float(vega_v0)

def bs_implied_vol_call(price, S0, K, T, r, q, lo=1e-6, hi=5.0, tol=1e-8, maxit=100):
# Robust bisection IV solver (bounds enforce arbitrage-consistent prices)
if T <= 0 or S0 <= 0 or K <= 0:
    return 0.2
disc_r = exp(-r*T); disc_q = exp(-q*T)
lb = max(S0*disc_q - K*disc_r, 0.0); ub = S0*disc_q
p = min(max(price, lb), ub)
f_lo = bs_price_delta_gamma_vega_v0(S0, K, T, r, q, lo)[0] - p
f_hi = bs_price_delta_gamma_vega_v0(S0, K, T, r, q, hi)[0] - p
if f_lo*f_hi > 0:
    return 0.2
a, b = lo, hi
for _ in range(maxit):
    c = 0.5*(a+b)
    fc = bs_price_delta_gamma_vega_v0(S0, K, T, r, q, c)[0] - p
    if abs(fc) < tol or (b-a) < tol:
        return float(max(c, 1e-6))
    if f_lo*fc <= 0:
        b, f_hi = c, fc
    else:
        a, f_lo = c, fc
return float(max(0.5*(a+b), 1e-6))

# ----- Heston CF (Lord{Kahl \little trap}) -----
# Ref: Lord & Kahl (2010), Mathematical Finance
def heston_charfunc_lord_kahl(u, T, v0, kappa, theta, sigma, rho, r, q, return_CD=False):
    iu = 1j * u
    a = kappa * theta
    b = kappa - rho * sigma * iu
    d = np.sqrt(b*b + (iu + u*u) * sigma * sigma)
    g = (b - d) / (b + d)
    e = np.exp(-d * T)
    C = (r - q) * iu * T + (a / (sigma*sigma)) * ((b - d) * T - 2.0 * np.log((1 - g*
    D = ((b - d) / (sigma*sigma)) * ((1 - e) / (1 - g*e))
    phi = np.exp(C + D * v0)
    if return_CD: return phi, C, D
    return phi

```

```

# ----- Carr{Madan FFT (Simpson weights) -----
# Ref: Carr & Madan (1999), J. Computational Finance
def cm_fft_grid_all(S0, T, r, q, v0, kappa, theta, sigma, rho,
                    alpha=2.0, N=2**16, eta=0.08, k0=None):
    if T <= 0:
        raise ValueError("Use T>0 for transform-based pricing.")
    m = np.arange(N, dtype=float)
    u = m * eta
    z = u - 1j * (alpha + 1.0)

    phi, C, D = heston_charfunc_lord_kahl(z, T, v0, kappa, theta, sigma, rho, r, q, r)
    denom = (alpha**2 + alpha - u*u) + 1j*(2*alpha + 1)*u
    base = np.exp(-r*T) * (np.exp(1j * z * np.log(S0)) * phi) / denom

    Fp = base
    Fd = base * (1j * z / S0)
    Fg = base * (-(1j * z + z*z) / (S0*S0))
    Fv = base * D

    # Simpson weights (significantly reduces ringing vs trapezoid)
    w = np.ones(N)
    if N >= 3:
        w[1:-1:2] = 4.0
        w[2:-1:2] = 2.0
    w *= (eta/3.0)

    # Strike grid: exact centering at log S0
    dk = 2.0*np.pi/(N*eta)
    if k0 is None:
        k0 = np.log(S0) - 0.5*N*dk
    k = k0 + np.arange(N) * dk
    kern = np.exp(-1j * u * k0) * w / np.pi

    P = np.fft.fft(Fp * kern)
    Df = np.fft.fft(Fd * kern)
    Gf = np.fft.fft(Fg * kern)
    Vf = np.fft.fft(Fv * kern)

    damp = np.exp(-alpha * k)
    return k, np.real(damp*P), np.real(damp*Df), np.real(damp*Gf), np.real(damp*Vf)

def price_greeks_fft_atK(S0, K, T, r, q, v0, kappa, theta, sigma, rho,
                          alpha=2.0, N=2**16, eta=0.08, k0=None):
    k_grid, P, D, G, V = cm_fft_grid_all(S0, T, r, q, v0, kappa, theta, sigma, rho,
                                          alpha=alpha, N=N, eta=eta, k0=k0)
    k = np.log(K)
    if k <= k_grid[0]:
        return float(P[0]), float(D[0]), float(G[0]), float(V[0])
    if k >= k_grid[-1]:
        return float(P[-1]), float(D[-1]), float(G[-1]), float(V[-1])

```

```

idx = np.searchsorted(k_grid, k) - 1
t = (k - k_grid[idx]) / (k_grid[idx+1] - k_grid[idx])
price = (1-t)*P[idx] + t*P[idx+1]
delta = (1-t)*D[idx] + t*D[idx+1]
gamma = (1-t)*G[idx] + t*G[idx+1]
vega = (1-t)*V[idx] + t*V[idx+1]
return float(price), float(delta), float(gamma), float(vega)

# ----- Near-Black{Scholes anchor (not a calibration) -----
def heston_params_near_bs(sigma_atm):
    return {
        "v0": float(sigma_atm**2),
        "theta": float(sigma_atm**2),
        "kappa": 100.0, # avoids stiffness; still near-BS
        "sigma": 1e-3, # small vol-of-vol
        "rho": 0.0
    }

# ----- Deribit helpers -----
DERIBIT = "https://www.deribit.com/api/v2"

def get_json(endpoint, params):
    r = requests.get(DERIBIT + endpoint, params=params, timeout=10)
    r.raise_for_status()
    j = r.json()
    if "result" not in j:
        raise RuntimeError(f"Unexpected response for {endpoint}: {j}")
    return j["result"]

def list_linear_btc_options():
    ins = get_json("/public/get_instruments", {
        "currency": "USDC", "kind": "option", "expired": "false"
    })
    return [it for it in ins
            if it.get("base_currency") == "BTC"
            and (it.get("settlement_currency") == "USDC" or it.get("counter_currency")

def list_inverse_btc_options():
    ins = get_json("/public/get_instruments", {
        "currency": "BTC", "kind": "option", "expired": "false"
    })
    return [it for it in ins
            if it.get("base_currency") == "BTC"
            and it.get("settlement_currency") in ("BTC", None)]

def get_mid_from_ticker(name):
    tk = get_json("/public/ticker", {"instrument_name": name})
    b = tk.get("best_bid_price") or tk.get("bid_price")
    a = tk.get("best_ask_price") or tk.get("ask_price")
    mid = None

```

```

    if b and a and a > b:
        mid = 0.5 * (b + a)
    elif tk.get("mark_price"):
        mid = float(tk["mark_price"])
    return mid, b, a

# ----- Build slices (USDC-first, inverse fallback), collect M expiries -----
def build_slice_linear(instruments, now_ms, min_pts=8):
    expiries = sorted({it["expiration_timestamp"] for it in instruments if it["expira
    buckets = []
    for exp_ts in expiries:
        calls = [it for it in instruments
                  if it["expiration_timestamp"] == exp_ts and it["option_type"] == "ca
        rows = []
        for it in calls:
            name = it["instrument_name"]
            mid_usd, b, a = get_mid_from_ticker(name) # linear → already USD
            if mid_usd is None or mid_usd <= 0: continue
            K = float(it["strike"])
            T = max(0.0, (exp_ts - now_ms) / (365.0*24*3600*1000.0))
            rows.append({"expiry": exp_ts, "instrument": name, "K": K, "T": T,
                        "mid_btc": np.nan, "mid_usd": float(mid_usd)})
        if len(rows) >= min_pts:
            buckets.append(rows)
    return buckets

def build_slice_inverse(instruments, now_ms, S0, min_pts=10):
    expiries = sorted({it["expiration_timestamp"] for it in instruments if it["expira
    buckets = []
    for exp_ts in expiries:
        calls = [it for it in instruments
                  if it["expiration_timestamp"] == exp_ts and it["option_type"] == "ca
        rows = []
        for it in calls:
            name = it["instrument_name"]
            mid_btc, b, a = get_mid_from_ticker(name)
            if mid_btc is None or mid_btc <= 0: continue
            K = float(it["strike"])
            T = max(0.0, (exp_ts - now_ms) / (365.0*24*3600*1000.0))
            mid_usd = float(mid_btc) * S0
            rows.append({"expiry": exp_ts, "instrument": name, "K": K, "T": T,
                        "mid_btc": float(mid_btc), "mid_usd": mid_usd})
        if len(rows) >= min_pts:
            buckets.append(rows)
    return buckets

# ----- Shape checks (per expiry) -----
def shape_checks_per_expiry(df_out, rel_tol=1e-3, abs_tol=2e-4):
    """Return summary row per expiry using robust, scale-aware tolerances."""
    res = []

```

```

for exp_ts, grp in df_out.groupby("expiry"):
    g = grp.sort_values("K").reset_index(drop=True).copy()
    price = g["P_fft_usd"].to_numpy()

    # Monotonicity at market strikes
    mono_raw = np.diff(price)
    mono_thr = np.maximum(abs_tol, rel_tol*np.maximum(price[:-1], price[1:]))
    mono_viol = np.maximum(0.0, mono_raw - mono_thr)

    # Convexity at market strikes (discrete second diff)
    if len(price) >= 3:
        sec = price[:-2] - 2.0*price[1:-1] + price[2:]
        local = np.maximum.reduce([price[:-2], price[1:-1], price[2:]])
        thr = np.maximum(abs_tol, rel_tol*local)
        conv_viol = np.maximum(0.0, -(sec) - thr)
    else:
        conv_viol = np.array([])

    res.append({
        "expiry_utc": datetime.fromtimestamp(exp_ts/1000, tz=timezone.utc).strftime("%Y-%m-%d %H:%M:%S"),
        "T_days": float((g["T"].iloc[0]*365.0)),
        "n_strikes": int(len(g)),
        "merton_bounds_ok": bool(g["ok_bounds"].all()),
        "delta_bounds_ok": bool(g["ok_delta"].all()),
        "gamma_nonneg_ok": bool(g["ok_gamma"].all()),
        "vega_v0_nonneg_ok": bool(g["ok_vega"].all()),
        "mono_viol_cnt": int((mono_viol > 0).sum()),
        "conv_viol_cnt": int((conv_viol > 0).sum()),
        "mono_viol_max": float(mono_viol.max() if mono_viol.size else 0.0),
        "conv_viol_max": float(conv_viol.max() if conv_viol.size else 0.0),
    })
return pd.DataFrame(res)

# =====
# Main
# =====
if __name__ == "__main__":
    now_ms = int(time.time()*1000)

    # Underlying (USD)
    idx = get_json("/public/get_index_price", {"index_name": "btc_usd"})
    S0 = float(idx.get("index_price", idx.get("btc")))
    r, q = 0.02, 0.0

    # Gather up to M expiries (linear first, then inverse)
    M = 3 # how many expiries to analyze
    buckets = build_slice_linear(list_linear_btc_options(), now_ms, min_pts=8)
    if not buckets:
        buckets = build_slice_inverse(list_inverse_btc_options(), now_ms, S0, min_pts=8)
    if not buckets:

```

```

        raise SystemExit("No liquid call slices found (linear nor inverse). Try later

buckets = buckets[:M]

all_rows = []

for rows in buckets:
    df = pd.DataFrame(rows).sort_values("K").reset_index(drop=True)

    # ATM IV anchor
    atm_row = df.iloc[(df["K"] - S0).abs().argmin()]
    sigma_atm = bs IMPLIED_VOL_CALL(atm_row["mid_usd"], S0,
                                     float(atm_row["K"]), float(atm_row["T"]), r,
    hp = heston_params_near_bs(sigma_atm)

    # FFT params (tight): Simpson weights are inside cm_fft_grid_all
    ALPHA = 2.0
    N      = 2**16
    ETA    = 0.08
    dk     = 2.0*np.pi/(N*ETA)
    k0     = np.log(S0) - 0.5*N*dk # exact centering

    # Compute FFT prices/Greeks at market strikes
    def fft_tuple(row):
        P, D, G, Vv0 = price_greeks_fft_atK(
            S0, float(row.K), float(row.T), r, q,
            hp["v0"], hp["kappa"], hp["theta"], hp["sigma"], hp["rho"],
            alpha=ALPHA, N=N, eta=ETA, k0=k0
        )
        return float(P), float(D), float(G), float(Vv0)

    greeks = [fft_tuple(row) for row in df.itertuples(index=False)]
    gdf = pd.DataFrame(greeks, columns=["P_fft_usd", "Delta_usd", "Gamma_usd", "Vega_
    out = pd.concat([df.reset_index(drop=True), gdf], axis=1)

    # --- Merton/Greeks sanity bounds (USD) ---
    lower = np.maximum(S0*np.exp(-q*out["T"]) - out["K"]*np.exp(-r*out["T"]), 0.0
    upper = S0*np.exp(-q*out["T"])
    tolPrice = 1e-6 * S0 + 2e-3
    ok_bounds = (out["P_fft_usd"] >= lower - tolPrice) & (out["P_fft_usd"] <= upp
    tolUnit = 1e-3
    ok_delta = (out["Delta_usd"] >= -tolUnit) & (out["Delta_usd"] <= np.exp(-q*ou
    tolGamma = 5e-6
    ok_gamma = (out["Gamma_usd"] >= -tolGamma)
    ok_vega = (out["Vega_v0_usd"] >= -1e-3)

    out = out.assign(ok_bounds=ok_bounds, ok_delta=ok_delta, ok_gamma=ok_gamma, o

    # Print brief table for this expiry
    print("\n=== Expiry:", datetime.fromtimestamp(int(out['expiry'].iloc[0])/1000

```

```

        f"(rows={len(out)}) | ATM ~ {sigma_atm:.4f}")
show = out.copy()
show["T_days"] = (show["T"] * 365.0).round(2)
cols = ["instrument", "K", "T_days", "mid_usd", "P_fft_usd", "Delta_usd", "Gamma_usd",
        "ok_bounds", "ok_delta", "ok_gamma", "ok_vega"]
print(show[cols].to_string(index=False, float_format=lambda x: f"{x:,.6g}"))

all_rows.append(out)

# Concatenate expiries and run shape checks per expiry
big = pd.concat(all_rows, ignore_index=True)
shape_df = shape_checks_per_expiry(big, rel_tol=1e-3, abs_tol=2e-4)
print("\n--- Shape checks per expiry (market strikes) ---")
print(shape_df.to_string(index=False, float_format=lambda x: f"{x:,.6g}"))

# Slice-level pass/fail bars
labels = ["Merton bounds", "Delta bounds", "Gamma 0", r"Vega$_{v0}$ 0", "Monoto
pass_per_expiry = []
for _, row in shape_df.iterrows():
    flags = [
        bool(row["merton_bounds_ok"]),
        bool(row["delta_bounds_ok"]),
        bool(row["gamma_nonneg_ok"]),
        bool(row["vega_v0_nonneg_ok"]),
        row["mono_viol_cnt"] == 0,
        row["conv_viol_cnt"] == 0,
    ]
    pass_per_expiry.append(flags)
pass_per_expiry = np.array(pass_per_expiry, dtype=bool)

# Count how many expiries pass each test
pass_counts = pass_per_expiry.sum(axis=0)
fail_counts = len(shape_df) - pass_counts

x = np.arange(len(labels))
plt.figure()
plt.bar(x - 0.2, pass_counts, width=0.4, label="Pass")
plt.bar(x + 0.2, fail_counts, width=0.4, label="Fail")
plt.xticks(x, labels, rotation=20)
plt.ylabel("Number of expiries (pass/fail)")
plt.title("Sanity & shape checks: pass/fail (per expiry)")
plt.legend()
plt.tight_layout()
plt.savefig("bars_checks_pass_fail.png", dpi=150)
plt.close()

```

2.5. Single-batched FFT (our approach) speed and time median comparison.

```
# ===== Single-FFT vs Separate FFTs vs Quadrature benchmark (self-contained) =====
```

```

import numpy as np, time, math, pandas as pd

# --- Utilities
def simpson_weights(N:int)->np.ndarray:
    if N % 2 != 0:
        raise ValueError("N must be even for Simpson weights.")
    w = np.ones(N)
    w[1:-1:2] = 4.0
    w[2:-1:2] = 2.0
    return w/3.0

def carr_madan_kernel(u, alpha, r, T):
    i = 1j
    return np.exp(-r*T) / (alpha**2 + alpha - u**2 + i*(2*alpha+1)*u)

# Lord{Kahl \little trap" Heston CF and D(z,T)
def heston_cf_little_trap(xi, T, S0, r, q, kappa, theta, sigma, rho, v0):
    i = 1j
    d = np.sqrt((rho*sigma*i*xi - kappa)**2 + sigma**2*(i*xi + xi**2))
    g = (kappa - rho*sigma*i*xi - d) / (kappa - rho*sigma*i*xi + d)
    e = np.exp(-d*T)
    C = (r-q)*i*xi*T + (kappa*theta/sigma**2)*((kappa - rho*sigma*i*xi - d)*T - 2*np.
    D = ((kappa - rho*sigma*i*xi - d)/sigma**2) * ((1 - e)/(1 - g*e))
    return np.exp(C + D*v0 + i*xi*np.log(S0)), D

def build_integrand_matrix(N, eta, alpha, k0, T, S0, r, q, kappa, theta, sigma, rho, v0,
    """Build stacked integrand H (N x 4) ONCE so we can time only the FFT."""
    i = 1j
    u = np.arange(N)*eta
    xi = u - i*(alpha+1)
    Psi = carr_madan_kernel(u, alpha, r, T)
    phi, Dxi = heston_cf_little_trap(xi, T, S0, r, q, kappa, theta, sigma, rho, v0)
    w = simpson_weights(N)
    base = (Psi*phi*w*eta) * np.exp(-i*u*k0) # (N,)
    H = np.stack([
        base, # price
        base * (i*xi)/S0, # Delta
        base * (i*xi)*(i*xi - 1)/S0**2, # Gamma
        base * Dxi # Vega_{v0}
    ], axis=1) # (N,4)
    return H

# --- Core: single FFT for Price, Delta, Gamma, Vega_{v0}
def single_fft_all(N, eta, alpha, k0, T, S0, r, q, kappa, theta, sigma, rho, v0):
    i = 1j
    u = np.arange(N)*eta
    xi = u - i*(alpha+1)
    Psi = carr_madan_kernel(u, alpha, r, T)
    phi, Dxi = heston_cf_little_trap(xi, T, S0, r, q, kappa, theta, sigma, rho, v0)

```

```

w = simpson_weights(N)
base = (Psi*phi*w*eta) * np.exp(-i*u*k0) # (N,)
H = np.stack([
    base, # price
    base * (i*xi)/S0, # Delta
    base * (i*xi)*(i*xi - 1)/S0**2, # Gamma
    base * Dxi # Vega_{v0}
], axis=1) # (N,4)
F = np.fft.fft(H, axis=0) # <-- ONE FFT CALL
k = k0 + np.arange(N)*(2*np.pi/(N*eta))
scale = np.exp(-alpha*k)/np.pi
out = {
    'k': k,
    'Price': scale*np.real(F[:,0]),
    'Delta': scale*np.real(F[:,1]),
    'Gamma': scale*np.real(F[:,2]),
    'Vega_v0':scale*np.real(F[:,3]),
}
}
return out

def separate_ffts(N, eta, alpha, k0, T, S0, r, q, kappa, theta, sigma, rho, v0):
    i=1j
    u = np.arange(N)*eta
    xi = u - i*(alpha+1)
    Psi = carr_madan_kernel(u, alpha, r, T)
    phi, Dxi = heston_cf_little_trap(xi, T, S0, r, q, kappa, theta, sigma, rho, v0)
    w = simpson_weights(N)
    base = (Psi*phi*w*eta) * np.exp(-i*u*k0)
    cols = [
        base, # price
        base*(i*xi)/S0, # delta
        base*(i*xi)*(i*xi-1)/S0**2, # gamma
        base*Dxi, # vega_v0
    ]
    Fcols = [np.fft.fft(col, axis=0) for col in cols] # four calls
    k = k0 + np.arange(N)*(2*np.pi/(N*eta))
    scale = np.exp(-alpha*k)/np.pi
    out = {
        'k': k,
        'Price': scale*np.real(Fcols[0]),
        'Delta': scale*np.real(Fcols[1]),
        'Gamma': scale*np.real(Fcols[2]),
        'Vega_v0':scale*np.real(Fcols[3]),
    }
    }
    return out

def quadrature_at_strike(k, alpha, T, S0, r, q, kappa, theta, sigma, rho, v0, eta_q=0
    i=1j
    u = np.arange(0.0, umax+1e-12, eta_q)
    if len(u)%2: u=u[:-1]

```

```

xi = u - i*(alpha+1)
Psi = carr_madan_kernel(u, alpha, r, T)
phi, Dxi = heston_cf_little_trap(xi, T, S0, r, q, kappa, theta, sigma, rho, v0)
w = simpson_weights(len(u))
common = Psi*phi*np.exp(-i*u*k)*w*eta_q
scale = np.exp(-alpha*k)/np.pi
P = scale*np.real(np.sum(common))
D = scale*np.real(np.sum(common*(i*xi)/S0))
G = scale*np.real(np.sum(common*(i*xi)*(i*xi-1)/S0**2))
V = scale*np.real(np.sum(common*Dxi))
return {'Price':P, 'Delta':D, 'Gamma':G, 'Vega_v0':V}

# --- Parameters and run
pars = dict(S0=100.0, r=0.0, q=0.0, kappa=2.0, theta=0.04, sigma=0.6, rho=-0.7, v0=0.0)
T = 0.5
N = 2**12
eta = 0.25
alpha = 1.5
k0 = math.log(pars['S0']) - 3.0

# Warm-up once
_ = single_fft_all(N, eta, alpha, k0, T, **pars)
_ = separate_ffts(N, eta, alpha, k0, T, **pars)

# Timings (median of R repeats)
def median_time(fn, R=10):
    times=[]
    for _ in range(R):
        t0=time.perf_counter(); fn(); times.append(time.perf_counter()-t0)
    return 1000*np.median(times)

t_single = median_time(lambda: single_fft_all(N, eta, alpha, k0, T, **pars))
t_sep     = median_time(lambda: separate_ffts(N, eta, alpha, k0, T, **pars))
k_atm    = math.log(pars['S0'])
t_quad   = median_time(lambda: quadrature_at_strike(k_atm, alpha, T, **pars), R=5)

# Build and print table
df = pd.DataFrame([
    {'Method':'Quadrature (ATM, Simpson)', 'Calls':'--', 'Time_ms': t_quad},
    {'Method':'Separate FFTs (4 calls/grid)', 'Calls':'4', 'Time_ms': t_sep},
    {'Method':'Single batched FFT (grid)', 'Calls':'1', 'Time_ms': t_single},
])
df['Relative (vs quad)'] = df['Time_ms'] / df['Time_ms'].iloc[0]
print("\n=== Runtime comparison ===")
print(df.to_string(index=False))

# Save CSVs
df.to_csv('fft_timings_local.csv', index=False)
print("\nSaved timings to fft_timings_local.csv")

```

```

# Accuracy: single vs separate (max abs diff over grid)
out_single = single_fft_all(N, eta, alpha, k0, T, **pars)
out_sep     = separate_ffts(N, eta, alpha, k0, T, **pars)
max_abs = {q: float(np.max(np.abs(out_single[q]-out_sep[q]))) for q in ['Price','Delta']}
print("\nMax |single - separate| over grid:", max_abs)

# Accuracy vs quadrature at ATM
k_grid = out_single['k']; idx = int(np.argmin(np.abs(k_grid - k_atm)))
atm_fft = {q: out_single[q][idx] for q in ['Price','Delta','Gamma','Vega_v0']}
atm_quad = quadrature_at_strike(k_atm, alpha, T, **pars)
atm_diff = {q: float(abs(atm_fft[q]-atm_quad[q])) for q in atm_fft}
acc_df = pd.DataFrame({
    'Quantity': ['Price','Delta','Gamma','Vega_v0'],
    'MaxAbsDiff_Single_vs_Separate': [max_abs['Price'],max_abs['Delta'],max_abs['Gamma'],max_abs['Vega_v0']],
    'ATM_AbsDiff_FFT_vs_Quadrature': [atm_diff['Price'],atm_diff['Delta'],atm_diff['Gamma'],atm_diff['Vega_v0']]
})
print("\n=== Accuracy checks ===")
print(acc_df.to_string(index=False))
acc_df.to_csv('fft_accuracy_local.csv', index=False)
print("\nSaved accuracy to fft_accuracy_local.csv")
# ===== End =====

def time_stats(callable_fn, R=30):
    """Return median/IQR/min/max (ms) over R repeats."""
    times = []
    callable_fn() # warm-up
    for _ in range(R):
        t0 = time.perf_counter()
        callable_fn()
        t1 = time.perf_counter()
        times.append(1000*(t1 - t0))
    times = np.array(times, float)
    return {
        'median_ms': float(np.median(times)),
        'iqr_ms': float(np.percentile(times, 75) - np.percentile(times, 25)),
        'min_ms': float(np.min(times)),
        'max_ms': float(np.max(times)),
        'repeats': int(R),
    }

def run_fft_benchmark(N_list, eta, alpha, k0, T, pars, R=30, save_csv=True, save_plot=True):
    """
    Compares SINGLE batched FFT vs FOUR separate FFTs.
    Times ONLY the FFT work (integrand build excluded).
    - N_list: list of sizes, e.g. [2**11, 2**12, 2**13]
    - R: repeats per configuration (use 10, 30, 100...)
    """
    rows = []
    for N in N_list:
        # 1) build integrands once
        H = build_integrand_matrix(N, eta, alpha, k0, T, **pars)

```

```

# SINGLE FFT (make axis contiguous to avoid stride penalty)
Hf = np.asfortranarray(H) # axis=0 contiguous in memory
def single_fft_call():
    _ = np.fft.fft(Hf, axis=0)
s1 = time_stats(single_fft_call, R=R)

# FOUR SEPARATE FFTs
cols = [H[:,i].copy() for i in range(4)]
def four_ffts_call():
    _ = [np.fft.fft(c, axis=0) for c in cols]
s4 = time_stats(four_ffts_call, R=R)

rows.append({'N':N, 'method':'single_batched', **s1})
rows.append({'N':N, 'method':'separate_four', **s4})

df = pd.DataFrame(rows)

# pretty print a compact median/IQR view
def fmt(x): return f"{x['median_ms']:.2f} ms (IQR {x['iqr_ms']:.2f})"
print("\n=== Median (IQR) over {} repeats ===".format(R))
for N in N_list:
    s = df[(df.N==N) & (df.method=='single_batched')].iloc[0]
    f = df[(df.N==N) & (df.method=='separate_four')].iloc[0]
    print(f"N={N}: single={fmt(s)} | four={fmt(f)}")

# optional CSV
stamp = f"_{tag}" if tag else ""
if save_csv:
    out_csv = f"fft_benchmark_median_iqr{stamp}.csv"
    df.to_csv(out_csv, index=False)
    print(f"\nSaved CSV -> {out_csv}")

# optional plot (median vs N)
if save_plot:
    out_png = f"fft_benchmark_median_plot{stamp}.png"
    import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
    plt.figure(figsize=(7,4.5))
    for method,label in [('single_batched','single batched'),('separate_four','separate four')]
        sub = df[df.method==method]
        plt.plot(sub['N'], sub['median_ms'], marker='o', label=label)
    plt.xlabel('N'); plt.ylabel('Median time (ms)')
    plt.title(f'FFT timing (median over {R} repeats)')
    plt.legend()
    plt.tight_layout()
    plt.savefig(out_png, dpi=150)
    plt.close()
    print(f"Saved plot -> {out_png}")

return df

```

```
# --- Parameters (keep yours)
pars = dict(S0=100.0, r=0.0, q=0.0, kappa=2.0, theta=0.04, sigma=0.6, rho=-0.7, v0=0.
T = 0.5
N_list = [2**11, 2**12, 2**13] # add more if you want
eta = 0.25
alpha = 1.5
k0 = math.log(pars['S0']) - 3.0

# run with 10 repeats:
run_fft_benchmark(N_list, eta, alpha, k0, T, pars, R=10, tag="R10")

# run with 100 repeats (heavier):
run_fft_benchmark(N_list, eta, alpha, k0, T, pars, R=100, tag="R100")
```


Appendix 3 - A brief history and development of the Heston Model and FFT-based Option Pricing

The development of option pricing theory began with the seminal work of Black and Scholes [2] and Merton [26], who introduced a continuous-time framework in which asset prices follow a geometric Brownian motion with constant volatility. This assumption of constant variance allowed for elegant closed-form solutions but was soon found to be empirically inadequate: market option prices systematically exhibit *volatility smiles* and *skews*, phenomena incompatible with a single, fixed volatility parameter. The early recognition of these discrepancies motivated researchers such as Hull and White [21], Wiggins [32], and Scott [30] to extend the Black–Scholes model by allowing volatility itself to evolve randomly through time.

The modern stochastic volatility framework was formalized by Heston [20], who derived a closed-form solution for European option prices under a mean-reverting square-root process for the instantaneous variance. The Heston model provided a tractable structure that could reproduce both volatility smiles and the observed clustering of variance in financial time series. Subsequent refinements addressed technical challenges such as numerical stability and characteristic-function evaluation, notably the “Little Heston Trap” discussed by Albrecher et al. [1] and the logarithmic branch corrections proposed by Lord and Kahl [24]. Further empirical and theoretical validation of the model was explored by Cui et al. [13, 14] and more recently by Cao and Lin [6].

In parallel, numerical research focused on efficient and accurate valuation techniques. Carr and Madan [9] demonstrated that option prices can be computed via the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT), an algorithmic idea originally introduced by Cooley and Tukey [12] and popularized by Brigham [4]. Fang and Oosterlee [16] later refined this approach through the Fourier–Cosine (COS) method, offering improved accuracy and convergence. Modern implementations rely on optimized FFT libraries [18, 17] and have been extended to sensitivity computation through adjoint algorithmic differentiation [7, 8]. This thesis builds upon these theoretical and numerical foundations to investigate the behaviour of FFT-based Greeks in the Heston stochastic volatility model, assessing both computational efficiency and numerical stability in the context of contemporary option-pricing practice.